

**A CRITICAL COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE
NATIONAL ACCREDITATION STANDARDS FOR
HOSPITALS OF INDIA, AUSTRALIA, DENMARK
AND SOUTH AFRICA**

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**THE UNIVERSAL HEALTHCARE QUALITY
STANDARDS FOR GENERAL HOSPITALS**

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INTRODUCTION

Healthcare is the fundamental need and right of every single human being on this planet. The healthcare quality needs are the same all over the world, and providing the quality healthcare services is the vision of each public and private healthcare service provider, for which they follow the National and or International Healthcare Accreditation Standards for their hospitals. Unfortunately, the World Health Organization (WHO), who monitors the health issues in the public sector of the world doesn't have a unique, comprehensive set of hospital quality standards applicable, available and accessible for all general hospitals in the private and public sectors of the world till date.

Hence, the researcher has taken this opportunity as one of the objectives of this research was to propose an outline of "The Universal Healthcare Quality Standards for General Hospitals". Hence, the researcher has developed these healthcare quality standards based on his experience and knowledge gained in the foreign countries as he is working for healthcare accreditations and successfully achieved 97 national and international healthcare accreditations.

The researcher has divided these chapters in two sections namely, Clinical and Non-Clinical. There are 11 chapters under the Clinical Chapters Section and 10 chapters under the Non-Clinical Chapters Section. Each Measurable Element should be scored as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met.

This proposed standards will be helpful to improve the NABH Standards of India and the rest of the countries in the world as well. Also, the WHO can adopt the proposed outline of the "The Universal Healthcare Quality Standards for General Hospitals".

CHAPTER-1

ACCESS TO CARE AND CONTINUITY OF CARE (ACC)

- 1. Lifts or ramps are available in multi-storey buildings for patients unable to use the stairs.**
 - A. The healthcare services being provided are clearly defined and are in consonance with the needs of the community.
 - B. Each defined service should have appropriate diagnostics and treatment facilities with suitably qualified personnel who provide out-patient, in-patient and emergency cover
 - C. The defined healthcare services are prominently displayed
 - D. The staff are oriented to these services.

- 2. The organisation has a well-defined registration and admission process.**
 - A. Documented policies and procedures are used for registering and admitting patients.
 - B. The documented procedures address out-patients, in-patients and emergency patients
 - C. A unique identification number is generated at the end of registration
 - D. Patients are accepted only if the organisation can provide the required service
 - E. The documented policies and procedures also address managing patients during non-availability of beds
 - F. Access to the healthcare services in the organisation is prioritised according to the clinical needs of the patient.
 - G. The staff are aware of these processes.

- 3. There is a process for admitting patients to inpatient facilities.**
 - A. There is a process known to personnel for admitting patients to the hospital.
 - B. The unit which accepts the patient for admission is noted in the patient record.
 - C. The time that the patient is accepted to the inpatient unit and the time the patient is transferred are documented in the patient record.
 - D. Holding times in the unit while awaiting transfer are monitored.
 - E. Policies and procedures that address the management of patients when bed space is not available in the desired service or unit or elsewhere in the hospital are implemented.

- 4. Admission or transfer to units providing intensive or specialised services is determined by established criteria.**
 - A. The hospital has established entry and/or transfer criteria for its oncology units, to meet specialised patient needs.

- B. There are guidelines for the medical responsibility on admission and treatment in intensive therapy unit.
 - C. The criteria are physiological where possible and appropriate.
 - D. Appropriate individuals are involved in developing the criteria.
 - E. Personnel are trained to apply the criteria.
 - F. Patients transferred or admitted to intensive and specialised units/services meet the criteria, as documented in the patient's record.
- 5. There is a system to ensure that patients are seen within the shortest possible time in out-patients, units and wards.**
- A. There is a screening process to separate those patients requiring emergency care from those requiring only outpatient services.
 - B. There is a process of registration for outpatient care and treatment.
 - C. The outpatient register contains at least the patient's name, patient specific identification number, age, gender, date and time of attendance, treatment, procedures, referral or death.
 - D. There is an appointment system for outpatient patients.
 - E. Patients who are waiting are advised of any delays that may be experienced in receiving attention.
 - F. Waiting times are monitored as part of the hospital's quality management and improvement programme.
 - G. The hospital implements policies and procedures for assessing patients referred to therapeutic support services.
- 6. There is an appropriate mechanism for transfer (in and out) or referral of patients.**
- A. Documented policies and procedures guide the transfer-in of patients to the organisation.
 - B. Documented policies and procedures guide the transfer-out/referral of unstable patients to another facility in an appropriate manner.
 - C. Documented policies and procedures guide the transfer- out/ referral of stable patients to another facility in an appropriate manner.
 - D. The documented procedures identify staff responsible during transfer/ referral.
 - E. The organisation gives a summary of patient's condition and the treatment given.
 - F. The hospital has targets for the quality of the transfer between departments and hospitals, and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.
 - G. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the information on transfer between departments and hospitals. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they

had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.

7. The hospital sets up and reports requirements to referrals from the primary sector.

- A. There are guidelines for the content of referrals of acute as well as electively referred patients to the hospital's services.
- B. Requirements to referrals are easily accessible for referring doctors, e.g. on hospital's websites or in relevant information systems for practises.
- C. The hospital has targets for the quality of the referrals and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.
- D. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the referrals. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.

8. There is a process known to personnel to refer patients for specialised consultation, investigations and/or treatment at other healthcare organisations.

- A. Policies and procedures that guide the movement of patients for referral to another organisation are implemented.
- B. A copy of the referral note is available in the patient record.
- C. Follow-up care based on the findings of investigations and/or consultations performed outside the referring hospital is documented in the patient record.

9. The treatment of the electively referred patient is managed by a treatment plan systematically adjusted on the basis on an on-going assessment of the patient.

- A. There is a description of which types of electively referred patients the hospital can receive.
- B. There are guidelines for reception and medical assessment of a referral.
- C. There are guidelines for letter of appointment of electively referred patients for treatment. The guidelines ensure that the content of the letters of appointment and the like meet the requirements in the legislation and the agreements. The guidelines ensure that time limits in the legislation and the agreements are met.
- D. There are guidelines for preparation and content of a treatment plan for the individual electively referred patient. The treatment plan could be a standardised programme which to a relevant extent is adjusted in collaboration with the patient and relatives, if any.

- E. There are guidelines for when to re-assess a treatment plan.
- F. The hospital's description of the types of electively referred patient which can be received is public.
- G. Medical assessment of received referrals takes place according to the hospital's guidelines.
- H. Electively referred patients receive a letter of appointment for treatment in accordance with the hospital's guidelines and requirements in the legislation and agreements.
- I. There is a treatment plan for the individual patient. The treatment plan is prepared within the determined time frame stipulated by the hospital and meets the time limits in the legislation and agreements.
- J. The individual treatment plan is re-assessed according to the hospital's guidelines.
- K. The hospital has targets for the quality of the treatment of electively referred patients and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.
- L. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the treatment of electively referred patients. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.

10. There is a process to transfer patients to another healthcare organisation to meet their continuing needs.

- A. There is a documented process for transferring patients to other healthcare organisations (for specialised and support services).
- B. Patients are stabilised according to appropriate clinical guidelines prior to transfer.
- C. The transferring hospital determines that the receiving healthcare organisation can meet the patient's continuing care needs and establishes arrangements to ensure continuity.
- D. The process for transferring the patient considers transportation needs.
- E. A policy that requires the responsible clinician to communicate the level of care required to Emergency Medical (ambulance) services is implemented.
- F. The process determines that patients are accompanied and monitored by an appropriately qualified person during transfer.
- G. When a patient is transferred to another healthcare organisation, the receiving organisation is given a written summary of the patient's clinical condition and the interventions provided by the referring hospital.
- H. A copy of the transfer summary is available in the patient record.
- I. The hospital agreeing to receive the patient is noted in the patient's record.

11. Patient care is continuous and multidisciplinary in nature.

- A. During all phases of care, there is a qualified individual identified as responsible for the patient's care.
- B. Information about the patient's care and response to treatment is shared among medical, nursing and other care-providers.
- C. Information is exchanged and documented during each staffing shift, between shifts, and during transfers between units/ departments.
- D. Transfers between departments/ units are done in a safe manner.
- E. The patient's record(s) is available to the authorised care-providers to facilitate the exchange of information.
- F. The organisation has a mechanism in place to monitor whether adequate clinical intervention has taken place in response to a critical value alert.

12. Collaboration and teamwork

- A. The health service organisation has processes to:
 - Support multidisciplinary collaboration and teamwork
 - Define the roles and responsibilities of each clinician working in a team
- B. Clinicians work collaboratively to plan and deliver comprehensive care

13. Designing systems to deliver comprehensive care

- A. The health service organisation has systems for comprehensive care that:
 - Support clinicians to develop, document and communicate comprehensive plans for patients' care and treatment
 - Provide care to patients in the setting that best meets their clinical needs
 - Ensure timely referral of patients with specialist healthcare needs to relevant services
 - Identify, at all times, the clinician with overall accountability for a patient's care

14. The service is organised to provide a safe and effective service and is coordinated with other relevant services.

- A. An on-call roster is available for after-hours, weekend and holiday emergency cover (e.g. for infectious diseases)

15. The hospital designs and implements processes to provide continuity of patient care services within the hospital and coordination among health professionals.

- A. Policies and procedures that guide the movement of patients within the hospital are implemented.

- B. Documentation regarding the transfer of a patient from the forensic service to another service within the hospital meets legal requirements.

16. Developing the comprehensive care plan

- A. Clinicians use processes for shared decision making to develop and document a comprehensive and individualised plan that:
 - Addresses the significance and complexity of the patient's health
 - issues and risks of harm
 - Identifies agreed goals and actions for the patient's treatment and care
 - Identifies the support people a patient wants involved in communications and decision-making about their care
 - Commences discharge planning at the beginning of the episode of care
 - Includes a plan for referral to follow-up services, if appropriate and available
 - Is consistent with best practice and evidence

17. The organisation has a documented discharge process.

- A. The patient's discharge process is planned in consultation with the patient and/or family.
- B. Documented procedures exist for coordination of various departments and agencies involved in the discharge process (including medico-legal and absconded cases).
- C. Documented policies and procedures are in place for patients leaving against medical advice and patients being discharged on request.
- D. A discharge summary is given to all the patients leaving the organisation (including patients leaving against medical advice and on request).
- E. The organisation defines the time taken for discharge and monitors the same.
- F. The hospital has targets for the quality of discharge planning in collaboration with the patient and the hospital assesses whether the goal/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.
- G. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of discharge by planning in collaboration with the patient. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.

18. Organisation defines the content of the discharge summary.

- A. Discharge summary is provided to the patients at the time of discharge.
- B. Discharge summary contains the patient's name, unique identification number, date of admission and date of discharge.

- C. Discharge summary contains the reasons for admission, significant findings and diagnosis and the patient's condition at the time of discharge.
- D. Discharge summary contains information regarding investigation results, any procedure performed, medication administered and other treatment given.
- E. Discharge summary contains follow-up advice, medication and other instructions in an understandable manner.
- F. Discharge summary incorporates instructions about when and how to obtain urgent care.
- G. In case of death, the summary of the case also includes the cause of death.
- H. The hospital has targets for the deadlines for forwarding of discharge letters in accordance with national and regionally determined targets. The hospital observes the deadlines for forwarding discharge letters on an on-going basis.
- I. The hospital has targets for the quality of the content of discharge letters and the hospital assesses whether the targets/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.
- J. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the discharge letters. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.

19. There is an organised process to discharge patients from wards and Emergency Department

- A. There is a documented process to discharge patients.
- B. Where the initial assessment indicates that discharge planning will be required, planning requirements are included in the patient's care plan and completed as scheduled.
- C. The hospital works with the family, caregivers, healthcare practitioners and agencies outside the hospital to ensure timely and appropriate discharge.
- D. Patients and where appropriate their families or caregivers are given understandable follow-up instructions which are documented in the patient's record.
- E. A discharge summary is written by the medical practitioner when each patient is discharged.
- F. Each record contains a copy of the discharge summary.

20. A system of visitor control is maintained to ensure the safety of patients and personnel.

- A. The hospital's policy on visitors to the emergency department is implemented.

- B. There is a system to inform patients and family of the visitors' policy.
- C. Areas where access is denied to persons other than personnel are clearly marked.
- D. The discretionary powers of personnel in charge of the service relating to visitors under special circumstances are documented.
- E. Policies regarding media invasion are implemented to guide clinical and security personnel.

21. The hospital has established processes for admitting inpatients and registering ambulatory patients.

- A. Admission and registration processes are standardised throughout the hospital by means of the development and implementation of policies and procedures.
- B. Policies and procedures for the management of patients deceased prior to arrival are implemented.
- C. General consent / acknowledgement of admission requirements is obtained when patients enter the hospital according to hospital policy.
- D. Written consent for the taking and/or publishing of photographic images is obtained from personnel, volunteers, patients and visitors prior to such images being taken.
- E. Patients receive information on the hospital's level of responsibility for patients' possessions.

22. The hospital seeks to identify and reduce barriers to access and delivery of services.

- A. The hospital has identified barriers to accessing healthcare services in its catchment population.
- B. There is a process to limit the impact of barriers on access to the services provided by the hospital.
- C. The hospital has access to ambulance services appropriate for the level of care provided.

CHAPTER-2
ASSESSMENT OF PATIENT (AOP)

- 1. Each patient has an initial assessment that complies with current policies, procedures and guidelines.**
 - A. Each patient admitted has an initial assessment according to hospital policy.
 - B. The initial assessment includes health history.
 - C. The initial assessment includes physical examination.
 - D. The initial assessment includes functional and nutritional examination, where applicable.
 - E. The initial assessment includes social and economic assessment, where applicable.
 - F. The initial assessment includes psychological assessment, where applicable.
 - G. The initial assessment includes cultural assessment, where applicable.
 - H. The initial assessment includes antenatal history.
 - I. The initial assessment includes maternal and foetal examination.
 - J. The initial assessment results in an initial diagnosis.
 - K. The patient's medical, nursing and other healthcare needs identified during the initial assessment are documented.
 - L. Discharge planning is commenced with the initial assessment and involves the patient and their family or carers.
 - M. Where appropriate, treatment planning is done in collaboration with the patient's family and/or carers.
 - N. Patients admitted to the unit against their will are assessed, admitted and cared for in accordance with legislative requirements.

- 2. Allergy and intolerance**
 - A. There are guidelines for documentation of known allergy
 - B. There are guidelines for documentation of known intolerance.
 - C. Known allergy and intolerance are documented in the patient health record.
 - D. Known allergy and intolerance are communicated to relevant professionals.
 - E. The hospital has targets for the quality of documentation of allergy and intolerance. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets. Data are analysed and assessed.

- 3. Planning for comprehensive care**
 - A. The health service organisation has processes relevant to the patients using the service and the services provided:
 - For integrated and timely screening and assessment

- That identify the risks of harm in the ‘Minimising patient harm’ criterion
- B. Patients are supported to document clear advance care plans
 - C. Clinicians use relevant screening processes:
 - On presentation, during clinical examination and history taking, and when required during care
 - To identify cognitive, behavioural, mental and physical conditions, issues, and risks of harm
 - To identify social and other circumstances that may compound these risks
 - D. Clinicians comprehensively assess the conditions and risks identified through the screening process
 - E. Clinicians document the findings of the screening and clinical assessment processes, including any relevant alerts, in the healthcare record
 - F. The workforce, patients, carers and families work in partnership to:
 - Use the comprehensive care plan to deliver care
 - Monitor the effectiveness of the comprehensive care plan in meeting the goals of care
 - Review and update the comprehensive care plan if it is not effective d. Reassess the patient’s needs if changes in diagnosis, behaviour, cognition, or mental or physical condition occur
- 4. Patients cared for by the organisation undergo an established initial assessment.**
- A. The organisation defines and documents the content of the initial assessment for the out-patients, in-patients and emergency patients.
 - B. The organisation determines who can perform the initial assessment.
 - C. The organisation defines the time frame within which the initial assessment is completed based on patient’s needs.
 - D. The initial assessment for in-patients is documented within 24 hours or earlier as per the patient’s condition, as defined in the organisation’s policy.
 - E. Initial assessment of in-patients includes nursing assessment which is done at the time of admission and documented.
 - F. Initial assessment includes screening for nutritional needs.
 - G. The initial assessment results in a documented care plan.
 - H. The care plan reflects desired results of the treatment, care or service.
 - I. The care plan is countersigned by the clinician in-charge of the patient within 24 hours.

5. The patients' nutritional risk is assessed and they get an adjusted nutrition.

- A. There are guidelines for nutritional screening with a view to identify patients with special nutritional risk.
- B. There are guidelines for initiation of plan for nutrition and follow-up for patients in nutritional risk. If the effort is performed in collaboration with external parties, the division of responsibility and tasks will be described.
- C. Nutritional screening is performed in accordance with the guidelines in element 1 of the standard.
- D. Patients in nutritional risk, which is directly significant for the treatment outcome, are offered relevant intervention (plan for nutrition). Other patients in nutritional risk are offered intervention or counselling on where to request intervention.
- E. Nutrition plan and follow-up are documented in the patient health record.
- F. The hospital has targets for the quality of the effort for patients with nutritional risk, and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.
- G. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality for patients with nutritional risk. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.

6. The hospital identifies patients who need a rehabilitation plan and prepares rehabilitation plans for them.

- A. There are guidelines for systematic assessment of the rehabilitation need.
- B. There are guidelines for preparation of rehabilitation plans for outpatient recovery in the municipality and outpatient specialised recovery at hospital. The guidelines describe how the recovery plans are passed on to the primary sector.
- C. Relevant patients have their rehabilitation need assessed.
- D. Rehabilitation plans are prepared in accordance with the guidelines in element 2 of the standard.
- E. The hospital has targets for the preparation of the rehabilitation plans The hospital collects quantitative data which illustrate whether rehabilitation plans are prepared when it is relevant. Data are analysed and assessed.
- F. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the preparation of rehabilitation plans. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.

- 7. All patients cared for by the hospital have their healthcare needs identified through an established assessment process.**
 - A. Hospital policies and procedures for assessing patients on admission and during ongoing care are implemented.
 - B. Only those individuals permitted by applicable laws and regulations or by registration perform the assessments.
 - C. The scope and content of assessment by each discipline is defined.
 - D. Assessments are performed within appropriate time frames and are comprehensively documented in the patients' records according to hospital policy.
 - E. Agreements are in place with the nearest psychiatric unit to ensure appropriate, expedited care for psychiatric patients.
 - F. Assessments completed entirely outside the hospital are verified on admission to the service

- 8. Patients cared for by the organisation undergo a regular reassessment.**
 - A. Patients are reassessed at appropriate intervals.
 - B. Out-patients are informed of their next follow-up, where appropriate.
 - C. For in-patients during reassessment the care plan is monitored and modified, where found necessary.
 - D. Staff involved in direct clinical care document reassessments.
 - E. Patients are reassessed to determine their response to treatment and to plan further treatment or discharge.
 - F. The organisation lays down guidelines and implements processes to identify early warning signs of change or deterioration in clinical conditions for initiating prompt intervention.

- 9. Healthcare professionals responsible for patient care collaborate to analyse and integrate assessment information.**
 - A. Assessment findings are documented in the patient's record and are readily available to those responsible for the patient's care.
 - B. Patient assessment data and information are analysed and integrated by those responsible for the patient's care and used to develop the treatment plan, which includes the goals of care.
 - C. Patient needs are prioritised on the basis of assessment results.
 - D. The patient and/or the family participate in the decisions regarding the priority needs to be met.

- 10. The delivery of services is integrated and coordinated amongst care providers.**
 - A. The patient's clinical records are completed according to hospital policy.
 - B. The patient's records are up to date to ensure the transfer of the latest information between care providers.

- C. Information exchanged includes a summary of the initial assessment, summary of care provided and the results of diagnostic tests.
- D. Information exchanged includes the patient's progress.
- E. The author can be identified for each patient record entry.
- F. The date of each patient record entry can be identified.
- G. Patient handover between healthcare professionals is standardised according to hospital policy.
- H. The time of each patient record entry can be identified.
- I. Patient care plans are formulated collaboratively by all healthcare professionals involved in the patient's care.
- J. Patient needs are prioritised on the basis of assessment results.
- K. The team conducts periodic re-evaluation of each patient's plan of care to determine whether established goals are being or have been met and whether change in the patient's condition requires modification of goals.
- L. A designated individual is responsible for the coordination and integration of care for each patient.
- M. The multidisciplinary team meets regularly to coordinate patient care.
- N. The care provided by the multidisciplinary team is documented according to hospital policy.
- O. There is a multidisciplinary approach to the development and implementation of a therapeutic programme in accordance with a policy framework.
- P. The team consists of appropriately qualified personnel and includes representatives from all services offering care to the patient.
- Q. Each patient's care is coordinated by a designated individual who is appointed by the team and made known to the patient.
- R. The team members' responsibilities include development and implementation of care plans for each patient, based on the assessment of the patient.
- S. The team conducts periodic re-evaluation of each patient's plan of care to determine whether established goals are being or have been met and whether change in the patient's condition requires modification of goals.
- T. The team includes the patient and his/her family in the development and review of the plan of care, as appropriate.

11. The treatment of acute patients is managed by a treatment plan which is systematically adjusted based on an on-going assessment of the patient.

- A. There are guidelines for which types of acute patients the hospital can receive. The guidelines describe any variations during day and night.
- B. There are guidelines for the preliminary assessment of the patient. The guidelines describe content and deadline for the assessment.
- C. There are guidelines for preparation and content of the treatment plan for the individual acute patient, including observation plan for the following

period. As far as possible, the plan is prepared by involving the patient and the relatives, if any.

- D. The hospital's guidelines for which types of acute patients can be received are available for the referring part.
- E. A preliminary assessment is performed of the patient at his/her arrival at the hospital.
- F. There is a treatment plan for the individual patient. The treatment plan is prepared within the determined time frame stipulated by the hospital and includes observation plan.
- G. The individual patient is re-assessed according to the hospital's guidelines.
- H. The hospital has targets for the quality of the treatment of the individual acute patient, and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.
- I. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the treatment of the individual acute patient. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.

12. Patients' need for recovery is assessed and when needed an effort is offered.

- A. There are guidelines for assessment and initiation of recovery for relevant patient groups. If the effort is performed in collaboration with external parties, the division of responsibility and tasks will be described.
- B. Patients who need recovery are offered a relevant recovery effort.
- C. The hospital has target for the quality of the recovery effort and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.
- D. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the recovery effort. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.

13. Documentation of information

- A. The health service organisation has processes to contemporaneously document information in the healthcare record, including:
 - **Critical information, alerts and risks**
 - **Reassessment processes and outcomes**
 - **Changes to the care plan**

14. The hospital identifies patients who need a rehabilitation plan and prepares rehabilitation plans for them.

- A. There are guidelines for systematic assessment of the rehabilitation need.
- B. There are guidelines for preparation of rehabilitation plans for outpatient recovery in the municipality and outpatient specialised recovery at hospital.
- C. Relevant patients have their rehabilitation need assessed.
- D. Rehabilitation plans are prepared in accordance with the standard.
- E. The hospital has targets for the preparation of the rehabilitation plans The hospital collects quantitative data which illustrate whether rehabilitation plans are prepared when it is relevant. Data are analysed and assessed.
- F. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the preparation of rehabilitation plans. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.

15. Patients' health-related risk is assessed on the basis of life style factors. Relevant patients are offered intervention.

- A. The hospital has a policy for prevention and health promotion describing defined goals and prioritisations for the effort at the area and how to clarify them for the staff, patients and relatives.
- B. There are guidelines for health-related risk assessment of patients describing how the hospital identifies patients, where an intervention in relation to life style factors is significant for the outcome of the patient pathway, or where life style factors otherwise pose a considerable risk for the patient.
- C. There are guidelines for implementation of intervention regarding life style factors which are significant for the outcome of the patient pathway or where life style factors otherwise pose a risk for the patient. If the intervention takes place in collaboration with external parties, the division of responsibility and tasks will be described
- D. Patients with life style factors significant for the outcome of the patient pathway are offered intervention.
- E. Other patients in risk related to life style factors are offered intervention or counselling on where to request intervention.
- F. The hospital has targets for the quality of the effort for prevention and health promotion, and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.
- G. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality for patients with nutritional risk. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.

CHAPTER- 3
CARE OF PATIENTS (COP)

- 1. Uniform care to patients is provided in all settings of the organisation and is guided by the applicable laws, regulations and guidelines.**
 - A. Care delivery is uniform for a given health problem when similar care is provided in more than one setting.
 - B. Uniform care is guided by documented policies and procedures.
 - C. These reflect applicable laws, regulations and guidelines.
 - D. The organisation adapts evidence-based medicine and clinical practice guidelines to guide uniform patient care.

- 2. During all phases of care, there are qualified individuals responsible for the patient's care.**
 - A. An appropriately qualified individual has clearly defined responsibilities and accountability for all aspects of the service.
 - B. The individuals responsible for the patient's care are designated.
 - C. The individuals responsible for patient care are qualified.
 - D. The individuals responsible for patient care are identified and made known to the patient and other personnel.
 - E. The requirements of antenatal, labour and postnatal wards and nurseries are individually included in the staffing requirements.
 - F. A registered midwife and/or medical practitioner is present at every birth.
 - G. Healthcare professionals, specifically doctors and nurses, indicate that they have access to adequate supervision.
 - H. Specialists are available for consultation.
 - I. At least one person is available at all times who is qualified (medical practitioner or advanced midwife) in the management of maternal and neonatal emergencies.
 - J. Staffing of the service complies with accepted staffing norms for critical care services.
 - K. During the hours of operation there is an adequate number of qualified professionals available to provide continuous cover to all sections at all times.
 - L. Emergency services personnel maintain skills in advanced life support in accordance with hospital policy.
 - M. Medical cover is reflected on a roster and each practitioner on the roster is contactable by telephone, pager or other two-way communication method.
 - N. Arrangements are in place to ensure that specialist consultation services are available.
 - O. Mechanisms for contacting medical practitioners who treat private patients in the hospital are known to personnel.

- 3. Clinical practice guidelines are used to guide patient care and reduce undesirable variation.**
 - A. Evidence-based clinical practice guidelines relevant to the patients and services of the hospital are available to guide patient care processes.
 - B. The implementation of guidelines is monitored as part of a structured clinical audit.
 - C. Guidelines are reviewed on a regular basis and updated when necessary and according to hospital policy.
 - D. Clinical practice guidelines include protocols for time-critical states
 - E. Guidelines are reviewed and adapted on a regular basis.

- 4. Documented policies and procedures guide the care of patients requiring cardio-pulmonary resuscitation and it is performed according to clinical evidence based practice.**
 - A. Documented policies and procedures guide the uniform use of resuscitation throughout the organisation.
 - B. It is documented that the staff has completed training and maintains training in relation to cardiopulmonary resuscitation at the level which the management has decided.
 - C. The events during a cardiopulmonary resuscitation are recorded.
 - D. A post-event analysis of all cardiopulmonary resuscitations is done by a multidisciplinary committee.
 - E. Corrective and preventive measures are taken based on the post-event analysis.
 - F. There are guidelines for cardiopulmonary resuscitation for adults, children and new-born babies which are common for the entire hospital. The guidelines are prepared in accordance with the latest national guidelines.
 - G. The staff is familiar with its own tasks and responsibilities on cardiac arrest.

- 5. A resuscitation committee coordinates the management of resuscitation equipment, procedures and training systems.**
 - A. The hospital identifies a resuscitation committee to advise on the resuscitation equipment required and the procedures to be followed.
 - B. Each committee member's responsibility for resuscitation is documented in a job description.
 - C. A suitably qualified and experienced health professional is appointed as the resuscitation coordinator.
 - D. The medical equipment coordinator is on the committee.
 - E. A designated individual provides information, instruction and training on resuscitation to the personnel of the hospital.
 - F. The committee checks and documents that systems for the provision of emergency power are regularly checked according to hospital policy.

- G. The committee checks and documents that systems for the supply of gases and vacuum are regularly checked according to hospital policy.
 - H. A member of the resuscitation committee visits all clinical departments where resuscitation equipment is kept at least monthly to monitor that requirements relating to resuscitation medication, supplies and equipment are met.
 - I. Records of these visits are kept, with reports on problems experienced, advice given and any remedial action taken.
 - J. Policies and procedures relating to the acquisition, maintenance and checking of resuscitation equipment are implemented.
- 6. Essential resuscitation equipment and medications are available in each patient care area.**
- A. The hospital has an updated list of equipment required for resuscitation.
 - B. Recommended appliances are available for specialised resuscitations
 - C. Diagnostic and vital sign monitoring equipment is available as per hospital policy
 - D. The committee ensures that resuscitation equipment is readily accessible to every patient care area in the hospital.
 - E. The committee checks and documents that resuscitation equipment and drugs are checked daily, or immediately after use (whichever is the sooner), by persons identified to be responsible for this.
- 7. All personnel are suitably trained and educated to provide resuscitation and competencies are regularly tested.**
- A. The resuscitation committee develops a continuing education strategy to ensure that all personnel in the hospital are trained in cardio-pulmonary resuscitation.
 - B. There is evidence that all members of the resuscitation committee, as well as relevant personnel, attend courses and seminars on resuscitation and that records of attendance are kept.
 - C. New healthcare professionals employed in patient care areas are provided with resuscitation training within one month of appointment.
 - D. The continuing education strategy ensures that resuscitation training of personnel is kept current.
 - E. Dated records are kept of attendance at in-service training programmes.
 - F. There is a mechanism whereby personnel show proficiency in resuscitation techniques.
- 8. Documented policies and procedures guide nursing care.**
- A. There are documented policies and procedures for all activities of the nursing services.
 - B. These reflect current standards of nursing services and practice, relevant regulations and purposes of the services.

- C. Assignment of patient care is done as per current good practice guidelines.
- D. Nursing care is aligned and integrated with overall patient care.
- E. Care provided by nurses is documented in the patient record.
- F. Nurses are provided with adequate equipment for providing safe and efficient nursing services.
- G. Nurses are empowered to take nursing-related decisions to ensure the timely care of patients.

9. Documented procedures guide the performance of various procedures.

- A. Documented procedures are used to guide the performance of various clinical procedures.
- B. Only qualified personnel order, plan, perform and assist in performing procedures.
- C. Documented procedures exist to prevent adverse events like a wrong site, wrong patient and wrong procedure.
- D. Informed consent is taken by the personnel performing the procedure, where applicable.
- E. Adherence to standard precautions and asepsis is adhered to during the conduct of the procedure.
- F. Patients are appropriately monitored during and after the procedure.
- G. Procedures are documented accurately in the patient record.

10. Documented policies and procedures guide the care of patients in the intensive care and high dependency units.

- A. Documented policies and procedures are used to guide the care of patients in the intensive care and high dependency units.
- B. The organisation has documented admission and discharge criteria for its intensive care and high dependency units.
- C. Staff are trained to apply these criteria.
- D. Adequate staff and equipment are available.
- E. Defined procedures for the situation of bed shortages are followed.
- F. Infection control practices are documented and followed.
- G. A quality assurance programme is documented and implemented.
- H. Patients and families are counselled by the treating medical professional at periodic intervals and when there is a significant change in the condition of the patient, and same is documented.
- I. The hospital has targets for the quality of the access to services in intensive therapy units and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.
- J. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of access to services in intensive therapy units. The effect of the initiatives has been

assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.

11. Treatment of patients admitted to intensive therapy units takes place according to clinical, evidence-based practices.

- A.** There are guidelines for diagnosis and treatment of sepsis and septic shock. The guidelines cover the hospital's overall efforts for treatment of these conditions.
- B.** There are guidelines for prevention, diagnosis and treatment of ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP).
- C.** There are guidelines for department specific (unit specific) antibiotic strategy.
- D.** There are guidelines for intensive care delirium.
- E.** There are guidelines for department specific (unit specific) sedation strategy.
- F.** Diagnosis and treatment of sepsis and septic shock takes place in accordance with standard.
- G.** Prevention, diagnosis and treatment of ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) take place in accordance with the standard.
- H.** Treatment with antibiotics is in accordance with the standard.
- I.** Treatment of intensive care delirium takes place in accordance with the standard.
- J.** The patients are sedated in accordance with the standard.
- K.** The hospital has targets for the quality of the treatment in intensive therapy unit. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets.
- L.** The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of treatment in intensive therapy unit. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. The hospital cannot deselect this element of the standard as not prioritised.

12. Documented policies and procedures guide the care of vulnerable patients.

- A.** Policies and procedures are documented and are in accordance with the prevailing laws and the national and international guidelines.
- B.** Care is organised and delivered in accordance with the policies and procedures.
- C.** The organisation provides for a safe and secure environment for the vulnerable group.
- D.** A documented procedure exists for obtaining informed consent from the appropriate legal representative.
- E.** Staff are trained to care for the vulnerable group.

13. Documented policies and procedures guide obstetric care.

- A. There is a documented policy and procedure for obstetric services.
- B. The organisation defines and displays whether high-risk obstetric cases can be cared for or not.
- C. Persons caring for high-risk obstetric cases are competent.
- D. Documented procedures guide the provision of ante-natal services.
- E. Obstetric patient's assessment also includes maternal nutrition.
- F. Appropriate pre-natal, peri-natal and post-natal monitoring is performed and documented.
- G. The organisation caring for high-risk obstetric cases has the facilities to take care of neonates of such cases.

14. Specific resources are available for the provision of safe care to patients in the obstetric and maternity unit/ ward.

- A. Current guidelines for the provision of obstetric/maternity care services and facilities are followed.
- B. Staffing of the service complies with accepted staffing norms for obstetric/maternity care services.

15. Documented policies and procedures guide paediatric services.

- A. There is a documented policy and procedure for paediatric services.
- B. The organisation defines and displays the scope of its paediatric services.
- C. The policy for care of neonatal patients is in consonance with the national/ international guidelines.
- D. Those who care for children have age-specific competency.
- E. Provisions are made for special care of children.
- F. Patient assessment includes detailed nutritional, growth, developmental and immunisation assessment.
- G. Documented policies and procedures prevent child/neonate abduction and abuse.
- H. The children's family members are educated about nutrition, immunisation and safe parenting and this is documented.

16. Documented policies and procedures guide the care of patients undergoing surgical procedures.

- A. The policies and procedures are documented.
- B. Surgical patients have a preoperative assessment and a provisional diagnosis documented prior to surgery.
- C. An informed consent is obtained by a surgeon prior to the procedure.
- D. Documented policies and procedures exist to prevent adverse events like wrong site, wrong patient and wrong surgery.
- E. Persons qualified by law are permitted to perform the procedures that they are entitled to perform.

- F. A brief operative note is documented prior to transfer out of patient from recovery.
- G. The operating surgeon documents the postoperative care plan.
- H. Patient, personnel and material flow conform to infection control practices.
- I. Appropriate facilities and equipment/ appliances/ instrumentation are available in the operating theatre.
- J. A quality assurance programme is followed for the surgical services.
- K. The quality assurance programme includes surveillance of the operation theatre environment.

17. Documented policies and procedures guide organ transplant programme in the organisation.

- A. The organ transplant program shall be in consonance with the legal requirements and shall be conducted in an ethical manner.
- B. Documented policies and procedures guide the organ transplant program.
- C. The organisation ensures education and counselling of recipient and donor through trained / qualified counsellors before organ transplantation.
- D. The organisation shall take measures to create awareness regarding organ donation.

18. Documented policies and procedures guide the care of patients under restraints (physical and/or chemical).

- A. Documented policies and procedures guide the care of patients under restraints.
- B. The policies and procedures include both physical and chemical restraint measures.
- C. The reasons for restraints are documented.
- D. Patients on restraints are more frequently monitored.
- E. Staff receives training and periodic updating in control and restraint techniques.

19. Minimising restrictive practices: restraint

- A. Where restraint is clinically necessary to prevent harm, the health service organisation has systems that:
 - Minimise and, where possible, eliminate the use of restraint
 - Govern the use of restraint in accordance with legislation
 - Report use of restraint to the governing body

20. Preventing delirium and managing cognitive impairment

- A. The health service organisation providing services to patients who have cognitive impairment or are at risk of developing delirium has a system for caring for patients with cognitive impairment to:

- Incorporate best-practice strategies for early recognition, prevention, treatment and management of cognitive impairment in the care plan, including the Delirium Clinical Care , where relevant
 - Manage the use of antipsychotics and other psychoactive medicines, in accordance with best practice and legislation
- B.** Clinicians providing care to patients who have cognitive impairment or are at risk of developing delirium use the system for caring for patients with cognitive impairment to:
- Recognise, prevent, treat and manage cognitive impairment
 - Collaborate with patients, carers and families to understand the patient and implement individualised strategies that minimise any anxiety or distress while they are receiving care

21. Predicting, preventing and managing selfharm and suicide

- A.** The health service organisation has systems to support collaboration with patients, carers and families to:
- Identify when a patient is at risk of self-harm
 - Identify when a patient is at risk of suicide
 - Safely and effectively respond to patients who are distressed, have thoughts of self-harm or suicide, or have self-harmed
- B.** The health service organisation ensures that follow-up arrangements are developed, communicated and implemented for people who have harmed themselves or reported suicidal thoughts

22. The hospital makes an active effort to prevent suicide among patients.

- A.** There are guidelines for prevention of suicides prepared by involving "The supportive and accompanying principle".
- B.** Managers and staff are familiar with relevant parts of the guidelines and work accordingly.
- C.** Analyses of reasons for suicide and suicide attempts at the hospital are completed.
- D.** The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the monitoring of suicide risk or to maintain an already high level of quality.

23. Predicting, preventing and managing aggression and violence

- A.** The health service organisation has processes to identify and mitigate situations that may precipitate aggression
- B.** The health service organisation has processes to support collaboration with patients, carers and families to:
- Identify patients at risk of becoming aggressive or violent
 - Implement de-escalation strategies
 - Safely manage aggression, and minimise harm to patients, carers, families and the workforce

24. Minimising restrictive practices: seclusion

- A. Where seclusion is clinically necessary to prevent harm and is permitted under legislation, the health service organisation has systems that:
- Minimise and, where possible, eliminate the use of seclusion
 - Govern the use of seclusion in accordance with legislation
 - Report use of seclusion to the governing body

25. Involuntary commitment and use of other coercion in psychiatry takes place according to current legislation.

- A. There are guidelines for use of coercion which complies with current legislation.
- B. Involuntary commitment and other use of coercion are conducted and documented in accordance with the guidelines and current legislation.
- C. Every sixth month the hospital reviews patient health records from patients who have been exposed to involuntary commitment or other coercion. In connection with the review, it is clarified whether a protocol exists on use of coercive measures which complies with applicable rules and legislation.
- D. Every sixth month the hospital reviews patient health records from patients who have been exposed to involuntary commitment or other use of coercion. The review clarifies whether it is documented that a follow-up conversation has been held with the patient after coercion.
- E. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the involuntary commitment and use of other coercion in psychiatry. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.

26. Where electro-convulsive therapy is provided, the service is managed and staffed to ensure patient safety.

- A. A senior medical practitioner who is suitably qualified and experienced is in charge of the ECT service.
- B. The design of the ECT treatment area provides space for the reception, anaesthetic induction, treatment, recovery and observation of patients.
- C. Policies and procedures relating to the activities in the ECT unit are implemented.
- D. There is documented evidence that the patient has consented to the procedure.
- E. Anaesthesia is administered only by qualified anaesthesiologists.
- F. Emergency resuscitation equipment is available in the ECT unit according to hospital policy.

- G. Resuscitation equipment and trolley contents are checked prior to each administration of ECT.
- H. There is a mechanism for summoning assistance in the event of an emergency.

27. Documented policies and procedures guide appropriate pain management.

- A. Documented policies and procedures guide the management of pain.
- B. All patients are screened for pain.
- C. Patients with pain undergo detailed assessment and periodic reassessment.
- D. Pain alleviation measures or medications are initiated and treated according to patient's need and response.
- E. The organisation respects and supports management of pain for such patients.
- F. Patient and family are educated on various pain management techniques, where appropriate.
- G. The hospital has processes to educate health professionals in assessing and managing pain.
- H. The hospital has targets for the quality of pain management. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets. Data are analysed and assessed.
- I. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of pain management. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.

28. Documented policies and procedures guide appropriate rehabilitative services.

- A. Documented policies and procedures guide the provision of rehabilitative services.
- B. These services are commensurate with the organisational requirements.
- C. Care is guided by functional assessment and periodic re-assessment which is done and documented by qualified individual(s).
- D. Care is provided adhering to infection control and safe practices.
- E. Rehabilitative services are provided by a multidisciplinary team.
- F. There is adequate space and equipment to perform these activities.

29. Documented policies and procedures guide all research activities.

- A. Documented policies and procedures guide all research activities in compliance with regulatory, national and international guidelines.
- B. The organisation has an ethics committee to oversee all research activities.

- C. The committee has the powers to discontinue a research trial when risks outweigh the potential benefits.
- D. Patient's informed consent is obtained before entering them in research protocols.
- E. Patients are informed of their right to withdraw from the research at any stage and also of the consequences (if any) of such withdrawal.
- F. Patients are assured that their refusal to participate or withdrawal from participation will not compromise their access to the organisation's services.

30. Documented policies and procedures guide the end of life care. (NABH)

- A. Documented policies and procedures guide the end of life care.
- B. These policies and procedures are in consonance with the legal requirements.
- C. These also address the identification of the unique needs of such patient and family.
- D. Symptomatic treatment is provided and where appropriate measures are taken for the alleviation of pain.
- E. Staff are educated and trained in end of life care.
- F. The health service organisation has processes to ensure that current advance care plans:
 - **Can be received from patients**
 - **Are documented in the patient's healthcare record**
- G. The health service organisation provides access to supervision and support for the workforce providing end-of-life care
- H. The health service organisation has processes for routinely reviewing the safety and quality of end-of-life care that is provided against the planned goals of care
- I. Clinicians support patients, carers and families to make shared decisions about end-of-life care.
- J. The patient, family and significant other(s) are involved in care decisions.
- K. Pain and primary or secondary symptoms are managed according to hospital policy.
- L. Religious and cultural needs of patients and their families or significant others are identified and met.

31. Preventing and managing pressure injuries

- A. The health service organisation providing services to patients at risk of pressure injuries has systems for pressure injury prevention and wound management that are consistent with best-practice guidelines
- B. Clinicians providing care to patients at risk of developing, or with, a pressure injury conduct comprehensive skin inspections in accordance with best-practice time frames and frequency

- C. The health service organisation providing services to patients at risk of pressure injuries ensures that:
- Patients, carers and families are provided with information about preventing pressure injuries
 - Equipment, devices and products are used in line with best-practice guidelines to prevent and effectively manage pressure injuries

32. Preventing falls and harm from falls

- A. The health service organisation providing services to patients at risk of falls has systems that are consistent with best-practice guidelines for:
- Falls prevention
 - Minimising harm from falls
 - Post-fall management
- B. The health service organisation providing services to patients at risk of falls ensures that equipment, devices and tools are available to promote safe mobility and manage the risks of falls
- C. Clinicians providing care to patients at risk of falls provide patients, carers and families with information about reducing falls risks and falls prevention strategies

33. Partnering with consumers-acute deterioration

- A. Clinicians use organisational processes from the Partnering with Consumers Standard when recognising and responding to acute deterioration to:
- Actively involve patients in their own care
 - Meet the patient's information needs
 - Share decision-making

34. Recognising acute deterioration

- A. Clinicians use the safety and quality systems from the Clinical Governance Standard when:
- Implementing policies and procedures for recognising and responding to acute deterioration
 - Managing risks associated with recognising and responding to acute deterioration
 - Identifying training requirements for recognising and responding to acute deterioration
- B. The health service organisation has processes for clinicians to detect acute physiological deterioration that require clinicians to:
- Document individualised vital sign monitoring plans
 - Monitor patients as required by their individualised monitoring plan
 - Graphically document and track changes in agreed observations to detect acute deterioration over time, as appropriate for the patient

- C. The health service organisation has processes for clinicians to recognize acute deterioration in mental state that require clinicians to:
- Monitor patients at risk of acute deterioration in mental state, including patients at risk of developing delirium
 - Include the person's known early warning signs of deterioration in mental state in their individualised monitoring plan
 - Assess possible causes of acute deterioration in mental state, including delirium, when changes in behaviour, cognitive function, perception, physical function or emotional state are observed or reported
 - Determine the required level of observation
 - Document and communicate observed or reported changes in mental state

35. Escalating care

- A. The health service organisation has protocols that specify criteria for escalating care, including:
- Agreed vital sign parameters and other indicators of physiological deterioration
 - Agreed indicators of deterioration in mental state
 - Agreed parameters and other indicators for calling emergency assistance
 - Patient pain or distress that is not able to be managed using available treatment
 - Worry or concern in members of the workforce, patients, carers and families about acute deterioration
- B. The health service organisation has processes for patients, carers or families to directly escalate care
- C. The health service organisation provides the workforce with mechanisms to escalate care and call for emergency assistance
- D. The workforce uses the recognition and response systems to escalate care

36. Responding to deterioration

- A. The health service organisation has processes that support timely response by clinicians with the skills required to manage episodes of acute deterioration
- B. The health service organisation has processes to ensure rapid access at all times to at least one clinician, either on site or in close proximity, who can deliver advanced life support
- C. The health service organisation has processes to ensure rapid referral to mental health services to meet the needs of patients whose mental state has acutely deteriorated
- D. The health service organisation has processes for rapid referral to services that can provide definitive management of acute physical deterioration

37. The hospital prepares and uses guidelines concerning treatment of specific patient groups which are used as basis for treatment decisions. The guidelines are based on national guidelines, where they exist.

- A. The hospital has a process ensuring the preparation of guidelines regarding treatment of specific patient groups for: the most frequent patient groups a) highly specialised treatment b) patient groups with complicated challenges in terms of assessment, c) treatment, rehabilitation, care or recovery.
- B. The hospital has guidelines for how the guidelines for treatment of specific patient groups undergo a professional hearing and approval procedure prior to the final managerial approval.
- C. There are guidelines prepared in accordance with the process and the determined professional hearing and approval procedure.
- D. Managers and staff are familiar with relevant parts of the guidelines regarding treatment of specific patient groups and work accordingly. In specific cases it may be well-founded to deviate from the guidelines. Specific de-selections are described and substantiated in the patient health record.
- E. The hospital has targets for the quality of the patient treatment. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the goals.
- F. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the patient treatment. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.

38. The hospital prepares patient pathway descriptions concerning treatment of specific patient groups which are used as basis for the preparation of frequent and/or complex patient pathways. (IKAS)

- A. The hospital has a process which ensures the preparation of pathway descriptions for: patients included by nationally integrated care pathways other complex and/or frequently occurring pathways
- B. There are agreements on the cross-sectorial collaboration between the primary sector and the secondary sector for patients with a chronic disease. As a minimum, the agreements describe: Tasks in the different phases of the pathway a) Unambiguous assignment of the responsibility for all the phases in the b) pathway
- C. There are pathway descriptions prepared in accordance with the process.
- D. There are specific pathway descriptions for patients with a chronic disease prepared as a result of the agreements on the cross-sectorial collaboration . As a minimum, the agreements include dementia, cardiac insufficiency, Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (COLD), type 2 diabetes and schizophrenia.

- E. Managers and staff are familiar with the relevant pathway descriptions and work accordingly. In specific cases it may be well-founded to deviate from the pathway descriptions. Specific de-selections are described and substantiated in the patient health record.
- F. The hospital has targets for the quality of its patient pathways. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets. Data are analysed and assessed.
- G. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of its patient pathways. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. The hospital cannot deselect this element of the standard as not prioritised. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals, including the nationally determined quality goals.

39. Policies and procedures guide the care of high risk patients and the provision of high risk services.

- A. Documented protocols, clinical guidelines or standard operating procedures for identified high risk patients and procedures are available and readily accessible.
- B. In-service training is provided to personnel to ensure they understand the intent and content of the policies and procedures.

40. Diversity and high-risk groups

- A. The health service organisation:
 - Identifies the diversity of the consumers using its services
 - Identifies groups of patients using its services who are at higher risk of harm
 - Incorporates information on the diversity of its consumers and high risk groups into the planning and delivery of care

41. The care provided to each patient is planned and documented in the patient's record.

- A. The planned care is provided and documented in the patient's record.
- B. The patient's response to care and therapeutic interventions is documented in the patient record.
- C. All procedures and diagnostic tests ordered and performed are documented in the patient's record.
- D. The results of procedures and diagnostic tests performed are available in the patient's record.
- E. The maternal and foetal conditions and the progress of labour are recorded on a partogram in every labour.

- F. Re-assessments are performed at appropriate, regular intervals and following a change in the patient's condition, and documented in the patient's record.
- G. Care plans are revised when necessary in response to the findings of re-assessments.

42. Each healthcare professional supports patient, family and caregiver participation in care decisions and care processes

- A. Patients and families indicate that they have received health education appropriate to their condition.
- B. Patients indicate that they have been informed about the clinical management of their condition.
- C. Patients are educated about their diagnosis relevant health risks, e.g. safe use of medication and medical equipment, medicine and food interaction, therapeutic diet and food interactions, defaulting on medication use, etc.
- D. Patients and families indicate that they have been informed about financial implications of care decisions.

43. Where observation and/or forensic services are provided, they comply with country-specific legislation.

- A. Policies and procedures that guide the care and/or observation of forensic patients and the provision of forensic services are implemented.
- B. Security or correctional personnel are educated/trained regarding their responsibilities in relation to assisting with the management of patients.
- C. All seclusion or restraint, whether for clinical or non-clinical purposes, is documented in the patient's record.
- D. There are mechanisms designed to facilitate communication and resolve conflict between judicial, correctional, penal, clinical and administrative agencies and those involved in an individual's care.

44. Integrating clinical governance

- A. Clinicians use the safety and quality systems from the Clinical Governance Standard when:
 - Implementing policies and procedures for comprehensive care
 - Managing risks associated with comprehensive care
 - Identifying training requirements to deliver comprehensive care

45. The hospital designs and implements processes to provide continuity of patient care services within the hospital and coordination among health professionals

- A. Policies and procedures that guide the movement of patients within the hospital are implemented.

- B.** Individuals responsible for the patient's care and its coordination are identified for all phases of patient care.
- C.** Continuity and coordination are evident throughout all phases of patient care.
- D.** When a patient is transferred within the hospital, they are accompanied by their patient record.
- E.** Patient handover between healthcare professionals is standardized according to hospital policy.
- F.** Documentation regarding the transfer of a patient from the forensic service to another service within the hospital meets legal requirements.

CHAPTER- 4

ANESTHESIA & SURGICAL CARE (ASC)

- 1. The operating theatre and anaesthetic services are managed and staffed to provide a safe and effective service.**
 - A.** A senior professional who is suitably qualified and experienced is in charge of the theatre and the recovery area.
 - B.** During all phases of care, there are qualified individuals responsible for the patient's care.
 - C.** There is a theatre users' committee or equivalent, which meets regularly and consists of representatives from all relevant services.
 - D.** Operating theatre rosters ensure that registered nurses with suitable qualifications and experience are present during all shifts for theatre duties, anaesthetic assistance and recovery room duties.
 - E.** Anaesthesia is administered only by medical practitioners or other professionals who are privileged by the hospital to do so.
 - F.** Trainee anaesthetists are under the supervision of trained anaesthesiologists.
 - G.** The person administering anaesthesia is directly responsible for only one anaesthetised patient at a time.
 - H.** Anaesthesia is commenced and terminated only in the presence of a member of personnel whose sole duty it is to assist the person administering anaesthesia until such time as the latter indicates that assistance is no longer required.
 - I.** The surgeon performing the procedure(s) is present in the operating theatre before the anaesthetist commences the administration of the anaesthetic.
 - J.** There is at least one suitably trained and/or experienced anaesthetic nurse per operating theatre.
 - K.** Nursing personnel trained and/or experienced in recovery room care are available until the patient has fully recovered.

- 2. Documented policies and procedures relating to the activities in the operating theatre are implemented.**
 - A.** Policies and procedures that guide the activities of the operating theatre services are implemented.
 - B.** Policies and procedures relating to the anaesthetic service are implemented.
 - C.** In-service training is provided to personnel to ensure they understand the intent and content of the policies and procedures.

- 3. Policies and procedures that guide the care of patients undergoing moderate and deep sedation are implemented.**
 - A. Policies and procedures regarding the care of patients undergoing moderate and deep sedation are implemented.
 - B. There is a pre-sedation assessment, according to hospital policy, to evaluate risk and appropriateness of sedation for the patient.
 - C. A qualified individual monitors the patient during sedation and during the period of recovery from sedation and documents the monitoring.
 - D. Moderate and deep sedation are administered according to hospital policy.

- 4. Documented policies and procedures guide the care of patients undergoing moderate sedation.**
 - A. Documented procedures guide the administration of moderate sedation.
 - B. Informed consent for administration of moderate sedation is obtained.
 - C. Competent and trained persons perform sedation.
 - D. The person administering and monitoring sedation is different from the person performing the procedure.
 - E. Intra-procedure monitoring includes at a minimum the heart rate, cardiac rhythm, respiratory rate, blood pressure, oxygen saturation, level of sedation and end tidal carbon dioxide.
 - F. Patients are monitored after sedation and the same documented.
 - G. Criteria are used to determine appropriateness of discharge from the observation/ recovery area.
 - H. Equipment and manpower are available to manage patients who have gone into a deeper level of sedation than initially intended.
 - I. The hospital has targets for the quality of sedation of patients for procedures without the involvement of anaesthesiological staff, and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year period. The goals include regular control of presence and function of monitoring and resuscitation equipment (e.g. oxygen, suction and bag) on the ward or in the immediate vicinity. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.
 - J. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of sedation of patients for procedures without the involvement of anaesthesiological staff. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.

- 5. Documented policies and procedures guide the administration of anaesthesia.**

- A. There is a documented policy and procedure for the administration of anaesthesia.
- B. Patients for anaesthesia have a pre-anaesthesia assessment by a qualified anaesthesiologist.
- C. The pre-anaesthesia assessment results in formulation of an anaesthesia plan which is documented.
- D. An immediate preoperative re-evaluation is performed and documented.
- E. Informed consent for administration of anaesthesia is obtained by the anaesthesiologist.
- F. Patient's post-anaesthesia status is monitored and documented.
- G. The anaesthesiologist applies defined criteria to transfer the patient from the recovery area.
- H. The type of anaesthesia and anaesthetic medications used are documented in the patient record.
- I. Procedures shall comply with infection control guidelines to prevent cross infection between patients.
- J. Adverse anaesthesia events are recorded and monitored.
- K. The hospital has targets for the quality of the assessment prior to the procedure in anaesthesia. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets. Data are analysed and assessed.
- L. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the assessment prior to the procedure in anaesthesia. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.

6. Pre-and post-procedural assessments are documented.

- A. The patient's pre-anaesthetic medical assessment to determine fitness for anaesthesia is documented.
- B. Patients have a pre-procedural diagnosis recorded before anaesthesia.
- C. A post-procedural diagnosis is documented.
- D. The name of the medical practitioner responsible for the procedure is documented.
- E. The patient's physiological status is monitored during the post-procedural period.

7. The hospital supports a surgical safety pathway by using WHO's Surgical Safety Check list.

- A. There are guidelines which support safe implementation of operative, invasive procedure in general or local anaesthesia with anaesthetic involvement. The guidelines are based on WHO's "Surgical safety".

Check lists have been prepared which can be adjusted to specific procedures.

- B. Managers and staff implement the initiatives in the hospital's check list in connection with operative, invasive procedures in general or local anaesthesia with anaesthetic involvement.
- C. Implementation of "Surgical safety" is documented.
- D. The hospital has targets for the quality for the implementation of "Surgical safety" and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.
- E. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the documentation of informed consent. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.

8. Each patient's physiological status is monitored and recorded during anaesthesia and surgery.

- A. The patient's physiological status is continuously monitored during anaesthesia and surgery.
- B. The results of such monitoring are entered into the patient's record.
- C. The anaesthetic agents used are entered into the patient's anaesthetic record.
- D. Analgesia administered on conclusion of the surgical procedure is documented in the patient's record.
- E. The patient's pre-anaesthetic medical assessment to determine fitness for anaesthesia is documented.
- F. The results of diagnostic tests performed on the patient are recorded prior to the administration of anaesthesia.
- G. The names of the anaesthetist, the medical practitioner who performs the ECT and other personnel, as required by law, are documented.
- H. The patient's physiological status is monitored during the immediate post-ECT period.

9. The patients' post-anaesthetic monitoring is secured through a stipulated post-anaesthetic plan.

- A. There are guidelines for planning of the post-anaesthetic monitoring.
- B. There are guidelines for termination of the post-anaesthetic monitoring.
- C. Post-anaesthetic monitoring is planned and implemented in accordance with the standard.
- D. Post-anaesthetic monitoring is terminated in accordance with the standard.
- E. The hospital has targets for the quality of post-anaesthetic monitoring and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two

times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.

- F. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the postanaesthetic monitoring. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.

10. There is a system to monitor and document each patient's post-anaesthetic status and to discharge the patient from the recovery area according to accepted guidelines.

- A. There are guidelines for assessment and initiation of recovery for relevant patient groups. If the effort is performed in collaboration with external parties, the division of responsibility and tasks will be described.
- B. Patients who need recovery are offered a relevant recovery effort.
- C. The hospital has target for the quality of the recovery effort and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.
- D. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the recovery effort. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.
- E. The anaesthetist is responsible for supervising the recovery period.
- F. The qualifications and experience of personnel members who may monitor patients are documented.
- G. Monitoring is appropriate to the patient's condition during the post-anaesthetic recovery period.
- H. Monitoring findings are documented in the patient's record.
- I. The individual responsible for discharging the patient and signs the discharge in the patient record.
- J. Verbal orders are documented according to hospital policy.
- K. Times of arrival in and discharge from the recovery area are recorded.
- L. Established criteria are used to make decisions to discharge patients from the recovery room.
- M. Patient safety is ensured by the correct implementation of the handover procedure from the recovery room personnel to the unit/ward personnel.
- N. Signatures of those receiving the patient are recorded.

11. Post-operative assessments are documented.

- A. A post-operative diagnosis is documented.
- B. The name of the surgeon and the names of other personnel are documented as required by law.

- C. The patient's physiological status is monitored during the immediate post-surgical period.

12. Minor invasive procedures performed in the outpatient department are controlled by policy.

- A. Policies and procedures govern invasive procedures performed in the outpatient department.
- B. Protocols guide medication use for sedation, pain and anaesthesia.
- C. Protocols address appropriate monitoring during and after the procedure.
- D. The procedure and the name of the person performing the procedure are recorded in the patient's record.
- E. Unsuccessful or complicated procedures are recorded.

13. Anaesthetic equipment, supplies and medication comply with the recommendations of anaesthetic professional organisations or other authoritative sources.

- A. Anaesthetic mixture components are available and used in accordance with hospital policy.
- B. The recommendations of anaesthetic professional organisations or other authoritative sources guide the provision and use of breathing circuits.
- C. The recommendations of anaesthetic professional organisations or other authoritative sources guide the use of scavenging equipment for removing vapours and anaesthetic gases.
- D. The recommendations of anaesthetic professional organisations or other authoritative sources guide the provision and use of monitoring equipment.
- E. The recommendations of anaesthetic professional organisations or other authoritative sources guide the provision and use of ancillary equipment.
- F. Medication is available according to the requirements of the level of care provided.
- G. A medication trolley is available for the exclusive use of the anaesthetist in each theatre.
- H. A tracheostomy tray is available.

14. Medical equipment available meets the minimum requirements for the level of care provided.

- A. Equipment and instrumentation for routine and emergency surgery must be available according to hospital policy for the level of care provided.
- B. Theatre personnel ensure that all equipment is included in the hospital's equipment replacement and maintenance programme.

15. Resuscitation and personal protective equipment are provided in the operating theatre.

- A. Standardised resuscitation equipment is available in all relevant areas of the operating theatre suite.
- B. Resuscitation equipment shows evidence of regular checking.
- C. Resuscitation equipment and supplies have clearly defined instructions for use.
- D. There is a mechanism for summoning assistance in an emergency.
- E. There is appropriate shielding and protective clothing in the presence of biohazards (including lasers) or radiographic equipment.
- F. Hazard or warning notices are displayed.

CHAPTER- 5
EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT (ED)

- 1. Emergency services are guided by documented policies, procedures, applicable laws and regulations.**
 - A. There shall be an identified area in the organisation which is easily accessible to receive and manage emergency patients.
 - B. Policies and procedures for emergency care are documented and are in consonance with statutory requirements.
 - C. This also addresses the handling of medico-legal cases.
 - D. The patients receive care in consonance with the policies.
 - E. Staff are familiar with the policies and trained on the procedures for care of emergency patients.
 - F. Admission or discharge to home or transfer to another organisation is also documented.
 - G. In case of discharge to home or transfer to another organisation, a discharge note shall be given to the patient.
 - H. Quality assurance programmes are documented and implemented.
 - I. The documented policies and procedures guide management of patients found dead on arrival to the hospital.

- 2. Patient registers are kept in accordance with country-specific requirements and/or hospital policy.**
 - A. A register is kept of patients attending the emergency unit.
 - B. The register contains at least the patient's name, patient-specific identification number, age, gender, date and time of admission, treatment, procedures, discharge, referral or death.
 - C. The information in the register is used to monitor waiting periods from time of arrival to time of assessment.

- 3. During all phases of care, there are qualified individuals responsible for the patient's care.**
 - A. During the hours of operation there is an adequate number of qualified professionals available to provide continuous cover to all sections at all times.
 - B. Emergency services personnel maintain skills in advanced life support in accordance with hospital policy.
 - C. Medical cover is reflected on a roster and each practitioner on the roster is contactable by telephone, pager or other two-way communication method.

- 4. The hospital has a formal triage process which uses documented guidelines to determine urgency.**
 - A. Documented policies and procedures guide the triage of patients for initiation of appropriate care.
 - B. The unit implements an evidence-based triage system.
 - C. All personnel responsible for patient triage have received training in the application of the triage system.
 - D. Clinical records of emergency patients include the time of arrival.
 - E. The triage category for each patient is recorded.
 - F. Clinical records of emergency patients include time of referral to medical practitioner.
 - G. Waiting times from triage categorisation to initial assessment are monitored.
 - H. Patients identified by triage as having emergency or immediate needs are prioritised for assessment and intervention according to established criteria.

- 5. Patients being transferred from the Emergency Unit to the operating theatre are appropriately prepared.**
 - A. The indication for surgery is recorded before anaesthesia.
 - B. Policies that address nursing preparation of patients being transferred to the operating theatre are implemented.
 - C. Patients being transferred to the operating theatre are accompanied by an appropriately qualified person, as determined by hospital policy.

- 6. The hospital implements policies for the management of patients requiring short-term observation and care.**
 - A. Policies and procedures that address the holding of patients for observation are implemented.
 - B. The hospital has established appropriate time frames which limit holding time in the emergency unit.
 - C. Patients under observation are reassessed at appropriate intervals to determine their response to care and treatment and this is documented in the record.
 - D. Any significant changes in the patient's condition are noted in the patient's record and acted upon appropriately.
 - E. Any patient care meetings or other discussions are noted in the patient's record.
 - F. Holding times are monitored and audited.

- 7. Transport of patients who need a health professional person to accompany them so it is a safe transport with a competent health professional person.**
 - A. There are guidelines for patient transports with a health professional.

- B. The management decides to which extent the staff must be trained to handle accompaniment in connection with patient transport and the management establishes a training programme. Hospitals receiving acute patients must have such a programme unless the hospital has agreements which place the task of accompanying patients somewhere else.
 - C. The responsibility for initiation and implementation of the individual patient transport has been assigned.
 - D. The responsibility for monitoring and treatment of the patient has been assigned before the individual patient transport.
 - E. Monitoring, treatment and care of the patient during the individual transport have been considered.
 - F. The staff is trained in patient transport in accordance with the hospital's decisions concerning this topic.
 - G. Emergency patients who require transfer to another hospital for appropriate services are stabilised prior to transfer.
- 8. The organisation plans for handling community emergencies, epidemics and other disasters.**
- A. The organisation identifies potential emergencies.
 - B. The organisation has a documented disaster management plan.
 - C. Provision is made for availability of medical supplies, equipment and materials during such emergencies.
 - D. Staff are trained in the hospital's disaster management plan.
 - E. The plan is tested at least twice a year.
- 9. Where the hospital provides an ambulance service, this service is delivered in line with relevant laws and regulations.**
- A. The hospital has a written response and deployment plan including the identification of response areas and availability of response units.
 - B. Response time standards are monitored against national laws, regulations, policies or guidelines.
 - C. The hospital designs and implements processes to provide coordination of services among other hospitals and agencies in the community.
 - D. The individuals responsible for management of the ambulance service develop a list of the equipment required for each ambulance in collaboration with other relevant services.
 - E. The individuals who provide patient care in the ambulance service have the required training and experience.
 - F. The hospital plans and implements processes for inspecting, testing and maintaining equipment and supplies.
 - G. The hospital maintains its ambulance vehicles to reduce risk and promote safety.
 - H. Medical transport/ambulance vehicles are cleaned in accordance with hospital policy.

10. The ambulance services are commensurate with the scope of the services provided by the organisation.

- A.** There is adequate access and space for the ambulance(s).
- B.** The ambulance adheres to statutory requirements.
- C.** The ambulance(s) is appropriately equipped.
- D.** The ambulance(s) is manned by trained and experienced personnel.
- E.** The ambulance(s) is checked on a daily basis.
- F.** Equipments are checked on a daily basis using a checklist.
- G.** Emergency medications are checked daily and prior to dispatch using a checklist.
- H.** The ambulance(s) has a proper communication system.
- I.** The emergency department identifies opportunities to initiate treatment at the
- J.** The emergency department identifies opportunities to initiate treatment at the earliest when the patient is in transit to the organisation.

CHAPTER- 6
PATIENT AND FAMILY RIGHTS (PFR)

- 1. The organisation protects patient and family rights and informs them about their responsibilities during care.**
 - A. Patient and family rights and responsibilities are documented and displayed.
 - B. Patients and families are informed of their rights and responsibilities in a format and language that they can understand.
 - C. The organisation's leaders protect patient and family rights.
 - D. Staff are aware of their responsibility in protecting patient and family rights.
 - E. Violation of patient and family rights is recorded, reviewed and corrective/preventive measures taken.

- 2. Patient and family rights support individual beliefs, values and involve the patient and family in decision making processes.**
 - A. Patients and family rights include respecting any special preferences, spiritual and cultural needs.
 - B. Patient and family rights include respect for personal dignity and privacy during examination, procedures and treatment.
 - C. Patient and family rights include protection from neglect or abuse.
 - D. Patient and family rights include treating patient information as confidential.
 - E. Patient and family rights include refusal of treatment.
 - F. Patient and family have a right to seek an additional opinion regarding clinical care.
 - G. Patient and family rights include informed consent before transfusion of blood and blood components, anaesthesia, surgery, initiation of any research protocol and any other invasive / high risk procedures / treatment.
 - H. Patient and family rights include right to complain and information on how to voice a complaint
 - I. Patient and family rights include information on the expected cost of the treatment.
 - J. Patient and family rights include access to his / her clinical records.
 - K. Patient and family rights include information on Care plan, progress and information on their health care needs.
 - L. Relevant written material for patients and/or relatives will be handed out.

- 3. Patient and families have a right to information and education about their healthcare needs.**
 - A. Patient and/or family are educated about the safe and effective use of medication and the potential side effects of the medication, when appropriate.

- B. Patient and/or family are educated about food-drug interaction
 - C. Patient and/or family are educated about diet and nutrition.
 - D. Patient and/or family are educated about immunisations.
 - E. Patient and/or family are educated about their specific disease process, complications and prevention strategies.
 - F. Patient and/or family are educated about preventing healthcare associated infections.
 - G. The patients and/or family members' special educational needs are identified and addressed.
 - H. Patient and/or family are educated in a language and format that they can understand.
 - I. Patient and/or family are receives information about the name of the healthcare professional contact person
- 4. Patients and families have a right to information on expected costs.**
- A. There is a uniform pricing policy in a given setting (out-patient and ward category).
 - B. The relevant tariff list is available to patients.
 - C. The patient and/or family members are explained about the expected costs.
 - D. Patient and/or family are informed about the financial implications when there is a change in the patient condition or treatment setting.
- 5. The hospital informs patients and families about its process to receive and act on complaints, conflicts and differences of opinion about patient care and the patient's right to participate in these processes.**
- A. Policies and procedures relating to the reporting and investigation of complaints are implemented.
 - B. The relevant hospital committee monitors adherence to the established time frame and takes appropriate action when required.
 - C. Patients are aware of their right to voice complaints and the processes by which to do so.
- 6. The department/service implements processes that support patient and family rights during care.**
- A. There are processes that support patient and family rights during care.
 - B. Measures are taken to protect the patient's privacy, person and possessions.
 - C. The personnel respect the right of patients and families to receive treatment and the right to refuse treatment.
 - D. There are processes that support patient and family rights related to food and nutrition.
 - E. Personnel respect the rights of patients and families and recognise cultural preferences related to meals.

7. Patients and their families receive sufficient information to make informed decisions regarding their care.

- A. Policies and procedures that guide personnel in relation to informed consent are implemented.
- B. Patients and their families/ carers/guardians are provided with information on the proposed care and the expected results of care.
- C. Patients and their families are informed about their rights to refuse or discontinue treatment.
- D. Patients and their families are informed about the consequences of such decisions.
- E. The hospital respects the right of patients and families to refuse or discontinue treatment.
- F. Legislative requirements are followed when patients with notifiable diseases refuse treatment.
- G. Patients and their families/ carers/guardians are informed about immunisations appropriate to their age and/or disease groups.

8. The hospital is responsible for providing processes that support patient and family rights during care.

- A. Patient and family rights are identified and documented in accordance with current relevant legislation.
- B. Policies and procedures which guide and support the protection of patient and family rights in the hospital are developed in accordance with ethical and legal norms, and implemented.
- C. Documented evidence of personnel training in relation to these policies and procedures is available.
- D. There are processes in place to respond to the patient's and their family's social, spiritual and cultural values, beliefs and needs.

9. The department/service implements processes that support patient and family rights during care.

- A. There are processes that support patient and family rights related to the provision of bed linen to promote patient comfort.
- B. Appropriate hospital attire is provided to patients to ensure that their right to dignity is preserved.
- C. There are processes that support patient and family rights related to a clean environment.
- D. Personnel respect the rights of patients and families related to protection from healthcare-associated infections by means of appropriate waste management.

10. Healthcare rights and informed consent

- A. The health service organisation uses a charter of rights that is:
 - Consistent with the National Charter of Healthcare Rights

- Easily accessible for patients, carers, families and consumers
- B.** The health service organisation ensures that its informed consent processes comply with legislation and best practice
- C.** The health service organisation has processes to identify:
 - The capacity of a patient to make decisions about their own care
 - A substitute decision-maker if a patient does not have the capacity to make decisions for themselves

11. The hospital respects and supports the patient's and the relatives' cultural and religious needs and wishes about existential and spiritual support.

- A.** There are guidelines on how the hospital identifies and supports the patient's and relatives' religious and cultural needs and existential or spiritual support.
- B.** The hospital's dietary offers take the patient's religious background into consideration.
- C.** The hospital takes the patient's shyness into consideration.
- D.** The hospital offers existential or spiritual support to patients and relatives during hospitalisation.

12. The hospital takes measures to protect patient privacy and maintain confidentiality of patient information.

- A.** The patient's need for privacy is protected when providing personal information.
- B.** The patient's need for privacy is protected during all examinations, procedures, treatments and carerelated discussions.
- C.** Policies and procedures to guide personnel in maintaining confidentiality of patient information are implemented.

13. Patients are protected from assault and harm.

- A.** The hospital has documented processes to protect patients from assault and harm.
- B.** Remote or isolated areas of the hospital are monitored.
- C.** The hospital has processes to protect patients from abuse and negligence, both within the hospital and in the community.

14. Partnering with consumers

- A.** Clinicians use organisational processes from the Partnering with Consumers Standard when providing comprehensive care to:
 - Actively involve patients in their own care
 - Meet the patient's information needs
 - Share decision-making

15. Integrating clinical governance

- A. Clinicians use the safety and quality systems from the Clinical Governance Standard when:
- Implementing policies and procedures for partnering with consumers
 - Managing risks associated with partnering with consumers
 - Identifying training requirements for partnering with consumers

16. Sharing decisions and planning care

- A. The health service organisation has processes for clinicians to partner with patients and/or their substitute decision-maker to plan, communicate, set goals, and make decisions about their current and future care
- B. The health service organisation supports the workforce to form partnerships with patients and carers so that patients can be actively involved in their own care

17. The organisation has a mechanism to capture patient's feedback and redressal of complaints.

- A. The organisation has a mechanism to capture feedbacks from patients which includes patient satisfaction and patient experience.
- B. The organisation has a documented complaint redressal procedure.
- C. Patient and/or family members are made aware of the procedure for giving feedback and /or lodging complaints.
- D. All feedback and complaints are reviewed and/or analysed within a defined time frame.
- E. Corrective and/or preventive action(s) are taken based on the analysis where appropriate.

18. The hospital manages and follows up on patient complaints and patient compensation cases.

- A. There are guidelines for managing both verbal and written complaints from patients, relatives and other partners.
- B. There are guidelines for case handling of patient compensation cases.
- C. The hospital has a determined process for analysis and communication of learning from patients' complaints and patient compensation cases.
- D. There is written information material describing the opportunities for patient complaints and compensation according to current legislation.
- E. Patient complaints are handled according to the standard.
- F. Patient compensation cases are handled according to the standard.
- G. There are guidelines for assessment and analysis of patient complaints and patient compensation cases. The analyses are used for learning in the organisation.
- H. The analyses are used to determine goals and prioritisations for the hospital's quality improvement work.

19. Feedback and complaints management

- A.** The health service organisation:
- Has processes to seek regular feedback from patients, carers and families about their experiences and outcomes of care
 - Has processes to regularly seek feedback from the workforce on their understanding and use of the safety and quality systems
 - Uses this information to improve safety and quality systems
- B.** The health service organisation has an organisation-wide complaints management system, and:
- a. Encourages and supports patients, carers and families, and the workforce to report complaints
 - b. Involves the workforce and consumers in the review of complaints
 - c. Resolves complaints in a timely way
 - d. Provides timely feedback to the governing body, the workforce and consumers on the analysis of complaints and actions taken
 - e. Uses information from the analysis of complaints to inform improvements in safety and quality systems
 - f. Records the risks identified from the analysis of complaints in the risk management system
 - g. Regularly reviews and acts to improve the effectiveness of the complaints management system

20. The hospital systematically collects information about patients and relatives' experiences with the hospital and uses the information to develop the quality of the hospital's services.

- A.** There is a plan for involvement of patients and relatives' experiences with the hospital. The plan includes participation in the national patient satisfaction surveys and how to supplement this with other local or regional activities.
- B.** Local and regional activities are implemented in accordance with the plan.
- C.** Data collected from national patient satisfaction surveys and from local or regional activities are analysed and assessed.
- D.** The collected data are used to determine goals and prioritisations for the hospital's quality improvement work.

21. The patient and/ or family members are educated to make informed decisions and are involved in the care planning and delivery process.

- A.** Informed consent includes information regarding the procedure, its risks, benefits, alternatives and as to who will perform the procedure in a language that they can understand.
- B.** The procedure describes who can give consent when patient is incapable of independent decision making.
- C.** Informed consent is taken by the person performing the procedure.
- D.** Informed consent process adheres to statutory norms.
- E.** Staff are aware of the informed consent procedure.

- F. The patient and/or family members are explained about the proposed care including the risks, alternatives and benefits.
- G. The patient and/or family members are explained about the expected results.
- H. The patient and/or family members are explained about the possible complications.
- I. The care plan is prepared and modified in consultation with patient and/or family members.
- J. The care plan respects and where possible incorporates patient and/or family concerns and requests.
- K. The patient and/or family members are informed about the results of diagnostic tests and the diagnosis.
- L. The patient and/or family members are explained about any change in the patient's condition in a timely manner.

22. A documented procedure for obtaining patient and/ or family's consent exists for informed decision making about their care.

- A. Documented procedure incorporates the list of situations where informed consent is required and the process for taking informed consent.
- B. General consent for treatment is obtained when the patient enters the organisation.
- C. Patient and/or his family members are informed of the scope of such general consent.

23. The patient's informed consent is obtained prior to treatment unless otherwise stipulated by the legislation. Informed consent is also obtained prior to communication of statement of health unless otherwise stipulated by the legislation.

- A. There are guidelines for obtainment of informed consent for treatment which complies with current legislation.
- B. There are guidelines for obtainment of informed consent for research projects which complies with current legislation.
- C. There are guidelines for obtainment of informed consent for disclosure of health information, which complies with current legislation.
- D. Obtainment of informed consent for treatment must be documented in the patient health record.
- E. There is separate documentation for obtainment of informed consent for research projects.
- F. There is documentation for obtainment of informed consent for disclosure of health information when there are legal requirements about this.
- G. The hospital has targets for the quality of documentation of informed consent. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets. Data are analysed and assessed.

H. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the documentation of informed consent. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.

24. Adequate information is provided when obtaining informed consent from patients or their legal representatives. (ER)

- A.** There is a documented process for obtaining or confirming informed consent.
- B.** Consent forms or the form confirming consent are completed comprehensively and available in patient records.
- C.** Verbal consent is obtained and recorded according to hospital policy.

25. Partnering with consumers

- A.** Clinicians use organisational processes from the Partnering with Consumers Standard when recognising and responding to acute deterioration to:
 - a. Actively involve patients in their own care
 - b. Meet the patient's information needs
 - c. Share decision-making

26. The staff treats the deceased person and his/her relatives in a correct and dignified manner.

- A.** There are guidelines ensuring observance of the legislation in connection with a death.
- B.** There are guidelines supporting correct and dignified treatment of the deceased person and his/her relatives.
- C.** Managers and staff are familiar with relevant parts of the guidelines and work accordingly.

CHAPTER-7
PATIENT AND FAMILY EDUCATION (PFE)

- 1. Patients are assessed on arrival to ensure their healthcare needs are met efficiently.**
 - A. Information on services, hours of operation and processes to obtain care are available to agencies and referral sources in the community and to the catchment population.
 - B. Assessment is initiated at the point of first contact with the hospital.
 - C. Patients attending for emergency care are triaged using an evidence-based triage process.
 - D. Patients identified by triage as having emergency or immediate needs are prioritised for assessment and intervention according to established criteria.
 - E. Patients are received into the hospital only if the hospital has the ability to provide the necessary services and settings for care.
 - F. Access to services not offered by the hospital is facilitated by providing patients with information on how to access these services.
 - G. Emergency patients who require transfer to another hospital for appropriate services are stabilised prior to transfer.
- 2. Partnerships in healthcare governance planning, design, measurement and evaluation**
 - A. The health service organisation:
 - Involves consumers in partnerships in the governance of, and to design, measure and evaluate, health care
 - Has processes so that the consumers involved in these partnerships reflect the diversity of consumers who use the service or, where relevant, the diversity of the local community
 - B. The health service organisation provides orientation, support and education to consumers who are partnering in the governance, design, measurement and evaluation of the organization
 - C. The health communities to meet their healthcare needs
 - D. The health service organisation works in partnership with consumers to incorporate their views and experiences into training and education for the workforce
- 3. The hospital seeks to identify and reduce barriers to access and delivery of services.**
 - A. The hospital has identified barriers to accessing healthcare services in its catchment population.
 - B. There is a process to limit the impact of barriers on access to the services provided by the hospital.
 - C. The hospital has access to ambulance services appropriate for the level of care provided.
- 4. Communication that supports effective partnerships**
 - A. The health service organisation uses communication mechanisms that are tailored to the diversity of the consumers who use its services and, where relevant, the diversity of the local community

- B. Where information for patients, carers, families and consumers about health and health services is developed internally, the organisation involves consumers in its development and review
 - C. The health service organisation supports clinicians to communicate with patients, carers, families and consumers about health and health care so that:
 - Information is provided in a way that meets the needs of patients, carers, families and consumers
 - Information provided is easy to understand and use
 - The clinical needs of patients are addressed while they are in the health service organisation
 - Information needs for ongoing care are provided on discharge
- 5. The organisation has a system for effective communication with patients and /or families.**
- A. Documented policies and procedures guide the effective communication with the patients and/or families.
 - B. The organisation shall identify special situations where enhanced communication would be required.
 - C. The organisation lays down an approach for effective communication in these identified situations.
 - D. The organisation also defines what constitutes an unacceptable communication and sensitizes the staff about the same.
 - E. The organisation has a system to monitor and review the implementation of effective communication
 - F. The staff are trained in healthcare communication techniques periodically.
- 6. The hospital plans and conducts the treatment involving the patient and relatives as partners.**
- A. The hospital has a policy on how to actively involve patients and relatives as partners when planning and implementing the treatment.
 - B. The hospital plans and conducts the treatment involving the patient and the relatives as partners in accordance with the policy.
 - C. The hospital has targets for the quality of the involvement of patients and relatives as partners, and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.
 - D. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the involvement of patients and relatives as partners. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.

7. Health education supports patient and family participation in care decisions and care processes.

- A. The hospital plans patient education consistent with its mission, services and patient population.
- B. There is an appropriate structure or mechanism for education throughout the hospital.
- C. Patients and families indicate that they have received health education appropriate to their condition.
- D. Patients indicate that they have been informed about the clinical management of their condition.
- E. Patients are educated about their diagnosis and relevant health risks, e.g. safe use of medication and medical equipment, medicine and food interaction, therapeutic diet and food interactions, defaulting on medication use, etc.
- F. When appropriate, patients and families indicate that they have been educated about the use of rehabilitation techniques and/or equipment.
- G. Interaction between personnel, the patient and the family is noted in the patient's record.

8. Organisational processes to support effective communication

- A. The health service organisation has clinical communications processes to support effective communication when:
 - a. Identification and procedure matching should occur
 - b. All or part of a patient's care is transferred within the organisation, between multidisciplinary teams, between clinicians or between organisations; and on discharge
 - c. Critical information about a patient's care, including information on risks, emerges or changes

9. Communicating critical information

- A. Clinicians and multidisciplinary teams use clinical communication processes to effectively communicate critical information, alerts and risks, in a timely way, when they emerge or change to:
 - a. Clinicians who can make decisions about care
 - b. Patients, carers and families, in accordance with the wishes of the patient
- B. The health service organisation ensures that there are communication processes for patients, carers and families to directly communicate critical information and risks about care to clinicians.

CHAPTER- 8

PHARMACY

- 1. Documented policies and procedures guide the organisation of pharmacy services and usage of medication.**
 - A. There is a documented policy and procedure for pharmacy services and medication usage.
 - B. Policies and procedures comply with the applicable laws and regulations.
 - C. A multidisciplinary committee guides the formulation and implementation of these policies and procedures.
 - D. There is a procedure to obtain medication when the pharmacy is closed.

- 2. There is a hospital formulary.**
 - A. A list of medications appropriate for the patients and as per the scope of the organisation's clinical services is developed collaboratively by the multidisciplinary committee.
 - B. The list is reviewed and updated collaboratively by the multidisciplinary committee at least annually.
 - C. The formulary is available for clinicians to refer and adhere to.
 - D. There is a defined process for acquisition of these medications.
 - E. There is a process to obtain medications not listed in the formulary.

- 3. Documented policies and procedures guide the storage of medication.**
 - A. Documented policies and procedures exist for storage of medication.
 - B. Medications are stored in a clean, safe and secure environment; and incorporating manufacturer's recommendation(s).
 - C. Sound inventory control practices guide storage of the medications in all areas throughout the organisation.
 - D. Look-alike and Sound-alike medications are identified and stored physically apart from each other.

- 4. The hospital stores medicine in a correct and safe manner.**
 - A. Patient-administered medicine is only available to the specific patient and the staff.
 - B. The department documents that medicine cupboards are checked at regular intervals.
 - C. If the inspection of the medicine cupboard shows lacks, initiatives have been made to improve the quality. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.

5. Documented policies and procedures guide the safe and rational prescription of medications.

- A. Documented policies and procedures exist for prescription of medications.
- B. These incorporate inclusion of good practices/guidelines for rational prescription of medications.
- C. The organisation determines the minimum requirements of a prescription.
- D. Known drug allergies are ascertained before prescribing.
- E. The organisation determines who can write orders.
- F. Orders are written in a uniform location in the medical records which also reflects patient's name and unique identification number.
- G. Medication orders are clear, legible, dated, timed, named and signed.
- H. Medication orders contain the name of the medicine, route of administration, dose to be administered and frequency/ time of administration.
- I. Documented policy and procedure on verbal orders is implemented.
- J. The organisation defines a list of high-risk medication(s).
- K. Audit of medication orders/prescription is carried out to check for safe and rational prescription of medications.
- L. Reconciliation of medications occur at transition points of patient care.
- M. Corrective and/or preventive action(s) is taken based on the analysis, where appropriate.

6. Documented policies and procedures guide the safe dispensing of medications.

- A. Documented policies and procedures guide the safe dispensing of medications.
- B. The procedure addresses medication recall.
- C. Expiry dates are checked prior to dispensing.
- D. There is a procedure for near expiry medications.
- E. Labelling requirements are documented and implemented by the organisation.
- F. High-risk medication orders are verified prior to dispensing.

7. The hospital has a process for correct dispensing of medicine.

- A. Control of difficult, individual dose calculations is conducted.
- B. Medicine poured and injection fluids/infusion fluids are labelled.
- C. Dispensing of medicine is documented in the unified pharmaceutical documentation system.

8. There are documented policies and procedures for medication administration.

- A. Medications are administered by those who are permitted by law to do so.
- B. Prepared medication is labelled prior to preparation of a second drug.

- C. Patient is identified prior to administration.
- D. Medication is verified from the order and physically inspected prior to administration.
- E. Dosage is verified from the order prior to administration.
- F. Route is verified from the order prior to administration.
- G. Timing is verified from the order prior to administration.
- H. Medication administration is documented.
- I. Documented policies and procedures govern patient's self-administration of medications.
- J. Documented policies and procedures govern patient's own medications brought from outside the organisation.

9. Medication use throughout the hospital complies with applicable laws and regulations.

- A. Only those permitted by the hospital and by relevant laws and regulations prescribe medication.
- B. On admission, all current medication taken by the patient is documented in the patient record, including herbal and over-the-counter medication.
- C. Verbal and telephonic medication prescriptions are documented according to hospital policy.

10. Patients are monitored after medication administration.

- A. Documented policies and procedures guide the monitoring of patients after medication administration.
- B. The organisation defines those situations where close monitoring is required.
- C. Monitoring is done in a collaborative manner.
- D. Medications are changed where appropriate based on the monitoring.

11. Near misses, medication errors and adverse drug events are reported and analysed.

- A. Documented procedure exists to capture near miss, medication error and adverse drug event.
- B. Near miss, medication error and adverse drug event are defined.
- C. These are reported within a specified time frame.
- D. They are collected and analysed.
- E. Corrective and/or preventive action(s) are taken based on the analysis where appropriate.

12. Documented procedures guide the use of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances.

- A. Documented procedures guide the use of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances which are in consonance with local and national regulations.
- B. These drugs are stored in a secure manner.

- C. A proper record is kept of the usage, administration and disposal of these drugs.
- D. These drugs are handled by appropriate personnel in accordance with the documented procedure.

13. Documented policies and procedures guide the usage of chemotherapeutic agents.

- A. Documented policies and procedures guide the usage of chemotherapeutic agents.
- B. Chemotherapy is prescribed by those who have the knowledge to monitor and treat the adverse effect of chemotherapy.
- C. Chemotherapy is prepared in a proper and safe manner and administered by qualified personnel.
- D. Chemotherapy drugs are disposed in accordance with legal requirements.
- E. Patient and family are educated regarding benefits/risks of chemotherapy, precautions to be taken and possible adverse reactions.

14. Medication and chemotherapy are safely administered.

- A. Only those permitted by the hospital and by relevant laws and regulations administer medication/chemotherapy.

15. Medication/ chemotherapy is stored in a safe and clean environment.

- A. Medication/ chemotherapy is stored in a locked storage device or cabinet that is accessible only to authorised personnel.
- B. Medication identified for special control (by law or hospital policy) is stored in a cabinet of substantial construction, for which only authorised personnel have the keys.
- C. Medication identified for special control (by law or hospital policy) is accurately accounted for.
- D. Medication/chemotherapy agents are securely and legibly labelled with relevant information as required by law and hospital policy.
- E. Medication/chemotherapy is stored in a clean environment.
- F. Medication/chemotherapy is stored in accordance with manufacturer's instructions relating to temperature, light and humidity.
- G. A refrigerator is available for medication/ chemotherapy requiring storage at low temperatures.
- H. The temperature of the refrigerator is monitored and recorded.
- I. Appropriate action is taken and recorded when the temperature of the refrigerator is outside the recommended range.
- J. Chemotherapy preparation is undertaken with protective gear and in an appropriate environment to protect the workers against possible adverse effects.

16. Documented policies and procedures govern usage of radioactive drugs.

- A. Documented policies and procedures govern usage of radioactive drugs.
- B. These policies and procedures are in consonance with laws and regulations.
- C. The policies and procedures include the safe storage, preparation, handling, distribution and disposal of radioactive drugs.
- D. Staff, patients and visitors are educated on safety precautions.

17. Documented policies and procedures guide the use of implantable prosthesis and medical devices.

- A. Usage of implantable prosthesis and medical devices is guided by scientific criteria for each individual item and national/international recognised guidelines/ approvals for such specific item(s).
- B. Documented policies and procedures govern procurement, storage/stocking, issuance and usage of implantable prosthesis and medical devices incorporating manufacturer's recommendation(s).
- C. Patient and his/her family are counselled for the usage of implantable prosthesis and medical device including precautions, if any.
- D. The batch and serial number of the implantable prosthesis and medical devices are recorded in the patient's medical record, the master logbook and the discharge summary.

18. Documented policies and procedures guide the use of medical supplies and consumables.

- A. There is a defined process for acquisition of medical supplies and consumables.
- B. Medical supplies and consumables are used in a safe manner, where appropriate.
- C. Medical supplies and consumables are stored in a clean, safe and secure environment; and incorporating manufacturer's recommendation(s).
- D. Sound inventory control practices guide storage of medical supplies and consumables.
- E. There is a mechanism in place to verify the condition of medical supplies and consumables.

19. Integrating clinical governance

- A. Clinicians use the safety and quality systems from the Clinical Governance Standard when:
 - Implementing policies and procedures for medication management
 - Managing risks associated with medication management
 - Identifying training requirements for medication management

20. Applying quality improvement systems

- A. The health service organisation applies the quality improvement system from the Clinical Governance Standard when:
- Monitoring the effectiveness and performance of medication management
 - Implementing strategies to improve medication management outcomes and associated processes
 - Reporting on outcomes for medication management

21. Partnering with consumers

- A. Clinicians use organisational processes from the Partnering with Consumers Standard in medication management to:
- Actively involve patients in their own care
 - Meet the patient's information needs
 - Share decision-making

22. Medicines scope of clinical practice

- A. The health service organisation has processes to define and verify the scope of clinical practice for prescribing, dispensing and administering medicines for relevant clinicians

23. Medication reconciliation

- A. Clinicians take a best possible medication history, which is documented in the healthcare record on presentation or as early as possible in the episode of care
- B. Clinicians review a patient's current medication orders against their best possible medication history and the documented treatment plan, and reconcile any discrepancies on presentation and at transitions of care

24. Adverse drug reactions

- A. The health service organisation has processes for documenting a patient's history of medicine allergies and adverse drug reactions in the healthcare record on presentation
- B. The health service organisation has processes for documenting adverse drug reactions experienced by patients during an episode of care in the healthcare record and in the organisation-wide incident reporting system
- C. The health service organisation has processes for reporting adverse drug reactions experienced by patients to the Therapeutic Goods Administration, in accordance with its requirements

25. Provision of a medicines list

- A. The health service organisation has processes to:
- Generate a current medicines list and the reasons for any changes

- Distribute the current medicines list to receiving clinicians at transitions of care
- Provide patients on discharge with a current medicines list and the reasons for any changes

26. Information and decision support tools for medicines

- A. The health service organisation ensures that information and decision support tools for medicines are available to clinicians

27. Safe and secure storage and distribution of medicines

- A. The health service organisation complies with manufacturers' directions, legislation, and jurisdictional requirements for the:
 - Safe and secure storage and distribution of medicines
 - Storage of temperature-sensitive medicines and cold chain management
 - Disposal of unused, unwanted or expired medicines

28. Medication is stored in a secure and clean environment.

- A. Separate designated storage areas for the receipt and unpacking of incoming goods are provided.
- B. Hazardous and flammable materials are stored in accordance with relevant regulations.
- C. Separate designated storage areas for materials under quarantine are provided.
- D. Safe and secure storage facilities are available, including smoke detectors, security alarm systems and/or barriers.
- E. Stock control systems are managed in the pharmacy and other related departments.
- F. A management information system is available, which provides accurate statistics relating to pharmaceutical receipts and issues.
- G. Medication is stored in a clean environment.
- H. The cold chain is maintained for medication where necessary.
- I. Medication storage areas are protected from heat, light and moisture and temperatures are monitored and recorded.
- J. Appropriate action is taken when temperatures are higher or lower than recommended limits.
- K. Medication identified for special control by law or hospital policy are stored in a cabinet of substantial construction, for which only authorised personnel have a key.
- L. Medication identified for special control by law or hospital policy are accurately accounted for.

29. High-risk medicines

- A. The health service organisation:
- Identifies high-risk medicines used within the organisation
 - Has a system to store, prescribe, dispense and administer high-risk medicines safely

30. Medicine used in emergency situations is easily accessible.

- A. There are guidelines describing how the availability of medicine for use in emergency situations is secured.
- B. The emergency trays are available and are controlled in accordance with the guidelines.
- C. The emergency trays are available for relevant staff in emergency situations.
- D. The control of the emergency trays is documented in the logbook and in particular it is noted that emergency trays are full after opening.
- E. If the inspection shows lacks in relation to availability and content of emergency trays, initiatives have been made to improve the quality. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.

31. The hospital uses medicine review for defined risk patients.

- A. There are guidelines describing how, when and whom makes and documents medicine review which are common for the hospital. Likewise, the guidelines document criteria for when patients should have medicine reviews performed. The guidelines furthermore define criteria when to perform medicine reviews among outpatients with a chronic disease. If the responsibility is shared with the primary sector, the division of responsibility and tasks is documented.
- B. Medicine review is made in accordance with the hospital's guidelines.
- C. The medicine review is documented in the patient health record.
- D. The hospital has targets for the quality of medicine review. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets. Data are analysed and assessed.
- E. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of medicine review. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.

32. The hospital receives medicine of an appropriate amount in relation to the handling of tasks.

- A. There are guidelines for ordering and receiving medicine both in connection with planned and acute situations.

- B. The hospital describes precautionary measures for situations where the supply of medicine fails.
- C. Medicine is ordered and requested in accordance with the guidelines.
- D. Follow-up on breakdown in deliveries and faulty deliveries on reception of medicine is conducted.
- E. Relevant managers and staff are familiar with the precautionary measures for situations where the supply of medicine fails.

33. Medication use is organised throughout the hospital to meet the needs of patients.

- A. The pharmaceutical service is managed by a registered pharmacist with clearly defined responsibilities and accountability for all aspects of the service.
- B. A registered pharmacist is designated as deputy to act in the absence of the manager.
- C. The responsibilities of the pharmacy manager include ensuring compliance with laws and regulations relating to the service.
- D. The responsibilities of the pharmacy manager include ensuring compliance with pharmacy practice and current pharmaceutical and other health professional guidelines, e.g. medical and nursing.
- E. The pharmacy manager facilitates collaboration between pharmacy personnel and other relevant personnel in the hospital to ensure safe prescribing, ordering, storage, preparation, dispensing and administration of medications.
- F. The manager ensures that reliable drug information is readily accessible.

34. An appropriate selection of medication for prescribing or ordering is stocked or readily available.

- A. Medication available for prescribing and ordering is appropriate for the hospital's mission, patient needs and services provided.
- B. There is a list of medication stocked in the hospital or readily available from outside sources.
- C. There is a method for control of medication use within the hospital.
- D. There is a process to obtain required medication which is not routinely stocked or normally available to the hospital.
- E. There is a process to obtain required medication when the pharmacy is closed.
- F. Emergency medication is available in the hospital within a time frame to meet emergency needs.
- G. Emergency medication is monitored and replaced in a timely manner, after use or when expired or damaged.
- H. In the event of medication stock outs, prescribers are informed of the stock out and advised of suitable alternatives.

35. There is a collaborative process to develop and monitor policies and procedures for the pharmaceutical service.

- A. Policies and procedures, which include the standard intent as a minimum, are developed and implemented.
- B. There is evidence that policies and procedures have been developed collaboratively with all relevant departments.

36. Medication is dispensed in accordance with legislation, regulations and professional standards of practice.

- A. Medication is prepared and dispensed in a safe and clean environment.
- B. There is a uniform medication dispensing and distribution system throughout the hospital.
- C. The system supports accurate and timely dispensing.
- D. Where computer programs are used to check for contra-indications and potential drug interactions for prescribed medication, there is a process to ensure that the program is current and updated according to the manufacturer's recommendations.

37. Medication is ordered according to hospital policy and stored in a secure and clean environment.

- A. Medication is ordered according to hospital policy.
- B. All storage areas for medicines and pharmaceutical supplies comply with current pharmaceutical acts and regulations and manufacturer guidelines (e.g. security, temperature control).
- C. Medication is stored in a locked storage device or cabinet that is accessible only to authorised personnel.
- D. Medication identified for special control by legislation or hospital policy is stored in a cabinet of substantial construction, for which only authorised personnel have the keys.
- E. Medication identified for special control by legislation or hospital policy is accurately accounted for.
- F. Medication is securely and legibly labelled with relevant information as required by legislation and hospital policy.
- G. Medication is stored in a clean environment.
- H. A dedicated refrigerator is available for medication requiring storage at low temperatures.
- I. The temperature of the refrigerator is monitored and recorded according to hospital policy.
- J. Appropriate action is taken and recorded when the temperature of the refrigerator is outside the recommended range.
- K. Expiry dates (including those of emergency drugs) are checked regularly at defined intervals according to hospital policy and drugs are replaced before the expiry date.

38. Medication and chemotherapy use in the hospital complies with applicable laws and regulations.

- A. The use of verbal/telephonic medication orders is documented according to hospital policy.
- B. Only those permitted by the hospital and by relevant laws and regulations prescribe medication and chemotherapy.
- C. Medication, including herbal and over-the-counter medication, brought into the hospital by the patient or the family is known to the patient's medical practitioner and is noted in the patient's record.

CHAPTER- 9
PREVENTION AND CONTROL OF INFECTION (PCI)

- 1. The organisation has a well-designed, comprehensive and coordinated Hospital Infection Prevention and Control (HIC) programme aimed at reducing/ eliminating risks to patients, visitors and providers of care.**
 - A. The hospital infection prevention and control programme is documented which aims at preventing and reducing risk of healthcare associated infections in all areas of the hospital.
 - B. The infection prevention and control programme is a continuous process and updated at least once in a year.
 - C. The hospital has a multi-disciplinary infection control committee, which coordinates all infection prevention and control activities.
 - D. The hospital has an infection control team, which coordinates implementation of all infection prevention and control activities.
 - E. The hospital has designated infection control officer as part of the infection control team.
 - F. The hospital has designated infection control nurse(s) as part of the infection control team.

- 2. Infection control management**
 - A. The programme is appropriate to the size and geographic location of the hospital, the services offered and the patients served.
 - B. Coordination of infection control activities involves medical, nursing and other personnel as appropriate to the hospital.
 - C. All patient, personnel and visitor areas of the hospital are included in the infection control activities.
 - D. Responsibility for coordinating the activities is assigned to one individual or a committee.
 - E. The individuals are competent to manage the scope and complexity of the activities.
 - F. The infection control activities are based on current scientific knowledge, accepted practice guidelines and applicable laws and regulations.
 - G. Information management systems support the infection control activities.

- 3. The organisation implements the policies and procedures laid down in the Infection Control Manual in all areas of the hospital.**
 - A. The organisation identifies the various high-risk areas and procedures and implements policies and/or procedures to prevent infection in these areas.
 - B. The organisation adheres to standard precautions at all times.
 - C. The organisation adheres to hand-hygiene guidelines.
 - D. Clinicians assess infection risks and use transmission-based precautions based on the risk of transmission of infectious agents, and consider:

- Patients' risks, which are evaluated at referral, on admission or on presentation for care, and re-evaluated when clinically required during care
 - Whether a patient has a communicable disease, or an existing or a pre-existing colonisation or infection with organisms of local or national significance
 - Accommodation needs to manage infection risks
 - The need to control the environment
 - Precautions required when the patient is moved within the facility or to external services
 - The need for additional environmental cleaning or disinfection
 - Equipment requirements
- E.** The organisation adheres to safe injection and infusion practices.
- F.** The organisation adheres to cleaning, disinfection and sterilization practices.
- G.** An appropriate antibiotic policy is established and documented
- H.** The organisation implements the antibiotic policy and monitors rational use of antimicrobial agents.
- I.** The organisation adheres to laundry and linen management processes.
- J.** The organisation adheres to kitchen sanitation and food-handling issues.
- K.** The organisation has appropriate engineering controls to prevent infections.
- L.** The organisation adheres to housekeeping procedures.

4. The organisation performs surveillance activities to capture and monitor infection prevention and control data.

- A.** Surveillance activities are appropriately directed towards the identified high-risk areas and procedures.
- B.** A Collection of surveillance data is an on-going process.
- C.** Verification of data is done on a regular basis by the infection control team.
- D.** The scope of surveillance activities incorporates tracking and analyzing of infection risks, rates and trends.
- E.** Surveillance activities include monitoring the compliance with hand-hygiene guidelines.
- F.** Surveillance activities include mechanisms to capture the occurrence of epidemiological significant diseases, multi-drug-resistant organisms and highly virulent infections.
- G.** Surveillance activities include monitoring the effectiveness of housekeeping services.
- H.** Appropriate feedback regarding Healthcare Associated Infection (HAI) rates is provided on a regular basis to appropriate personnel.

- I. In cases of notifiable diseases, information (in relevant format) is sent to appropriate authorities.

5. Surveillance

- A. The health service organisation has a surveillance strategy for healthcare associated infections and antimicrobial use that:
 - Collects data on healthcare-associated infections and antimicrobial use relevant to the size and scope of the organisation
 - Monitors, assesses and uses surveillance data to reduce the risks associated with healthcare-associated infections and support
 - appropriate antimicrobial prescribing
 - Reports surveillance data on healthcare-associated infections and antimicrobial use to the workforce, the governing body, consumers and other relevant groups

6. The organisation takes actions to prevent and control Healthcare Associated Infections (HAI) / Nosocomial Infections in patients.

- A. The organisation takes action to prevent catheter-associated urinary tract Infections.
- B. The organisation takes action to prevent Ventilator Associated Pneumonia.
- C. The organisation takes action to prevent catheter linked blood stream infections.
- D. The organisation takes action to prevent surgical site infections.

7. Infection control processes

- A. The hospital has identified those processes associated with the risk of infection and implemented strategies to reduce such risk.
- B. Policies and procedures to guide personnel in the implementation of adequate infection prevention and control measures are readily accessible and implemented.
- C. Processes associated with risk are documented.
- D. Epidemiologically significant diseases and organisms are included as appropriate to the hospital and its community.
- E. Emerging or re-emerging infections are included as appropriate to the hospital and its community.

8. The organisation provides adequate and appropriate resources for prevention and control of Healthcare Associated Infections (HAI).

- A. Adequate and appropriate personal protective equipment, soaps, and disinfectants are available and used correctly.
- B. Adequate and appropriate facilities for hand hygiene in all patient-care areas are accessible to healthcare providers.

- C. Isolation/barrier nursing facilities are available.
- D. Appropriate pre- and post-exposure prophylaxis is provided to all staff members concerned.

9. The organisation identifies and takes appropriate action to control outbreaks of infections.

- A. Organisation has a documented procedure for identifying an outbreak.
- B. The hygiene organisation prepares an annual report describing handling of outbreak of infectious diseases, screening for resistant bacteria and other nationally and locally specified focus areas set out in the hospital's hygiene policy. The report includes targets for the hospital's handling of nosocomial infections.
- C. Organisation has a documented procedure for handling such outbreaks.
- D. This procedure is implemented during outbreaks.
- E. After the outbreak is over appropriate corrective actions are taken to prevent recurrence.

10. There are documented policies and procedures for sterilization activities in the organisation.

- A. The organisation provides adequate space and appropriate zoning for sterilization activities.
- B. Documented procedure guides the cleaning, packing, disinfection and/or sterilization, storing and issue of items.
- C. Reprocessing of instruments and equipment are covered.
- D. The organisation shall have a documented policy and procedure for reprocessing of devices whenever applicable.
- E. Regular validation tests for sterilization are carried out and documented.
- F. There is an established recall procedure when breakdown in the sterilization system is identified.

11. Biomedical waste (BMW) is handled in an appropriate and safe manner.

- A. The organisation adheres to statutory provisions with regard to biomedical waste.
- B. Proper segregation and collection of biomedical waste from all patient-care areas of the hospital is implemented and monitored.
- C. The organisation ensures that biomedical waste is stored and transported to the site of treatment and disposal in properly covered vehicles within stipulated time limits in a secure manner.
- D. The biomedical waste treatment facility is managed as per statutory provisions (if in-house) or outsourced to authorized contractor(s).
- E. Appropriate personal protective measures are used by all categories of staff handling biomedical waste.

12. The infection control programme is supported by the management and includes training of staff.

- A. The management makes available resources required for the infection control programme.
- B. The organisation earmarks adequate funds from its annual budget in this regard.
- C. The organisation conducts induction training for all staff.
- D. The organisation conducts appropriate —in-service training sessions for all staff at least once in a year.

13. Integrating clinical governance

- A. The workforce uses the safety and quality systems from the Clinical Governance Standard when:
 - Implementing policies and procedures for healthcare-associated infections and antimicrobial stewardship
 - Managing risks associated with healthcare-associated infections and antimicrobial stewardship
 - Identifying training requirements for preventing and controlling healthcare-associated infections, and antimicrobial stewardship

14. Applying quality improvement systems

- A. The health service organisation applies the quality improvement system from the Clinical Governance Standard when:
 - Monitoring the performance of systems for prevention and control of healthcare-associated infections, and the effectiveness of the antimicrobial stewardship program
 - Implementing strategies to improve outcomes and associated processes of systems for prevention and control of healthcare associated infections, and antimicrobial stewardship
 - Reporting on the outcomes of prevention and control of healthcare associated infections, and the antimicrobial stewardship program

15. Partnering with consumers

- A. Clinicians use organisational processes from the Partnering with Consumers Standard when preventing and managing healthcare-associated infections, and implementing the antimicrobial stewardship program to:
 - Actively involve patients in their own care
 - Meet the patient's information needs
 - Share decision-making
- B. The health service organisation has processes for communicating relevant details of a patient's infectious status whenever responsibility for care is transferred between clinicians or health service organisations

16. Hand hygiene is correctly performed and correct uniform is used.

- A. The health service organisation has a hand hygiene program that:
- Is consistent with the current National Hand Hygiene Initiative,
 - Addresses noncompliance or inconsistency with the current National Hand Hygiene Initiative
- B. Hand hygiene is implemented in accordance with the hospital's guidelines.
- C. Uniform and use of hand jewellery and wrist watches are in accordance with the hospital's guidelines.
- D. The hospital has goals for the quality of hand and uniform hygiene. The goals could be process goals (implementation of correct procedures) and outcomes (occurrence of infections related to lacks in hand and uniform hygiene). The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the goals. Data are analysed and assessed.
- E. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of hand and uniform hygiene. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.

17. Aseptic technique

- A. The health service organisation has processes for aseptic technique that:
- Identify the procedures where aseptic technique applies
 - Assess the competence of the workforce in performing aseptic technique
 - Provide training to address gaps in competency
 - Monitor compliance with the organisation's policies on aseptic technique

18. Invasive medical devices

- A. The health service organisation has processes for the appropriate use and management of invasive medical devices that are consistent with the current standard.

19. Clean environment

- A. The health service organisation has processes to maintain a clean and hygienic environment that:
- Respond to environmental risks
 - Require cleaning and disinfection in line with recommended cleaning frequencies
 - Include training in the appropriate use of specialised personal protective equipment for the workforce

- B.** The health service organisation has processes to evaluate and respond to infection risks for:
- New and existing equipment, devices and products used in the organisation
 - Maintaining, repairing and upgrading buildings, equipment, furnishings and fittings
 - Handling, transporting and storing linen

20. Workforce immunization

- A.** The health service organisation has a risk-based workforce immunization program that:
- Is consistent with the current edition of the National Immunization Handbook
 - Is consistent with jurisdictional requirements for vaccine-preventable diseases
 - Addresses specific risks to the workforce and patients

21. Reprocessing of reusable devices

- A.** Where reusable equipment, instruments and devices are used, the health service organisation has:
- Processes for reprocessing that are consistent with relevant national and international standards, in conjunction with manufacturers' guidelines
 - A traceability process for critical and semi-critical equipment, instruments and devices that is capable of identifying
 - the patient
 - the procedure
 - the reusable equipment, instruments and devices that were used for the procedure

22. The hospital prevents nosocomial infections while reprocessing equipment and textiles.

- A.** There are guidelines for procedures and working procedures while reprocessing of medical equipment for reuse.
- B.** There are joint guidelines for the entire hospital for handling, storing and washing of textiles for reuse.
- C.** Medical equipment for reuse is reprocessed in accordance with the standard.
- D.** Textiles are handled and stored in a correct manner in accordance with the standard.
- E.** The hospital has targets for the quality of reprocessing medical equipment and textiles. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets. The quality monitoring includes

cleaning and disinfection of flexible endoscopes. Data are analysed and assessed.

- F. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of reprocessing medical equipment and textiles. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.

23. Antimicrobial stewardship

- A. The health service organisation has an antimicrobial stewardship program that:
- Includes an antimicrobial stewardship policy
 - Provides access to, and promotes the use of, current evidence-based National therapeutic guidelines and resources on antimicrobial prescribing
 - Has an antimicrobial formulary that includes restriction rules and approval processes
 - Incorporates core elements, recommendations and principles from the current Antimicrobial Stewardship Clinical Care Standard²⁰
- B. The antimicrobial stewardship program will:
- Review antimicrobial prescribing and use
 - Use surveillance data on antimicrobial resistance and use to support appropriate prescribing
 - Evaluate performance of the program, identify areas for improvement,
 - and take action to improve the appropriateness of antimicrobial prescribing and use
 - Report to clinicians and the governing body regarding
 - compliance with the antimicrobial stewardship policy
 - antimicrobial use and resistance
 - appropriateness of prescribing and compliance with current evidence-based National therapeutic guidelines or resources on antimicrobial prescribing

24. Building, facilities and fixtures are cleaned in accordance with stipulated quality requirements.

- A. There are plans for cleaning the hospital's buildings, facilities and fixtures.

25. Obtaining of laboratory cultures

- A. The hospital identifies those environmental sites from which specimens are to be collected.

- B. The hospital identifies the frequency with which specimens are collected.
- C. Procedures which describe how specimens are taken and sent to the laboratory, and action to be taken when laboratory reports identify pathogenic organisms, are implemented.

26. Infection control education for personnel

- A. The hospital provides ongoing in-service training in infection control to all personnel.
- B. Personnel are educated in infection control processes when new policies are implemented.
- C. Personnel are provided with additional education in relevant aspects of the infection control processes when significant trends are noted in surveillance data.
- D. Patients and families are educated when appropriate to the patient's needs and condition.

27. Infection control quality management

- A. The hospital tracks infection risks, infection rates and trends in healthcare-associated infections.
- B. Monitoring includes the use of indicators related to infections that are epidemiologically important to the hospital.
- C. The hospital uses risk, rate and trend information to design or modify processes to reduce healthcare associated infections to the lowest possible levels.
- D. The hospital compares its infection rates with other hospitals through comparative databases.
- E. The results of infection monitoring in the hospital are regularly communicated to medical and nursing personnel and to the management of the hospital.
- F. The hospital reports information on infections to appropriate external public health agencies.

28. The department/service implements infection prevention and control processes.

- A. The department identifies the procedures and processes associated with the risk of infection and implements strategies to reduce risk.
- B. Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of respiratory tract infections.
- C. Personnel are trained in correct hand washing procedures.
- D. Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of urinary tract infections.
- E. Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of infection through intravascular invasive devices.

- F. Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of infection through surgical wounds.
- G. Infection control processes include safe injection practices, including single-use injection devices.
- H. Personnel responsible for sluicing are appropriately trained and made aware of the potential hazards associated with sluicing.
- I. Infection control measures of particle counts and bacterial growth are performed in each theatre according to hospital policy.
- J. Policies and procedures address the correct management of sharps within the department
- K. Post exposure prophylaxis kits are readily available for personnel and employees who sustain needle stick injuries.
- L. Information regarding needle stick injuries is recorded and action taken as appropriate
- M. Personnel and employees are routinely offered BCG and vaccination for Hepatitis B.
- N. Sero-conversion is measured and recorded in personnel folders
- O. Booster vaccinations are offered as appropriate
- P. Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of infection through use of medical and rehabilitation equipment.
- Q. Infection control processes include prevention of infection from contaminated instruments.
- R. Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of food-related infections.
- S. Infection control processes include in-service training on appropriate disinfection of medical equipment as part of the maintenance process.

29. The department/service implements infection prevention and control processes.

- A. Infection control processes include prevention of infection while undertaking sterile procedures.
- B. Infection control processes include prevention of infection during the process of preparation and dispensing of medication.
- C. Infection control processes include prevention of water contamination during the preparation of suspensions/liquid medications.

30. The Occupational Health Service undertakes monitoring and prevention measures for notifiable medical conditions and communicable diseases where relevant.

- A. The Occupational Health Service identifies, investigates and monitors the outbreak of communicable disease when indicated.
- B. The Occupational Health Service institutes the necessary corrective and preventive occupational health measures when required.

- C. The Occupational Health Service participates in the development of necessary reaction teams in relation to municipal health measures.
- D. The Occupational Health Service promotes health and hygiene aimed at the prevention of occupational conditions that lead to communicable diseases.
- E. The Occupational Health Service gathers, analyses and distributes epidemiological data and information.
- F. There is an appropriate system in place for the prompt reporting of notifiable medical conditions.
- G. There is a system in place to ensure the referral and uptake of confirmed cases of relevant communicable diseases into appropriate treatment programmes.

31. The department/service implements infection prevention and control processes.

- A. Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of infection related to infected linen.
- B. Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of infection related to the separation of soiled and clean linen.
- C. The sluicing process has been approved by a hospital's infection control coordinator.
- D. Infection control processes include effective hand washing procedures.
- E. No eating, drinking or smoking is permitted in the laundry areas.

32. Infection Control in Housekeeping

- A. Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of infection related to the cleaning and storage of cleaning equipment.
- B. Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of infection related to the correct dilution of cleaning chemicals
- C. Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of infection related to implementing the colour-coded identification of mops for different areas

CHAPTER-10
LABORATORY (LB)

- 1. Laboratory services are available to meet the needs of patients in compliance with local and national laws, regulations and standards.**
 - A. Adequate, convenient and regular laboratory services are available to meet the hospital's needs.
 - B. Where laboratory services are outsourced, the hospital has a valid service level agreement with an accredited laboratory.
 - C. The laboratory services are organised and provided in a manner that meets applicable local and national standards, laws and regulations.
 - D. Emergency laboratory services are available, including after-hours services.
 - E. The hospital has established the expected turnaround times for results.
 - F. Laboratory results are reported within the agreed turnaround times.

- 2. A qualified individual is responsible for managing the Laboratory Service.**
 - A. The laboratory is under the direction of a qualified individual.
 - B. The responsibilities of this person include maintaining quality control programmes.
 - C. The responsibilities of this person include administrative supervision.
 - D. The responsibilities of this person include the monitoring and reviewing of all laboratory services.

- 3. Individuals with adequate training, skills, orientation and experience administer tests and interpret the results.**
 - A. Those individuals who may perform testing and those who may direct or supervise testing are identified.
 - B. Appropriately trained and experienced personnel administer tests.
 - C. Appropriately trained and experienced personnel interpret tests.
 - D. Laboratory results are validated and include unique patient identities, the date of testing/reporting, name and location of requesting physician.
 - E. The validating officer is identified and recorded.
 - F. There is an adequate number of personnel to meet patient needs.
 - G. A roster of experts for specialised diagnostic areas is maintained.
 - H. There is a record of each test done, by whom, the result thereof and a monthly summary.

- 4. Laboratory services are provided as per the scope of services of the organisation.**
 - A. Scope of the laboratory services commensurate to the services provided by the organisation.

- B. The infrastructure (physical and equipment) is adequate to provide the defined scope of services.
- C. The manpower is adequate to provide the defined scope of services.
- D. Qualified and trained personnel perform, supervise and interpret the investigations.
- E. Documented procedures guide ordering of tests, collection, identification, handling, safe transportation, processing and disposal of specimens.
- F. Laboratory results are available within a defined time frame.
- G. Critical results are intimated immediately to the personnel concerned.
- H. Results are reported in a standardised manner.
- I. There is a mechanism to address recall / amendment of reports whenever applicable.
- J. Laboratory tests not available in the organisation are outsourced to organisation(s) based on their quality assurance system.

5. Laboratory buildings are adequate to provide a safe and effective laboratory service.

- A. The laboratory is a separate designated area within, or in close proximity to, the hospital.
- B. The size of the laboratory is appropriate to the services provided.
- C. The walls, ceilings and floors are smooth, easy to clean, impermeable to liquids and resistant to chemicals.
- D. Hand washing facilities with running water are provided in each laboratory room, preferably near the exit door.
- E. Separate facilities are provided for personnel to store personal items.
- F. Separate rest-room facilities where personnel can eat and drink are available.

6. Laboratory fixtures and fittings are adequate to provide a safe and effective laboratory service.

- A. There are sufficient laboratory benches for the projected activities.
- B. Laboratory benches are strong enough for the projected activities (e.g. large instruments).
- C. Space around and under benches should allow for ease of cleaning and maintenance.
- D. Storage space is adequate to hold supplies for immediate use and to prevent clutter of bench tops.
- E. There is either an uninterrupted power supply (UPS) or battery backup system, and an automated voltage stabiliser (AVS) present for critical equipment, which are tested regularly and the results of testing are fully documented.
- F. Each laboratory compartment has adequate ventilation, room temperature is maintained below 25°C and a temperature record is kept.

- 7. There is adequate laboratory equipment to provide a safe and effective laboratory service.**
 - A. Sufficient equipment is available to provide the required laboratory services for the projected activities.
 - B. All equipment is in good working order, operated appropriately and functioning well.
 - C. There are laboratory equipment management processes.
 - D. The processes include selecting, acquiring and replacing of equipment.
 - E. The processes include taking an inventory of the equipment.
 - F. The processes include monitoring and follow-up.
 - G. There is adequate documentation of all testing, maintenance and calibration of equipment.

- 8. The supplies of laboratory consumables, reagents, chemicals and kits are adequate to provide a safe and effective laboratory service.**
 - A. The available supplies, consumables, reagents, chemicals and kits are sufficient for projected activities.
 - B. Specific laboratory reagents, chemicals and kits are used appropriately.
 - C. All reagents and chemicals are stored and dispensed according to guidelines.
 - D. All reagents and solutions are completely and accurately labelled.
 - E. All reagents are periodically evaluated for accuracy and results.
 - F. All reagents are stored in a lockable storage room or cupboard.
 - G. A named person is responsible for the specimen and reagent fridges.

- 9. Procedures are followed for collecting, identifying, transporting and tracking specimens or samples and reporting the results.**
 - A. Policies and procedures or standard operating procedures (SOPs) for handling specimens are implemented.
 - B. Request forms and specimen labels include unique patient identifiers and adequate supporting information.
 - C. There is a collection and delivery service for specimens from the hospital, every weekday.
 - D. Specimens are given a laboratory specimen accession number.
 - E. Procedures guide the ordering of tests.
 - F. Procedures guide the collection and identification of specimens.
 - G. Procedures guide the transport, storage and preservation of specimens.
 - H. Procedures guide receiving, logging-in and tracking of specimens.
 - I. Emergency results may be obtained by telephone.

- 10. Established norms and ranges are used to interpret and report clinical laboratory results.**
 - A. Policies and procedures or standard operating procedures regarding reporting and reviewing results are implemented.

- B. The laboratory has established reference ranges for each test performed.
- C. The range is included in the clinical record at the time test results are reported.
- D. Ranges are provided when tests are performed by outside sources.
- E. Ranges are appropriate to the hospital's catchment population.
- F. Ranges are reviewed and updated, as needed.

11. Quality control procedures are implemented and documented.

- A. There is a quality control process for the clinical laboratory.
- B. The process includes the validation of test methods.
- C. The process includes the daily surveillance of test results.
- D. The process includes the rapid correction of deficiencies.
- E. There is a current register of quality control results and of the corrective and preventive actions taken.
- F. The laboratory participates in a proficiency testing programme, or an alternative, for all speciality laboratory services and tests.
- G. A cumulative record of participation is maintained.
- H. The hospital regularly reviews quality control results from all outside sources of laboratory services.
- I. Copies of the quality control audits for the past six months verify that accurate/reliable results are being provided.

12. There is an established laboratory quality assurance programme.

- A. The laboratory quality assurance programme is documented.
- B. The programme addresses verification and / or validation of test methods.
- C. The programme addresses surveillance of test results.
- D. The programme includes periodic calibration and maintenance of all equipment.
- E. The programme includes the documentation of corrective and preventive actions.

13. Diagnostic examinations with equipment and/or staff attached to nondiagnostic departments are subject to the same quality control as examinations performed at diagnostic departments.

- A. There are guidelines for quality control of diagnostic examinations which are performed outside diagnostic department.
- B. Staff performing diagnostic examinations outside diagnostic departments obtain and maintain the right competences.
- C. The responsibility for quality control, calibration and correct use of equipment is clearly assigned and known by relevant staff.
- D. The responsibility for interpretation and documentation of the results of the examinations is clearly assigned and known by relevant staff.
- E. The hospital has targets for the quality of the examinations performed outside diagnostic department and the hospital assesses whether the

target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.

- F. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the examinations performed outside diagnostic department. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.

14. Early follow-up on test results and results of examinations are performed.

- A. The hospital has targets for the quality of early reaction to test results. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets. The quality monitoring includes deadlines for responses. Data are analysed and assessed.
- B. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of early reaction to test results. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element is not relevant if the hospital meets the stipulated quality goals.

15. The department/service implements infection prevention and control processes.

- A. Personal protective equipment, including eye protection, is available to all personnel.
- B. Individuals who handle specimens are trained in the correct handling of dangerous specimens.
- C. Suitable processes are followed for cleaning and decontamination of laboratory surfaces and equipment.

16. There is an established laboratory safety programme.

- A. The laboratory safety programme is documented.
- B. This programme is aligned with the organisation's safety programme.
- C. Written procedures guide the handling and disposal of infectious and hazardous materials.
- D. Laboratory personnel are appropriately trained in safe practices.
- E. Laboratory personnel are provided with appropriate safety equipment / devices.

17. The outpatient department is adequately supported by clinical laboratory services.

- A. Laboratory services are available at all times.

- B. Established waiting times for laboratory tests to be done according to triage status are monitored.
- C. Established waiting times for laboratory results to be available are monitored.
- D. Laboratory services are available to meet the needs of employees.
- E. A register is kept of all laboratory specimens sent and results received.

18. Documented policies and procedures define rational use of blood and blood components.

- A. Documented policies and procedures are used to guide the rational use of blood and blood components.
- B. Documented procedures govern transfusion of blood and blood components
- C. The transfusion services are governed by the applicable laws and regulations.
- D. Informed consent is obtained for donation and transfusion of blood and blood components.
- E. Informed consent also includes patient and family education about the donation.
- F. The organisation defines the process for availability and transfusion of blood/ blood components for use in emergency situations.
- G. Post-transfusion form is collected, reactions if any identified and are analysed for preventive and corrective actions.
- H. Staff are trained to implement the policies.
- I. There are guidelines for procedure for identification of patient and blood sample/blood components.
- J. Indication for blood transfusion is documented in the patient health record.
- K. The hospital has targets for the quality of infusion with blood components. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets. Data are analysed and assessed.
- L. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of infusion with blood components. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.

19. Optimising and conserving patients' own blood

- A. Clinicians use the blood and blood products processes to manage the need for, and minimise the inappropriate use of, blood and blood products by:
 - Optimising patients' own red cell mass, haemoglobin and iron stores
 - Identifying and managing patients with, or at risk of, bleeding

- Determining the clinical need for blood and blood products, and related risks

20. Partnering with consumers

- A. Clinicians use organisational processes from the Partnering with Consumers Standard when providing safe blood management to:
- Actively involve patients in their own care
 - Meet the patient's information needs
 - Share decision-making

21. Documenting

- A. Clinicians document decisions relating to blood management, transfusion history and transfusion details in the healthcare record

22. Prescribing and administering blood and blood products

- A. The health service organisation supports clinicians to prescribe and administer blood and blood products appropriately, in accordance with national guidelines and national criteria

23. Storing, distributing and tracing blood and blood products

- A. The health service organisation has processes:
- That comply with manufacturers' directions, legislation, and relevant jurisdictional requirements to store, distribute and handle blood and blood products safely and securely
 - To trace blood and blood products from entry into the organisation to transfusion, discard or transfer

24. Availability of blood

- A. The health service organisation has processes to:
- Manage the availability of blood and blood products to meet clinical need
 - Eliminate avoidable wastage
 - Respond in times of shortage

25. Blood Bank-Integrating clinical governance

- A. Clinicians use the safety and quality systems from the Clinical Governance Standard when:
- Implementing policies and procedures for blood management
 - Managing risks associated with blood management
 - Identifying training requirements for blood management

26. Applying quality improvement systems

- A. The health service organisation applies the quality improvement system from the Clinical Governance Standard when:
- Monitoring the performance of the blood management system
 - Implementing strategies to improve blood management and associated processes
 - Reporting on the outcomes of blood management

27. There is access to emergency blood and blood products in accordance with hospital policy.

- A. Emergency blood is available at all times.
- B. There is a designated refrigerator for emergency blood and blood products.
- C. The temperature of the refrigerator is monitored and recorded according to hospital policy.
- D. Appropriate action is taken and recorded when the temperature of the refrigerator is outside the recommended range.
- E. Banked emergency blood is subject to stock control, which includes the replacement of stock before its expiry date.

28. Reporting adverse events

- A. The health service organisation uses processes for reporting transfusion-related adverse events, in accordance with national guidelines and criteria
- B. The health service organisation participates in haemovigilance activities, in accordance with the national framework

29. Integrating clinical governance

- A. Clinicians use the safety and quality systems from the Clinical Governance Standard when:**
- Implementing policies and procedures for blood management
 - Managing risks associated with blood management
 - Identifying training requirements for blood management

CHAPTER-11
RADIOLOGY (RD)

- 1. A radiology and diagnostic imaging service is provided by the hospital, or is readily available through arrangements with outside sources, to meet the needs of its catchment population.**
 - A. An adequate, convenient and regular radiology and diagnostic imaging service is available to meet patient needs.
 - B. Where radiology and diagnostic imaging services are outsourced, the hospital has a valid service level agreement with an accredited radiology service.
 - C. The selection of an outside source is based on an acceptable record of accurate, timely service and compliance with applicable laws and regulations.
 - D. An emergency radiology and diagnostic imaging service is available after hours.

- 2. The radiology and diagnostic imaging service meets applicable local and national standards and legislation.**
 - A. Documented policies and procedures that address compliance with applicable standards, laws and regulations are implemented.
 - B. A copy of the local rules relating to current Ionising Radiation regulations is available.
 - C. A copy of the most recent radiation safety report is held.
 - D. The hospital satisfies the statutory requirements under Ionising Radiation regulations.
 - E. A radiation protection supervisor is identified and available to assist a radiation protection adviser in complying with the Ionising Radiation regulations.
 - F. A patient register is held in the radiology and diagnostic imaging department.

- 3. Imaging services are provided as per the scope of services of the organisation.**
 - A. Imaging services comply with legal and other requirements.
 - B. Scope of the imaging services is commensurate to the services provided by the organisation.
 - C. The infrastructure (physical and equipment) and manpower is adequate to provide for its defined scope of services.
 - D. Adequately qualified and trained personnel perform, supervise and interpret the investigations.
 - E. Documented policies and procedures exist to ensure correct identification and safe and timely transportation of patients to and from the imaging services.

- F. Imaging results are available within a defined timeframe.
 - G. Critical results are intimated immediately to the personnel concerned.
 - H. Results are reported in a standardised manner.
 - I. There is a mechanism to address recall / amendment of reports whenever applicable.
 - J. Imaging tests not available in the organisation are outsourced to organisation(s) based on their quality assurance system.
- 4. A qualified individual is responsible for managing the radiology and diagnostic imaging service.**
- A. A radiologist or radiographer, who is qualified by education, training and experience, manages the radiology and diagnostic imaging service.
 - B. The responsibilities of this person include developing, implementing and maintaining relevant policies and procedures.
 - C. The responsibilities of this person include administrative control.
 - D. The responsibilities of this person include maintaining quality control programmes.
 - E. The responsibilities of this person include recommending outside sources of radiology and diagnostic imaging services.
 - F. The responsibilities of this person include monitoring and reviewing all radiology and diagnostic imaging services.
- 5. Individuals with adequate training, skills and experience perform diagnostic imaging procedures and interpret the results.**
- A. Those individuals who may perform diagnostic imaging procedures and those who may interpret and report the results are identified.
 - B. A system is in place to ensure that procedures are performed only by radiographers, radiologists, or specially trained doctors and other persons, authorised to do so by a radiation protection advisor.
 - C. Diagnostic imaging is done only upon a signed request from a qualified medical practitioner.
 - D. Diagnostic images are interpreted and reported on by appropriately trained and experienced personnel.
 - E. There is an adequate number of personnel to meet patient needs.
 - F. Experts in specialised diagnostic areas are contacted, when needed.
 - G. A roster of experts for specialised diagnostic areas is maintained.
- 6. Measures to protect patients and personnel from unnecessary exposure are applied.**
- A. Warning signs are placed at the entrances to X-ray rooms.
 - B. Notices encouraging women to inform the radiographer of pregnancy are prominently displayed.
 - C. Dosimeter badges are worn and handled according to Ionising Radiation regulations.

- D. Documented systems are in place to ensure that pregnant radiographers/technicians are provided with additional radiation monitoring devices and are restricted to work in low risk areas.
 - E. Protective clothing and appliances for personnel and patients are available and in good order.
 - F. A documented system is in place to ensure that doors are closed during radiographic examinations.
 - G. Beam restricting devices are used.
 - H. Each X-ray room is provided with an exposure chart.
 - I. Each X-ray machine is provided with a log-book, which includes quality control information on the device.
- 7. Essential resuscitation equipment and medications are available.**
- A. There is a mechanism for the summoning of medical help in an emergency.
 - B. Resuscitation equipment is available in accordance with hospital policy.
 - C. Resuscitation equipment and drugs are checked daily or immediately after use, whichever is the sooner, by persons identified to be responsible for this.
- 8. Reporting and recording policies and procedures within the radiology and diagnostic imaging service ensure safety and legality.**
- A. Diagnostic imaging request forms contain the patient's name, examination requested, relevant previous examinations and clinical information to explain the request.
 - B. The request form includes information regarding previous investigations.
 - C. The hospital has established the expected report time for results.
 - D. Radiology and diagnostic imaging results are reported on within a time frame to meet patient needs.
 - E. There is a method of checking the reports against the clinical records.
 - F. Reports contain a clear conclusion and recommendations for future treatment where appropriate.
 - G. A copy of the report is filed in the patient's record.
 - H. Images are available at each visit of the patient.
 - I. A policy that defines the duration and method of storage of images is implemented.
 - J. Where digital imaging is used, appropriate back-up services are available.
- 9. X-ray film and other supplies are regularly available.**
- A. Essential quantities of film, reagents and supplies are available.
 - B. All film and reagents are stored and disposed of according to guidelines.
 - C. All reagents and solutions are completely and accurately labelled.

10. Quality control procedures are implemented and documented.

- A. There is a quality control process for the radiology and diagnostic imaging service which is implemented.
- B. Quality control includes daily surveillance of imaging results.
- C. Quality control includes rapid correction when a deficiency is identified.
- D. Quality control includes equipment
- E. Quality control includes documenting results and corrective actions.

11. There is an established quality assurance programme for imaging services.

- A. The quality assurance programme for imaging services is documented.
- B. The programme addresses periodic internal / external peer review of imaging protocols and results using appropriate sampling.
- C. The programme addresses surveillance of imaging results in collaboration with referring clinicians for follow up wherever applicable
- D. A system is in place to ensure the appropriateness of the investigations and procedures for the clinical indication.
- E. The programme includes periodic calibration and maintenance of all equipment.
- F. The programme includes the documentation of corrective and preventive actions.

12. There is an established safety programme in the imaging services.

- A. The radiation-safety programme is documented.
- B. This programme is aligned with the organisation's safety programme.
- C. Patients are appropriately screened for safety / risk prior to undergoing an imaging on a particular modality.
- D. Handling, usage and disposal of radio-active and hazardous materials are as per statutory requirements.
- E. Imaging personnel and patients are provided with appropriate radiation safety and monitoring devices where applicable.
- F. Radiation-safety and monitoring devices are periodically tested and results are documented.
- G. Imaging and ancillary personnel are trained in imaging safety practices and radiation-safety measures.
- H. Imaging signage are prominently displayed in all appropriate locations.

13. Requisition of paraclinical examinations and handling of samples take place in a correct and safe manner.

- A. There are guidelines from each paraclinical department for ordering examination.
- B. There are guidelines from each paraclinical department for sampling for examination.

- C. There are guidelines from each paraclinical department for handling diagnostic material after sampling.
- D. Paraclinical examinations are ordered in accordance with the standard.
- E. Samples for paraclinical examinations are extracted in accordance with the standard.
- F. Diagnostic material is handled in accordance with the standard.

14. Diagnostic examinations with equipment and/or staff attached to nondiagnostic departments are subject to the same quality control as examinations performed at diagnostic departments.

- A. There are guidelines for quality control of diagnostic examinations which are performed outside diagnostic department.
- B. Staff performing diagnostic examinations outside diagnostic departments obtain and maintain the right competences.
- C. The responsibility for quality control, calibration and correct use of equipment is clearly assigned and known by relevant staff.
- D. The responsibility for interpretation and documentation of the results of the examinations is clearly assigned and known by relevant staff.
- E. The hospital has targets for the quality of the examinations performed outside diagnostic department and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.
- F. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the examinations performed outside diagnostic department. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.

15. Early follow-up on test results and results of examinations are performed.

- A. There are guidelines for giving test results and results of examinations.
- B. There are guidelines for receiving test results and results of examinations.
- C. Test results and results of examinations are in accordance with the standard.
- D. Acknowledge the receipt of test results and results of examinations.
- E. On reception of test results and results of examination, which require acute efforts, the reaction is early.
- F. For each patient it has been registered which tests and examinations have been requested and which results have been received.
- G. The hospital has targets for the quality of early reaction to test results. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets. The quality monitoring includes deadlines for responses. Data are analysed and assessed.

H. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of early reaction to test results. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.

16. Diagnostic imaging services are available to meet patient needs (ER)

- A.** Adequate and convenient diagnostic imaging services are available at all times.
- B.** Established waiting times for diagnostic imaging studies to be done according to triage status are monitored.
- C.** Established waiting times for diagnostic images to be available are monitored.
- D.** Where X-rays are initially interpreted by emergency unit medical personnel, there is a system for review by appropriately qualified diagnostic imaging personnel, when required.

CHAPTER-12
GOVERNANCE AND LEADERSHIP DIRECTIONS (GLD)

- 1. Governance of the Hospital/ Organization**
 - A. Governance structure is described in written documents and is known to the personnel of the hospital.
 - B. Organisational chart lines of authority and accountability between the governance structure and the hospital, as well as within the hospital.

- 2. The responsibilities of those responsible for governance are defined.**
 - A. Governance approves and lay down the organisation's vision, mission, values and make public the hospital's mission statement.
 - B. Governance approve the strategic and operational plans and organisation's annual budget and allocate resources required to meet the hospital's mission.
 - C. Governance monitor and measure the performance of the organisation against the stated mission
 - D. Governance approves Organization Structure
 - E. Governance appoint the senior leaders in the organization
 - F. Governance support safety initiatives and quality improvement plan
 - G. Governance support research activities.
 - H. Governance address the organisation's social responsibility.
 - I. Governance inform the public of the quality and performance of services.
 - J. Governance provides leadership support to develop a culture of safety
 - K. Governance provides leadership support to ensure partnering with patients, carers and consumers
 - L. Sets priorities and strategic directions for safe and high-quality clinical care, and ensures that these are communicated effectively to the workforce and the community
 - M. Endorses the organisation's clinical governance framework and support clinicians to perform their delegated safety, quality roles, responsibilities and to operate within the clinical governance framework to improve the safety and quality of health care for patients
 - N. Ensures that roles and responsibilities are clearly defined for the governing body, management, clinicians and the workforce
 - O. Monitors the action taken as a result of analyses of clinical incidents
 - P. Reviews reports and monitors the organisation's progress on safety and quality performance
 - Q. The governing body ensures that the organisation's safety and quality priorities address the specific health needs of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people
 - R. Governance collaborate with the hospital's managers.
 - S. Governance approves receive and act upon reports of the quality programme, at least quarterly.

- T. Governance approves receive and act upon reports on risk management, at least quarterly.
- U. Governance approves evaluate the performance of the hospital's senior manager, at least annually.
- V. Communication and cooperation between the hospital's governance structure, management and the catchment population is established.
- W. Effectiveness and performance of the governance structure is evaluated, at least annually.

3. Community involvement

- A. The hospital has a policy for involvement of citizens.
- B. The citizens are involved in accordance with the hospital's policy.
- C. The hospital's leaders meet with the leaders of other relevant provider organisations in their community to develop and revise strategic and operational plans to meet the needs of the catchment population.

4. Mission, Vision and Values

- A. The business mission is regular updated, at least every fourth year.
- B. The management plans and supports the implementation of the business mission. The implementation involves all levels of management.
- C. The hospital has a business mission defining mission, vision, values and overall strategies.
- D. The business mission is available for the hospital's managers, staff and the public.
- E. The business mission is regular updated, however, at least every fourth year.
- F. The management plans and supports the implementation of the business mission. The implementation involves all levels of management.

5. Strategic Plan

- A. The leaders work collaboratively to develop and implement the strategic plan of the hospital.
- B. Progress in implementing the plan is monitored at regular intervals according to hospital policy.

6. Planning, operations and economy

- A. Goals have been decided for activity, quality and economy on a short term and long term basis for the hospital as a whole and for the individual departments at the hospital. The goals reflect the hospital's overall strategies.
- B. There is a management information system ensuring managements at all levels updated and valid information in order to follow up on the goals for activity, quality and economy.

- C. The hospital has a strategy to improve effective resource utilisation and reduction of waste.
- D. The hospital has a policy which supports research and innovation, adjusted to the hospital's size and tasks. The policy includes use of research and active participation by the hospital itself in research and innovation.
- E. The hospital has formalised feed-back systems so stakeholders and staff can comment on the hospital's current goals, requirements and results and suggest proposals for development and improvement.
- F. Managements at hospital and department level plan the operation in accordance with the goals decided for activity, quality and economy, effective resource utilisation and research and innovation.
- G. Managements at all levels receive regular overviews of activity, quality and economy.
- H. The hospital and the individual departments use feedback received via formalised feed-back systems.
- I. It is documented that managements at all levels are evaluated in relation to fulfilling activity-, quality- and economy targets.
- J. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the compliance of the goals for activity, quality and economy. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the goals for activity, quality and economy.

7. Organisational leadership

- A. The health service organisation establishes and maintains a clinical governance framework, and uses the processes within the framework to drive improvements in safety and quality
- B. The health service organisation implements and monitors strategies to meet the organisation's safety and quality priorities for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people
- C. The health service organisation considers the safety and quality of health care for patients in its business decision-making

8. Senior Leader, Manager and Clinical Leaders Complies with the laid-down and applicable legislations, regulations and notifications.

- A. The management is conversant with the applicable laws and regulations and undertakes the responsibility to adhere to the same.
- B. The management ensures that the policies and procedures pertaining to patient care are in compliance with the prevailing laws, regulations and notifications.
- C. The management has a mechanism which ensures implementation of these requirements.

- D. Management has a mechanism which regularly updates any amendments in the prevailing laws of the land.
- E. There is a mechanism to regularly update licenses/ registrations/ certifications.
- F. The senior manager has the education and experience to match the requirements in the job description.
- G. The senior manager manages the day-to-day operation of the hospital, including those responsibilities described in the position description.
- H. The senior manager carries out approved policies for management functions.
- I. The senior manager monitors compliance with applicable laws and regulations.
- J. The senior manager responds to any reports from inspecting and regulatory agencies.
- K. The senior manager implements processes to manage and control human, financial and other resources.
- L. The hospital is licensed in terms of relevant legislation for the level of service provided.
- M. The senior manager ensures that the required physical facilities, installations and equipment are available and are used optimally to provide the specified services.
- N. There is a documented procedure to guide the delegation of authorities within the hospital.
- O. The senior manager ensures the implementation of risk management processes and activities.
- P. The senior manager implements processes to monitor patient expectations and satisfaction.
- Q. The senior manager implements processes for quality management and improvement.
- R. The senior manager implements processes to monitor the quality of clinical and other services.
- S. The leaders of the hospital are formally identified.

9. Clinical Leadership Support Clinicians

- A. Understand and perform their delegated safety and quality roles and responsibilities
- B. Operate within the clinical governance framework to improve the safety and quality of health care for patients
- C. Care planning and delivery is integrated and coordinated among care settings, departments and services.

10. Management of departments and services

- A. The hospital ensures that a qualified and/or experienced individual manages each department or service in the hospital.

- B. The responsibilities of each departmental manager are defined in writing.
- C. The departmental or service manager implements processes to manage and control human, financial and other resources.
- D. The departmental or service manager ensures that there are sufficient personnel to provide the services.
- E. The departmental or service manager ensures that resources are available to provide those services.
- F. Departmental or service managers provide orientation and training for all personnel of the department or service, appropriate to their responsibilities.
- G. There is coordination and integration of services with other departments and services.
- H. Departmental managers implement quality control and improvement systems.

11. Organization and Department Scope of services document and access to information

- A. Scope of services of each department is defined.
- B. Administrative policies and procedures for each department are maintained.
- C. Each organisational programme, service, site or department has effective leadership.
- D. Departmental leaders are involved in quality improvement.
- E. The leaders of the hospital identify the desired or expected services for their catchment population.
- F. The hospital has identified its catchment population.
- G. The hospital has implemented a communication strategy with its catchment population.
- H. The services provided by the hospital are made known to the catchment population
- I. The hospital provides information on the quality of its services.
- J. Information on services, hours of operation and processes to obtain care are available to agencies and referral sources in the community and to the catchment population.
- K. Patients are received into the hospital only if the hospital has the ability to provide the necessary services and settings for care.
- L. Access to services not offered by the hospital is facilitated by providing patients with information on how to access these services.

12. Organizational Ethics and legal norms

- A. The leaders make public the vision, mission and values of the organisation.
- B. The leaders establish the organisation's ethical management.
- C. The organisation discloses its ownership.

- D. The organisation honestly portrays the services which it can and cannot provide.
- E. The organisation honestly portrays its affiliations and accreditations.
- F. The organisation accurately bills for its services based upon a standard billing tariff.
- G. The hospital's leaders establish ethical and legal norms that protect patients and their rights.
- H. The hospital's leaders establish processes to receive and resolve ethical dilemmas within a specified time frame according to hospital policy.
- I. The hospital's leaders establish organisational values to guide personnel in the manner in which they should behave when performing their functions.
- J. The hospital discloses its ownership.
- K. The hospital honestly portrays its services to patients.
- L. The hospital provides clear admission, treatment, transfer and discharge policies.
- M. The hospital bills accurately for services rendered.
- N. The hospital has a mechanism to control all research undertaken within the hospital.
- O. Policies and procedures that guide the activities of those responsible for oversight of research in the hospital reflect international best practice and are implemented.
- P. Policies and procedures that guide personnel in gaining informed consent for research studies are developed and implemented.
- Q. The authority responsible for control of research activities ensures that adequate indemnity insurance is available to compensate patients who experience an adverse event caused by participation in research studies conducted at the hospital.

13. The organisation displays professionalism in management of affairs.

- A. The person heading the organisation has requisite and appropriate administrative qualifications.
- B. The person heading the organisation has requisite and appropriate administrative experience.
- C. The organisation prepares the strategic and operational plans including long-term and short-term goals commensurate to the organisation's vision, mission and values in consultation with the various stakeholders.
- D. The organisation coordinates the functioning with departments and external agencies, and monitors the progress in achieving the defined goals and objectives.
- E. The organisation plans and budgets for its activities annually.
- F. The performance of the senior leaders is reviewed for their effectiveness.
- G. The functioning of committees is reviewed for their effectiveness.
- H. The organisation documents employee rights and responsibilities.

- I. The organisation documents the service standards.
- J. The organisation has a formal documented agreement for all outsourced services.
- K. The organisation monitors the quality of the outsourced services.

14. Management Principle

- A. There is a management principle for the hospital.
- B. Managers at all levels are familiar with the management principle and work accordingly.

15. Clinical performance and effectiveness-Evidence-based care

- A. The health service organisation has processes that:
 - Provide clinicians with ready access to best-practice guidelines, integrated care pathways, clinical pathways and decision support tools relevant to their clinical practice
 - Support clinicians to use the best available evidence, including relevant clinical care standards.

16. Clinical performance and effectiveness-clinical practice guidelines

- A. The health service organisation has systems to:
 - Monitor variation in practice against expected health outcomes
 - Provide feedback to clinicians on variation in practice and health outcomes
 - Review performance against external measures
 - Support clinicians to take part in clinical review of their practice
 - Use information on unwarranted clinical variation to inform improvements in safety and quality systems
 - Record the risks identified from unwarranted clinical variation in the risk management system
- B. Clinical practice guidelines relevant to the patients and services of the hospital are implemented to guide uniform patient care processes.

17. Contracts/ agreements

- A. Copies of contracts are made available to those who ensure their implementation.
- B. Services provided under contracts/agreements meet patient needs.
- C. Contracts and other arrangements are monitored as part of the hospital's quality management and improvement programme.
- D. There is a mechanism to ensure that all volunteers work under the guidance of suitably qualified personnel in the employ of the hospital.
- E. Volunteers sign a memorandum of agreement to abide by the conditions of the hospital.

- F. There are documented policies and procedures for the activities of the volunteer service which are implemented.
- G. Contract workers, volunteers and independent clinical practitioners are orientated to the hospital, their job responsibilities and their specific assignments.
- H. There is a system to ensure that independent clinical practitioners and volunteers undergo an evaluation of their performance each year or more frequently, as defined by hospital or organisational policy.
- I. The hospital has a process to ensure that independent clinical practitioners and volunteers providing clinical care have valid credentials.

18. Communication and Committee Meetings

- A. The hospital's leaders promote communication between departments, services and individual personnel members.
- B. Agendas are prepared for meetings and personnel are given timely notification in order to prepare for participation.
- C. Minutes of meetings are prepared and circulated to all relevant personnel.
- D. There is a mechanism to ensure that key issues arising from meetings of the governance structure and/or the management of the hospital are communicated to and acted upon by personnel.

19. Integrating clinical governance

- A. Clinicians use the safety and quality systems from the Clinical Governance Standard when:
 - Implementing policies and procedures to support effective clinical communication
 - Managing risks associated with clinical communication
 - Identifying training requirements for effective and coordinated clinical communication

20. Budgeting, reporting and auditing processes are consistent with statutory requirements and accepted standards.

- A. A designated financial manager is responsible for the implementation and maintenance of the financial strategy.
- B. The financial manager ensures that policies and procedures and/or directives, which include the standard as a minimum, are available to guide personnel and that they are implemented.
- C. There is a mechanism for allowing personnel to participate in the development and management of budgets.
- D. A monthly report is produced for the senior management team, setting out the financial position to date.
- E. There is a mechanism for establishing the reason for budget variation in either income or expenditure.

- F. Annual financial statements are produced at the end of each financial year.
- G. Internal and external audit reports and responses thereto are available.
- H. There is a capital asset register, which is routinely maintained.
- I. There is a capital asset replacement programme.
- J. When the acquisition of new assets is agreed, required asset specifications are defined in collaboration with users and those responsible for medical equipment maintenance.
- K. There is a mechanism to ensure that the level of debtors is kept to a minimum.

21. There is a system to ensure that equipment and supplies are ordered, available, stored and distributed from a designated point.

- A. A designated individual is responsible for the ordering, storage, distribution and control of equipment and supplies used in the hospital.
- B. The supply chain manager ensures that policies and procedures and/or directives, including the standard as a minimum, are available to guide personnel and that they are implemented.
- C. All losses are reported, recorded and investigated and appropriate action taken to prevent recurrence.
- D. There is an inventory of all goods stored.

22. All equipment and supplies are safely stored

- A. Secure storage facilities with controlled access are available.
- B. Separate designated storage areas for receiving and unpacking incoming goods are provided.
- C. A record is kept of goods received and goods issued.
- D. Records are audited.
- E. There is adequate space to allow for orderly storage of goods which enables the safe retrieval of equipment and supplies.
- F. Hazardous and flammable materials are stored in accordance with relevant regulations.
- G. Goods are stored in accordance with the temperature requirements specified by the manufacturer.
- H. Walk-in refrigerators and cool rooms can be opened from the inside using a safety release mechanism.

CHAPTER-13
FACILITY MANAGEMENT AND SAFETY (FMS)

- 1. The Facility Maintenance Service is managed to ensure the provision of a safe and effective service.**
 - A. A designated individual is responsible for supervising the maintenance of buildings, plant and installations.
 - B. The responsibilities of the manager are documented.
 - C. The maintenance manager identifies the requirements of the hospital's maintenance programme, which informs the budgeting process.
 - D. Laws, regulations and other requirements applicable to the hospital's facilities are available to personnel.
 - E. Policies and procedures guide personnel in the implementation of country-specific legislation.
 - F. The manager works with the multidisciplinary team to develop and implement risk management systems according to hospital policy.

- 2. Service facilities and equipment**
 - A. There is a dedicated work area for maintenance activities.
 - B. Basic maintenance equipment, tools and spare parts are available.
 - C. There is a separate area for personnel with adequate, secure storage facilities for outdoor clothing and personal possessions.
 - D. There are adequate, suitable and conveniently placed change rooms, toilets and ablution facilities for personnel.

- 3. There is an adequate number of suitably qualified and/ or experienced personnel to provide a safe and effective service.**
 - A. There are sufficient suitably trained and/or experienced personnel to manage the hospital's buildings, plant and machinery.
 - B. Where there are no in-house personnel to perform these functions, the services of consultants/service providers are utilised.
 - C. Contact details for specialist service contractors for buildings, plant and machinery are available, which include the name of the organisation, their location, telephone numbers, responsible persons and specified nominated contact person(s).
 - D. There is a system for the provision of emergency technical backup.

- 4. The organisation has a system in place to provide a safe and secure environment.**
 - A. Safety committee coordinates development, implementation and monitoring of the safety plan and policies.
 - B. Patient-safety devices & infrastructure are installed across the organisation and inspected periodically.
 - C. The organisation is a non-smoking area.

- D. There is a procedure which addresses the identification and disposal of material(s) not in use in the organisation.
 - E. Facility inspection rounds to ensure safety are conducted at least twice in a year in patient-care areas and at least once in a year in non-patient-care areas.
 - F. Inspection reports are documented and corrective and preventive measures are undertaken.
 - G. There is a safety education programme for staff.
- 5. The organisation's environment and facilities operate in a planned manner to ensure safety of patients, their families, staff and visitors and promotes environment friendly measures.**
- A. Facilities are appropriate to the scope of services of the organisation.
 - B. Up-to-date drawings are maintained which detail the site layout, floor plans and fire-escape routes.
 - C. There is internal and external sign postings in the organisation in a language understood by the patient, families and community.
 - D. The provision of space shall be in accordance with the available literature on good practices (National or international standards) and directives from government agencies.
 - E. Operational planning describes access to different areas in the hospital by staff, patients, visitors and vendors.
 - F. Potable water and electricity are available round the clock.
 - G. Alternate sources for electricity and water are provided as backup for any failure/shortage.
 - H. The organisation regularly tests these alternate sources.
 - I. There are designated individuals (with appropriate equipment) responsible for the maintenance of all the facilities.
 - J. Maintenance staff is contactable round the clock for emergency repairs.
 - K. There is a maintenance plan for facility and furniture.
 - L. Response times are monitored from reporting to inspection and implementation of corrective actions.
 - M. The organisation takes initiatives towards an energy efficient and environmental friendly hospital.
- 6. The hospital's buildings and surrounding areas are accessible and safe to walk in.**
- A. There are on-going plans for ensuring buildings' and surrounding areas' safety and accessibility.
 - B. The hospital has planned measures to ensure the accessibility in all weather conditions. The effort is based on a risk assessment.
 - C. According to current legislation, the hospital is accessible for persons with impairments.

- D. The hospital has implemented measures to ensure against unauthorised access (theft and assault). The effort is based on a risk assessment.
 - E. The hospital's buildings and surrounding areas are maintained so the buildings and access roads do not pose a danger to people. The effort is based on a risk assessment.
 - F. The hospital has implemented measures to prevent fire. The measures include safe storage of inflammable materials. The effort is based on a risk assessment.
 - G. The hospital has planned measures for firefighting and protection of patients and staff from the consequences of a fire, including safety precaution of escape routes and presence of fire-fighting equipment. The effort is based on a risk assessment.
- 7. The hospital's buildings and facilities support the assignment of tasks, operations and safety for people.**
- A. The hospital has a process to assess whether the buildings and facilities for treatment of patients are suitable for the intended purpose.
 - B. Prior to large reconstructions and new buildings and in connection with significant changes for using the facilities for patient treatment, the suitability of the buildings and facilities is assessed in relation to the intended purpose.
 - C. Prior to large reconstructions and new buildings, a risk assessment of the construction phase, including evaluation of hygiene and fire safety, is made. Based upon this, relevant precautionary measures are initiated.
 - D. There is documentation for assessment of the suitability of the buildings and facilities when used for new purposes. This only applies to facilities for patient treatment.
 - E. If there are lacks in relation to the assessment of the suitability of buildings and facilities when used for new purposes, initiatives have been made to improve the quality. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.
- 8. Functional facilities are available to provide safety and comfort for patients and personnel.**
- A. Sufficient office/administrative space is available for personnel.
 - B. Where required, air-conditioning is installed in laboratories, pharmacies, operating theatres and sterilising departments and is tested and maintained according to hospital policy or manufacturer's guidelines.
 - C. Temperature and ventilation control mechanisms are installed in the kitchen, laundries and other relevant areas and tested and maintained according to hospital policy or manufacturer's guidelines.

- 9. A security system is maintained for the routine monitoring and safeguarding of the premises, patients, personnel, volunteers and visitors.**
- A. Internal security is provided 24 hours per day, seven days per week.
 - B. External security is provided 24 hours per day, seven days per week.
 - C. Policies on the management of weapons are implemented.
 - D. Policies on the management of violence and aggression are implemented.
 - E. Where vulnerable patients are cared for, special safety and security measures are implemented.
 - F. There is a mechanism known to personnel for summoning the assistance of the local security/police/protection service in case of an emergency.
- 10. The organisation has a programme for engineering support services and utility system.**
- A. The organisation plans for equipment in accordance with its services and strategic plan.
 - B. Equipment are selected, rented, updated or upgraded by a collaborative process.
 - C. Equipment are inventoried and proper logs are maintained as required.
 - D. Qualified and trained personnel operate, inspect, test and maintain equipment and utility systems.
 - E. Utility equipment are periodically inspected and calibrated (wherever applicable) for their proper functioning.
 - F. There is a documented operational and maintenance (preventive and breakdown) plan.
 - G. There is a maintenance plan for water management.
 - H. There is a maintenance plan for electrical systems.
 - I. There is a maintenance plan for heating, ventilation and air-conditioning.
 - J. There is a maintenance plan for Information technology & communication network.
 - K. There is a documented procedure for equipment replacement and disposal.
- 11. The hospital has a process to protect hospital occupants in the event of electrical system disruption or failure, which is tested on a regular basis.**
- A. Electrical power is available continuously from regular and emergency sources.
 - B. Emergency electricity supply is available in the areas and services that present the greatest patient safety risk during a power failure.
 - C. Sufficient fuel, e.g. diesel, is available to provide power for 24 hours.
 - D. The hospital ensures that relevant personnel are trained to use/operate emergency electrical supply systems.

12. Water supplies are regularly inspected, tested, maintained and, when appropriate, improved.

- A. Regular and emergency water supplies, including drinkable water, are available continually.
- B. All water supplies are tested and the results are documented on a regular basis.
- C. Should the water supply be contaminated or interrupted, the areas and services at risk have been identified and provision has been made for an alternative water supply.
- D. There is documented evidence that relevant personnel are regularly trained to ensure that all operations to secure safe water are properly performed.

13. The hospital receives utensils of an appropriate amount and quality in relation to the handling of tasks.

- A. There are guidelines for ordering, reception and storage of utensils.
- B. There are guidelines for follow-up on quality flaws when receiving utensils.
- C. The hospital describes precautionary measures for situations where the supply of utensils fails.
- D. Utensils are ordered and requested in accordance with the guidelines in element 1 of the standard.
- E. Follow-up is made for quality flaws on reception of utensils in accordance with the guidelines in element 2 of the standard.
- F. Relevant managers and staff are familiar with the precautionary measures for situations where the supply of utensils fails.

14. The hospital's technical supplies are in accordance with the need.

- A. There are guidelines for operations, maintenance, control and prevention of breakdown of technical supplies. The guidelines are based on a risk assessment.
- B. Managers and staff are familiar with relevant parts of the guidelines and work accordingly.
- C. There are guidelines for documentation of microbiological and toxicological control of tap water.
- D. There is documentation for control of compressed-air plant, oxygen, medical gases and vacuum.
- E. There is documentation for control of ventilation system.
- F. There is documentation for control of emergency supplies of tap water.
- G. There is documentation for test runs of emergency supplies.
- H. If there are lacks in relation to technical supplies, initiatives have been made to improve the quality. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.

15. The hospital implements a documented planned preventative maintenance (PPM) programme for buildings, plant, installations and machinery.

- A. Policies and procedures relating to the maintenance of plant, equipment and installations are implemented.
- B. The service implements planned preventative maintenance according to a schedule.
- C. The department holds regular, documented, current and accurate inspections of the hospital's physical facility, plant and machinery.
- D. Records/log books indicate that emergency generators are regularly tested on full load according to manufacturer's specifications.
- E. Servicing and testing of the uninterruptible power supplies (UPS) and/or battery backup systems is documented.
- F. There is documented evidence that the recommendations of the inspections have been addressed.
- G. A documented procedure for reporting defects in maintenance installations during and after normal working hours is known to departmental and hospital personnel.
- H. Records indicate that upgrading, replacement, de-commissioning and/or disposal of operational plant are undertaken according to hospital policy.
- I. Records indicate that the sewerage management system is maintained according to hospital policy.

16. The organisation has plans for fire and non-fire emergencies within the facilities.

- A. The organisation has plans and provisions for early detection, abatement and containment of fire, and non-fire emergencies.
- B. The organisation has a documented safe-exit plan in case of fire and non-fire emergencies.
- C. Staff is trained for its role in case of such emergencies.
- D. Mock drills are held at least twice a year.

17. Structured systems to ensure fire safety are implemented.

- A. Structured systems and processes to ensure that all occupants of the hospital facilities are safe from fire or smoke are implemented.
- B. Documented evidence is available from the relevant authority to confirm that the hospital complies with applicable laws and regulations in relation to fire safety.
- C. Fire-fighting equipment is inspected and serviced at least annually with the date of service recorded on the apparatus.
- D. Flammable materials are clearly labelled and safely stored.
- E. Easily recognised and understood signs prohibiting smoking are displayed in areas where flammable materials and combustible gases are stored.

- F. A floor plan is displayed, which shows the location of firefighting equipment, evacuation routes and emergency exits.
- G. Annual personnel training in fire prevention and evacuation procedures is documented.
- H. The hospital has implemented a policy regarding smoking, which applies to patients, families, visitors, personnel and volunteers.
- I. There is a maintenance plan for fire-related equipment & infrastructure

18. The organisation has a programme for bio-medical equipment management.

- A. The organisation plans for equipment in accordance with its services and strategic plan.
- B. Equipment are selected, rented, updated or upgraded by a collaborative process.
- C. Equipment are inventoried and proper logs are maintained as required.
- D. Qualified and trained personnel operate and maintain the medical equipment.
- E. Equipment are periodically inspected and calibrated for their proper functioning.
- F. There is a documented operational and maintenance (preventive and breakdown) plan for equipment.
- G. There is a documented procedure for equipment replacement and disposal.
- H. The procedure addresses medical equipment recalls.
- I. Response times are monitored from reporting to inspection and implementation of corrective actions.

19. Adequate human resources are available for the Medical Equipment Management Service (MEMS) to ensure safety and the correct management, usage and operation of medical equipment.

- A. A medical equipment maintenance manager is designated by the hospital.
- B. The responsibilities of the medical equipment maintenance manager are defined in writing.
- C. Policies and procedures developed in accordance with country-specific legislation guide personnel in the acquisition, allocation and utilisation of equipment and technical support for MEMS.
- D. A multidisciplinary advisory committee is appointed to represent managers, clinical and technical personnel involved in the management and use of medical equipment.
- E. Members of the committee are appointed in writing, based on their competence in the area of healthcare technology management.
- F. The responsibilities of the committee are documented.
- G. The committee meets regularly to discuss and advise on issues relating to healthcare technology management and these meetings are minuted.

- H. The committee has ready access to a reliable source of expertise relating to healthcare technology.

20. Medical equipment is managed and maintained throughout the hospital.

- A. An audit of medical equipment is conducted.
- B. There is a comprehensive inventory of all medical equipment.
- C. Operator and/or service manuals are available to operators and technicians at all times.
- D. Operator and/or service manuals for donated equipment are available in local languages.
- E. Initial commissioning records are available for all high risk medical equipment, which include details of tests performed and training given.
- F. The hospital develops and implements a planned preventative inspection and maintenance system according to the service requirements specified by the manufacturers.
- G. The manager identifies the requirements of the hospital's medical equipment maintenance programme, which informs the budgeting process.
- H. There is a service history for each piece of equipment, which includes signed and dated job-cards detailing all time and expenses associated with maintaining the device, e.g. procedures carried out, time taken to complete the procedure, parts fitted, etc.
- I. Patient care unit managers have access to information on service and repairs of equipment.
- J. A documented system which addresses the provision of basic technical support in first line emergency situations is in place and known to all relevant persons.
- K. Advanced technical support is provided in emergency situations.
- L. Names of specialist service contractors are available with their locations, telephone numbers and the responsible persons specified.
- M. Where there are in-house clinical engineering personnel the department has access to all specialised test equipment and consumables (as specified by the manufacturer of the medical equipment) for the equipment they are expected to maintain.
- N. Where there are in-house clinical engineering personnel, the tools and test equipment required to offer the service are appropriately maintained.
- O. Where there are in-house clinical engineering personnel, they are provided with access to appropriate support documentation, such as equipment standards and other regulatory documentation.
- P. Checklists are available for the inspection and maintenance of each type of device in use in the hospital.
- Q. Where there are in-house clinical engineering personnel, the service develops and implements a system to obtain information on medical

device hazard alerts or safety bulletins and responds to the information appropriately.

21. There are systems in place to ensure that all users of medical equipment and devices are competent in the use thereof.

- A. Training is provided for all users of basic medical equipment, with a record of all such training given and successfully completed.
- B. Training is provided for all users of complex and/or critical life-support equipment, with a record of all such training given and successfully completed.
- C. Training in basic electrical safety is provided to all personnel involved in the use of electrically operated equipment.
- D. Where clinical engineering personnel are employed, they are provided with appropriate training in respect of all medical equipment, devices and instruments, which they are expected to maintain and/or repair.
- E. Where clinical engineering personnel are employed, they are encouraged and assisted by management to attend seminars, congresses, conferences and training sessions, to improve their knowledge of and proficiency in medical technology matters.

22. Where clinical engineering personnel are employed, systems are in place to ensure safe working conditions and the safety of equipment in clinical engineering workshops.

- A. Clinical engineering personnel implement risk management processes in accordance with the hospital risk management systems.
- B. There is an adequate scavenging system for the removal of nitrous oxide and volatile anaesthetic agents in the medical equipment workshop.
- C. Where anaesthetic vaporisers are tested and serviced in the workshop, a suitable fume extraction chamber is provided.
- D. Where extensive soldering work is undertaken, soldering stations are provided with a suitable fume extraction system.
- E. Where volatile cleaning agents are used, an appropriate fume extraction chamber is provided for the safe dispersal of hazardous vapours, e.g. ether.
- F. The medical equipment workshop has adequate 15 amp surge-protected electrical power outlets.
- G. The medical equipment workshop is fitted with air-conditioning capable of maintaining a year-round constant temperature of 21 degrees Celsius.

23. Any acquisition, testing and implementation of equipment for clinical use are made in accordance with current rules.

- A. There are guidelines for acquisition, testing and implementation of equipment for clinical use taking the administrative, clinical and medico-technical conditions into consideration.

24. The staff is trained to handle equipment for clinical use.

- A. There are guidelines for systematic training in handling of equipment for clinical use.
- B. There are easily accessible instructions and manuals for relevant equipment for clinical use in the departments.
- C. Relevant staff is trained in handling equipment for clinical use.
- D. It is documented that relevant staff has completed training in handling high-risk equipment.
- E. If there are any lacks in completing the training of handling high-risk equipment, the hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the participation. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.

25. Equipment for clinical use is controlled, maintained, repaired and phased-out in accordance with stipulated plans.

- A. There are guidelines for preventive maintenance and control of equipment for clinical use.
- B. There are guidelines for handling of faulty equipment for clinical use.
- C. Training of relevant clinical and technical staff in preventive maintenance, repair and control of equipment has been completed.
- D. Equipment for clinical use is controlled and maintained in accordance with the hospital's guidelines.
- E. There is an updated registration of all equipment for clinical use and documentation of: preventive maintenance and control within determined time frames, repairs carried out, expected service life of equipment, any software changes
- F. If any lacks are shown in relation to preventive maintenance and control, initiatives have been made to improve the quality. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.

26. The organisation has a programme for medical gases, vacuum and compressed air.

- A. Documented procedures govern procurement, handling, storage, distribution, usage and replenishment of medical gases.
- B. Medical gases are handled, stored, distributed and used in a safe manner.
- C. The procedures for medical gases address the safety issues at all levels.
- D. Alternate sources for medical gases, vacuum and compressed air are provided for, in case of failure.
- E. The organisation regularly tests these alternate sources.

- F. There is an operational, inspection, testing and maintenance plan for, piped medical gas, compressed air and vacuum installation.

27. Medical gas systems are regularly inspected, maintained and when necessary improved.

- A. Medical gas (oxygen, nitrous oxide and medical air) supplies are available according to the operational requirements of the hospital.
- B. Medical gas supply systems comply with safety standards.
- C. Where there is piped gas, the enclosure, gas bank, pressure regulators, related control/alarm systems and all outlet points are clean and in good operating condition.
- D. Where there is piped gas, the main oxygen supply system is fitted with an alarm, which operates automatically in the event of low pressure in the gas supply system and is regularly tested and documented.
- E. Documented testing of medical gas alarm systems is undertaken regularly according to hospital policy.
- F. Backup supplies of medical gases are available and strategically positioned to ensure timely deployment in emergencies.

28. Medical vacuum systems are regularly inspected and maintained.

- A. Where there is a piped vacuum system, it is externally ventilated and able to provide sufficient suction to all piped vacuum points in the hospital.
- B. In the event of failure of the piped vacuum/suction facilities, backup facilities are provided in relevant services.
- C. Where there are no piped vacuum facilities installed, portable/ mobile vacuum/suction units are available and strategically positioned to ensure timely deployment in emergencies.

29. The organisation has a plan for management of hazardous materials.

- A. Hazardous materials are identified within the organisation.
- B. The organisation implements processes for sorting, labelling, handling, storage, transporting and disposal of hazardous material.
- C. Requisite regulatory requirements are met in respect of radioactive materials.
- D. There is a plan for managing spills of hazardous materials.
- E. Staff are educated and trained for handling such materials.

30. The hospital handles and disposes of waste, chemicals and isotopes in a healthrelated and safe manner.

- A. There are guidelines for handling, storing and disposing waste material, including clinical hazardous waste.
- B. There are guidelines for handling, storing and disposing chemicals and isotopes.

- C. Clinical hazardous waste is handled in accordance with the guidelines in element 1 of the standard.
- D. Chemicals and isotopes are handled in accordance with the guidelines in element 2 of the standard.

31. The hospital has documented control systems for the handling, storage and disposal of healthcare waste.

- A. Waste is managed according to documented systems consistent with legislation, local by-laws and regulations.
- B. Control systems include safe handling of different types of waste.
- C. Control systems include safe storage of different types of waste.
- D. Control systems include safe storage of different types of waste.
- E. Control systems include safe disposal of different types of waste.
- F. Control systems include the procedures to be adopted if spills occur.
- G. Control systems include the use of personal protective equipment when handling waste.
- H. There is a colour-coding system for bags to be used for the segregation of different types of waste.

32. A documented plan to respond to emergencies is developed and rehearsed.

- A. There is a documented plan to deal with internal and external emergencies.
- B. Documented evidence is available that personnel participate in a rehearsal of the plan at least annually.

33. Adequate resources are available for the provision of safe care to patients in the ward and units.

- A. Patient and personnel accommodation and equipment in the service are adequate to meet patient care needs.
- B. Oxygen and vacuum supplies meet patient care requirements.
- C. When patients receive oxygen from a cylinder, the cylinder pressures are monitored according to hospital policy.
- D. There is evidence that equipment is maintained in accordance with hospital policy.
- E. Resuscitation equipment is available in accordance with hospital policy.
- F. There are isolation rooms available which comply with the minimum requirements for isolation.
- G. Electricity and water are available in accordance with the hospital's arrangements.

34. Clinical areas within the emergency unit are adequate to meet the needs of patients.

- A. Facilities allow privacy when providing personal information or undergoing examination or procedures.
- B. Electricity and water are available in accordance with the hospital's arrangements.
- C. There is a waiting area for patients and families.
- D. There is adequate seating in the waiting area.
- E. Wheelchair-accessible toilets are available.
- F. Quiet and private areas are available for waiting relatives and grieving or otherwise distressed relatives or carers.
- G. There is access to a functioning telephone facility for use by the public.
- H. There is a designated triage area.
- I. There is a designated resuscitation area.
- J. There is a mechanism for summoning medical help in an emergency.
- K. There is adequate storage space to enable rapid retrieval and removal of equipment when needed.
- L. There is a low pressure, hand-held shower suitable for the management of patients contaminated with hazardous materials.
- M. There is access to inpatient facilities consistent with the level of emergency care.
- N. There is easy access to the operating theatre.

35. Resuscitation equipment is available in accordance with the policies of the hospital in Emergency Unit.

- A. Resuscitation equipment is available in accordance with hospital policy.
- B. Recommended appliances are available for specialised resuscitations.
- C. Diagnostic and vital sign monitoring equipment is available as per hospital policy.

36. There is a rest area for personnel in close proximity to the clinical areas in Emergency Unit, all other wards, units and OPD.

- A. There is an adequately equipped kitchen, with at least a kettle, toaster and microwave.
- B. There are rest room facilities for personnel including a changing area, toilet and hand washing facilities.
- C. Where personnel undertake 24 hour shifts, there are sleeping and shower facilities.
- D. The rest area is equipped with a telephone or intercom system.

37. Specific resources are available for the provision of safe care to patients in the Obstetric and Maternity unit/ Ward.

- A. Available medical equipment complies with accepted norms for obstetric/maternity care services.

- B. Where resuscitation, intensive care, life support or obstetric/maternity monitoring equipment is used that does not have built-in battery backup units, there is an uninterruptible power supply (UPS) that complies with relevant requirements and is regularly serviced and tested.
- C. Security measures are adequate to safeguard newborns, including identification of newborns and restricted access and exit monitoring in wards.

38. Specific resources are available for the provision of safe care to patients in the Paediatric Ward.

- A. Security measures are adequate to safeguard paediatric patients, including identification of children and restricted access and exit monitoring in wards.
- B. Single rooms are available that are large enough to accommodate parents/guardians who choose to stay with their children.
- C. There are isolation rooms available which comply with the minimum requirements for isolation.
- D. A treatment room for patient assessment and procedures is provided separate from the other patients.
- E. Window guards are fitted and/or opening potential is limited on all windows.
- F. Electrical sockets are placed above child height and/or covered.
- G. Door latches and locks are located above child height.
- H. Floor surfaces are non-slippery and clear of clutter.
- I. Safety gates have small openings to prevent children getting through or being trapped.
- J. Restraining measures such as secure cot sides on cots and beds are used.
- K. Appropriate padding is available for sharp edges on furniture and equipment.
- L. Where play/education area/s are available, age appropriate furniture and equipment are provided.

39. There is a dedicated area for the preparation of Infant Feeds.

- A. Personnel working in the feed preparation area wear protective clothing such as gloves, masks and aprons.
- B. Appropriate hand washing facilities are available in the feed preparation area with appropriate disinfectant solutions.
- C. Appropriate facilities and equipment to clean and disinfect utensils in the feed preparation area are available and functional.
- D. Information about disinfectant solutions and frequency of replacement in the feed preparation area is displayed.
- E. There is clear signage of unauthorised entry on the door to limit people traffic.
- F. The storage cupboard for baby formula is clearly marked and locked.

40. Facilities for safe surgical and anaesthetic care are provided and maintained.

- A. The design of the theatre suite provides space for the reception, induction of anaesthesia, surgery, recovery and observation of patients.
- B. The theatre suite is equipped in accordance with approved requirement lists.
- C. There is direct access to the operating theatres from the receiving, scrubbing-up and recovery areas.
- D. There is safe and adequate storage space for pharmaceutical and surgical supplies.
- E. Access to the theatre suite is controlled.
- F. There is access to sterilisation and disinfection facilities.
- G. There is a system for controlling the environmental temperature and humidity that ensures safe limits for anaesthetised patients in accordance with professional society guidelines.
- H. Where resuscitation, intensive care, life support or critical monitoring equipment without built-in battery backup units is used, there is an uninterruptible power supply (UPS), which is regularly serviced and tested
- I. There is either an UPS or a battery backup system for the theatre lamp, which is regularly tested, with such tests being fully documented.
- J. The theatre has a refrigerator for medication, the temperature of which is measured and recorded daily.
- K. Appropriate action is taken and recorded when the temperature of the refrigerator is outside the recommended range.

41. Recovery Room facilities and equipment are available to provide safe and effective care.

- A. The recovery area forms part of the theatre suite.
- B. There are an adequate number of recovery beds for the patients from the operating theatre.
- C. There is adequate lighting.
- D. The provision, use and maintenance of recovery room equipment comply with the guidelines for practice of the relevant professional society.

42. Clinical areas within the outpatient department are adequate to meet the needs of patients.

- A. There is a mechanism for the summoning of medical help in an emergency.
- B. Diagnostic and vital sign monitoring equipment is available as per hospital policy.
- C. There is adequate storage space to enable rapid retrieval and removal of equipment when needed.
- D. There is access to inpatient facilities consistent with the level of care.

43. Required furniture and equipment are available and functional in Occupational Therapy Department.

- A. Occupational health offices are clearly sign-posted.
- B. There is a mechanism to prevent unauthorised individuals from entering the offices.
- C. There is a reception area for employees.
- D. There is adequate office space for administrative activities.
- E. There is privacy for interviewing employees.
- F. Lockable facilities for storing personal clothing and property are provided.
- G. Ablution facilities are provided.
- H. Transport is available for occupational health personnel to perform their functions.
- I. Facilities and equipment are maintained to provide clean and safe working conditions, which comply with relevant legislation.
- J. Records of equipment maintenance are available.

44. Resources are available to meet the treatment needs of the population served.

- A. Each service has adequate space to treat patients effectively.
- B. There is adequate space for the storage of equipment and materials.
- C. Privacy is ensured through private cubicles, curtains or screens.
- D. There is an emergency call system for summoning of medical assistance.
- E. The audiology service has relevant equipment and materials to provide an effective service.
- F. The clinical psychology service has relevant equipment and materials to provide an effective service.
- G. The occupational therapy service has relevant equipment and materials to provide an effective service.
- H. The physiotherapy service has relevant equipment and materials to provide an effective service.
- I. The social work service has relevant equipment and materials to provide an effective service.
- J. The speech therapy service has relevant equipment and materials to provide an effective service.
- K. The prosthetics and orthotics service has relevant equipment and materials to provide an effective service.
- L. The manager of each department ensures that equipment is included in the hospital's maintenance programme.

45. Safe environment

- A. The health service organisation maximises safety and quality of care: a. Through the design of the environment

- B. The health service organisation:
 - Identifies service areas that have a high risk of unpredictable behaviours and develops strategies to minimise the risks of harm for patients, carers, families, consumers and the workforce
 - Provides access to a calm and quiet environment when it is clinically required
- C. The health service organisation facilitates access to services and facilities by using signage and directions that are clear and fit for purpose
- D. The health service organisation admitting patients overnight has processes that allow flexible visiting arrangements to meet patients' needs, when it is safe to do so
- E. The health service organisation demonstrates a welcoming environment that recognises the importance of the cultural beliefs and practices of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people

46. Where Information Technology equipment is available, it is properly maintained to meet the needs of the services.

- A. A designated individual supervises the management of IT equipment in the organisation.
- B. Technical IT support is provided in the hospital.
- C. Clinical and managerial personnel participate in IT decisions.
- D. Policies and procedures that guide the management of IT equipment are implemented.
- E. All server computers are attached to an uninterrupted power supply (UPS) with surge protection.
- F. Records are kept of the maintenance of IT equipment.
- G. There is a documented procedure known to personnel for reporting defects in IT equipment during and after normal working hours.
- H. Quality management processes are designed and implemented.

47. The use of organisational motor vehicles by personnel is planned and monitored to ensure safety and legality.

- A. A specific manager is identified for the control, use and maintenance of vehicles.
- B. The ability of the transport service to meet the transport needs of the departments/services is evaluated on an annual basis and appropriate action taken when necessary.
- C. There is a system for monitoring the use of vehicles.
- D. There is a system for booking vehicles in advance.
- E. There is a control system for mileage travelled.
- F. There is a vehicle maintenance plan.
- G. There is proof of vehicle maintenance.
- H. There is proof of current licensing of vehicles.
- I. Drivers of vehicles are suitably licensed.

- J. Drivers of vehicles are suitably insured.
- K. Quality management processes are designed and implemented.

48. Structural barriers to access to the hospital are identified and overcome or lessened.

- A. Directional signage to the hospital is clearly visible from all main access roads.
- B. The name of the hospital and the services provided is clearly indicated on the site.
- C. Adequate parking is available for patients and visitors, including designated parking provision for disabled patients.
- D. Ramps and stairs include safety features such as rails where appropriate.
- E. Directional signage within the hospital includes local languages and relevant symbols.
- F. The hospital makes assistive mobility devices, e.g. wheelchairs, available for patients who require such assistance during their visit.
- G. There is access to and within the building for patients using assistive devices, e.g. wheelchairs, walking frames, etc.
- H. Lifts or ramps are available in multi-storey buildings for patients unable to use the stairs.

CHAPTER-14

MANAGEMENT OF INFORMATION (MOI)

- 1. Documented policies and procedures exist to meet the information needs of the care providers, management of the organisation as well as other agencies that require data and information from the organisation.**
 - A. The information needs of the organisation are identified and are appropriate to the scope of the services being provided by the organisation.
 - B. Documented policies and procedures to meet the information needs exist.
 - C. All information management and technology acquisitions are in accordance with the documented policies and procedures.
 - D. Documented policies and procedures guide the use of Telemedicine facility in a safe and secure manner.
 - E. The organisation contributes to external databases in accordance with the law and regulations.
 - F. Information systems are developed and implemented in the hospital.
 - G. The senior management team, in collaboration with all departments, identify key indicators and other information required to monitor quality assurance and improvement processes.
 - H. Clinical and managerial personnel participate in information technology decisions.

- 2. The organisation has processes in place for effective control and management of data.**
 - A. The organisation has an effective process for document control.
 - B. Formats for data collection are standardized.
 - C. Necessary resources are available for analyzing data.
 - D. Documented procedures are laid down for timely and accurate dissemination of data.
 - E. Documented procedures exist for storing and retrieving data.
 - F. Appropriate clinical and managerial staff participates in selecting, integrating and using data.

- 3. The organisation has a complete and accurate medical record for every patient.**
 - A. Every medical record has a unique identifier.
 - B. Organisation policy identifies those authorized to make entries in medical record.
 - C. Entry in the medical record is named, signed, dated and timed.
 - D. The author of the entry can be identified.
 - E. The contents of medical record are identified and documented.

- F. The organisation has a documented policy for usage of abbreviations and develops a list based on accepted practices.
- G. The record provides a complete, up-to-date and chronological account of patient care.
- H. Provision is made for 24-hour availability of the patient's record to healthcare providers to ensure continuity of care.

4. The medical record reflects continuity of care.

- A. The medical record contains information regarding reasons for admission, diagnosis and care plan.
- B. The medical record contains the results of tests carried out and the care provided.
- C. Operative and other procedures performed are incorporated in the medical record.
- D. When patient is transferred to another hospital, the medical record contains the date of transfer, the reason for the transfer and the name of the receiving hospital.
- E. The medical record contains a copy of the discharge summary duly signed by appropriate and qualified personnel.
- F. In case of death, the medical record contains a copy of the cause of death certificate.
- G. Whenever a clinical autopsy is carried out, the medical record contains a copy of the report of the same.
- H. Care providers have access to current and past medical record.

5. Documented policies and procedures are in place for maintaining confidentiality, integrity and security of records, data and information.

- A. A designated individual with appropriate training and experience is responsible for information management systems.
- B. Documented policies and procedures exist for maintaining confidentiality, security and integrity of records, data and information.
- C. Documented policies and procedures are in consonance with the applicable laws.
- D. The policies and procedure(s) incorporate safeguarding of data/record against loss, destruction and tampering.
- E. The organisation has an effective process of monitoring compliance of the laid down policy and procedure.
- F. The organisation uses developments in appropriate technology for improving confidentiality, integrity and security.
- G. Privileged health information is used for the purposes identified or as required by law and not disclosed without the patient's authorisation.
- H. A documented procedure exists on how to respond to patients/ physicians and other public agencies requests for access to information in the medical record in accordance with the local and national law.

- I. Confidentiality of data and information is maintained
 - J. Security and integrity of data and information is maintained
- 6. Documented policies and procedures exist for retention time of records, data and information.**
- A. Documented policies and procedures are in place on retaining the patient's clinical records, data and information.
 - B. The policies and procedures are in consonance with the local and national laws and regulations.
 - C. The destruction of medical records, data and information is in accordance with the laid-down policy.
- 7. The organisation regularly carries out review of medical records.**
- A. The medical records are reviewed periodically.
 - B. The review uses a representative sample based on statistical principles.
 - C. The review is conducted by identified individuals.
 - D. The review focuses on the timeliness, legibility and completeness of the medical records.
 - E. The review process includes records of both active and discharged patients.
 - F. The review points out and documents any deficiencies in records.
 - G. Appropriate corrective and preventive measures are undertaken within a defined period of time and are documented.
- 8. The organisation establishes, implements and maintains procedures for controlling relevant documents and data.**
- A. Documents and information are periodically reviewed and revised as necessary and approved by an authorised person.
 - B. Obsolete documents and information are promptly marked as such and removed from all points of issue and points of use or otherwise assured against unintended use.
 - C. Archival documents and information retained for legal or knowledge preservation purposes or both are suitably identified.
- 9. The hospital minimises the consequences of failure of technical patient-critical supplies plus IT- and communication systems.**
- A. In each department there are guidelines describing tasks and duties in connection with failure of technical patient-critical supplies plus IT and communication systems.
 - B. Managers and staff are familiar with their own duties and responsibilities in case of breakdown of technical patient-critical supplies.
 - C. Managers and staff are familiar with their own duties and responsibilities in case of breakdown of patient critical IT systems.

- D. Managers and staff are familiar with their own duties and responsibilities in case of breakdown of patient critical communication systems.
- E. After events causing major breakdown of technical patient-critical supplies and IT- and communication systems, reports are prepared where the event is analysed.
- F. If the reports show lacks in handling breakdown of technical patient-critical supplies and IT- and communication systems, initiatives have been implemented to improve the quality.

10. Policies and Procedures

- A. The hospital's leaders ensure that policies and procedures guide and support the activities and management of the hospital.
- B. The departmental manager ensures that policies and procedures are implemented in the department.
- C. Policies and procedures guide the retention and destruction of all hospital documentation, including patient-related information, legal, managerial and research documentation.
- D. A designated manager is responsible for compiling and indexing policies and procedures and ensuring their circulation, recall, archiving and review.
- E. Policies and procedures are signed by persons authorised to do so.
- F. Policies and procedures are compiled into a comprehensive manual(s) or filing system (paper-based and/or electronic) which is indexed and easily accessible to all personnel.
- G. All policies and procedures are reviewed at appropriate intervals, dated and signed.
- H. There is a mechanism to ensure that policies are known and implemented.
- I. Outdated policies and procedures are recalled and archived according to hospital policy.

11. Healthcare Records and Data Safety

- A. The health service organisation has healthcare record systems that:
 - Make the healthcare record available to clinicians at the point of care
 - Support the workforce to maintain accurate and complete healthcare records
 - Comply with security and privacy regulations
 - Support systematic audit of clinical information
 - Integrate multiple information systems, where they are used
- B. The health service organisation works towards implementing systems that can provide clinical information that:
 - Are designed to optimise the safety and quality of health care for patients
 - Use national patient and provider identifiers

- Use standard national terminologies
- C. The health service organisation providing clinical information that:
 - Describe access to the system by the workforce, to comply with legislative requirements
 - Maintain the accuracy and completeness of the clinical information the organisation uploads into the system
- D. There are guidelines for data safety. The guidelines are based on a risk assessment.
- E. Managers and staff are familiar with relevant parts of the guidelines and work accordingly.
- F. There is documentation for completed backup of data systems.
- G. It is documented that emergency procedures upon system failure are tested at regular intervals.
- H. If there are lacks in the backup procedures or emergency procedures upon system failure, initiatives have been made to improve the quality. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed, and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.
- I. The hospital maintains a clinical record for each patient.
- J. The patients' clinical records are completed according to guidelines determined by the hospital.

12. There is a system for the management of health records, which meets confidentiality and safety requirements.

- A. A designated individual with appropriate training and/or experience is responsible for the storage, maintenance and retrieval of health records.
- B. The health record manager ensures that policies and procedures, including the standard as a minimum, are available to guide personnel and that they are implemented.
- C. All patient documents, including medical, nursing and other health professional notes, diagnostic test results, referral letters, etc. are filed in the correct record, chronologically and in a standardised manner.
- D. There is a system that allows for the rapid retrieval and distribution of health records.
- E. There is a communication system for the requesting of health records.
- F. There is an effective monitoring system whereby records can be traced within the facility at all times.
- G. The filing system allows for incorrectly filed records to be easily identified.
- H. There is provision for authorised access to health records at all times.
- I. All storage areas for health records are secured against unauthorised entry.
- J. Quality management processes are designed and implemented.

13. Information management systems are implemented and supported by sufficient personnel and other resources.

- A. Sufficient personnel support implementation of the information management system.
- B. Decision-makers and others are provided with appropriate training in the principles of information management

14. The hospital has a process to aggregate data for user needs.

- A. The hospital has a process to aggregate data.
- B. Clinical and managerial data and information are integrated as needed to support decision making.
- C. Aggregated data and information are used to support patient care.
- D. Aggregated data and information are used to support management of the hospital.
- E. Aggregated data and information are used to support the quality management programmes.
- F. Appropriate data is collected and used to study areas targeted for improvement.
- G. Appropriate data is collected and used to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of interventions implemented to achieve improvements.
- H. The results of these monitoring activities are communicated to the leaders and governance structure of the hospital and to other relevant stakeholders, such as departmental personnel responsible for the process under consideration.

15. The hospital contributes to external databases

- A. The hospital has a process to participate in and/or use information from external databases.
- B. Data or information is contributed to external databases as required by law or regulation, where applicable.
- C. Notifiable diseases are reported within an acceptable time frame, according to hospital policy.
- D. The hospital compares its performance with that of other, similar hospitals, using external reference databases.

CHAPTER-15

HUMAN RESOURCES (HR)

1. Human resource management support

- A.** A designated individual is responsible for providing support for the hospital's human resource strategy.
- B.** The human resource manager is suitably qualified and experienced in human resource management.
- C.** The human resource manager ensures that policies and procedures are available to guide personnel and that they are implemented.
- D.** The responsibilities of the human resource manager include ensuring compliance with labour legislation and regulations.
- E.** The human resource manager uses information on staffing needs provided by clinical and managerial personnel to ensure adequate provision of personnel for service delivery.
- F.** Details of the hospital's absenteeism, sickness rates and personnel turnover rates are recorded, analysed and presented to senior management to inform relevant decision-making processes.
- G.** Details of the personnel establishment are recorded and analysed to allow for informed decision making by the hospital's management.
- H.** Receptionists, telephonists, clerical support personnel and porters are allocated to wards and departments in accordance with service delivery requirements.

2. Human Resource Planning

- A.** Human resource planning supports the organisation's current and future ability to meet the care, treatment and service needs of the patient.
- B.** The organisation maintains an adequate number and mix of staff to meet the care, treatment and service needs of the patient.
- C.** The required job specification and job description are well defined for each category of staff.
- D.** The organisation verifies the antecedents of the potential employee with regards to criminal/negligence background.
- E.** There are documented processes for staffing the hospital.
- F.** The processes include personnel recruitment.
- G.** The processes include the numbers and categories of personnel required.
- H.** The processes include the selection and documentation of desired education, qualifications, experience, skills and knowledge for each personnel member to be recruited.
- I.** The processes include assignment and reassignment of personnel.
- J.** The processes include personal development of personnel.
- K.** The processes include measures to improve personnel retention.
- L.** The processes include succession planning.

3. Recruitment/ Employment of staff

- A. There is a documented procedure for recruitment/ employment.
- B. Recruitment is based on pre-defined criteria.
- C. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the employment process. The effect has been assessed and it has either been concluded that the initiatives either had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.

4. Verification of personnel credentials

- A. Those permitted to provide patient care without supervision are identified.
- B. The registration, education, training and experience of all healthcare professionals is verified from the original sources where possible.
- C. The services to be provided by each personnel member are made known to appropriate individuals and units within the hospital.

5. Credentialing and privileging of medical (Doctors, dentists and chiropractors) professionals

- A. Medical professionals permitted by law, regulation and the organisation to provide patient care without supervision are identified.
- B. The education, registration, training and experience of the identified medical professionals is documented and updated periodically.
- C. All such information pertaining to the medical professionals is appropriately verified when possible.
- D. Medical professionals are granted privileges to admit and care for patients in consonance with their qualification, training, experience and registration.
- E. The requisite services to be provided by the medical professionals are known to them as well as the various departments/units of the organisation.
- F. Medical professionals admit and care for patients as per their privileging.
- G. The hospital has a policy for authorisation describing how to determine the employees assigned to clinical privileges with the necessary competences to deliver clinical services of special risk. As regards the individual employee, the policy ensures that this is assessed in connection with new appointment, and then a re-assessment takes place after set intervals. The policy describes how to relate when the hospital adopt significant new types of treatment. The policy describes how to ensure the authenticity of the documentation which makes the basis for the authorisation.

6. Credentialing and privileging of nursing professionals

- A. Nursing staff permitted by law, regulation and the organisation to provide patient care without supervision are identified.

- B. The education, registration, training and experience of nursing staff is documented and updated periodically.
- C. All such information pertaining to the nursing staff is appropriately verified when possible.
- D. Nursing staff are granted privileges in consonance with their qualification, training, experience and registration.
- E. The requisite services to be provided by the nursing staff are known to them as well as the various departments/units of the organisation.
- F. Nursing professionals care for patients as per their privileging.

7. Clinical performance and effectiveness-Credentialing and Privileges

- A. The health service organisation:
 - Conducts processes to ensure that clinicians are credentialed, where relevant
 - Monitors and improves the effectiveness of the credentialing process

8. Delegation of assigned clinical privileges

- A. The hospital has a policy for delegation of healthcare professional tasks the policy describes the hospital's overall principles for what can be delegated and how the legislation's requirements are observed.
- B. The delegation takes place in accordance with the hospital's policy.
- C. There are lists stating who is delegated for what and on which conditions.

9. Work planning

- A. The hospital defines the staff resources and competences that have present to solve specific tasks in the patient treatment.
- B. The individual departments have methods in relation to staffing in extraordinary situations where the desired staff resources and competences are not present or in case of workloads.
- C. The daily staffing is based on the determined framework defined by the hospital.
- D. Extraordinary situations are handled in accordance with the determined methods.

10. Job Description

- A. There are satisfactory job descriptions and descriptions of function.
- B. Managers and staff are familiar with their job descriptions and descriptions of function.
- C. Job descriptions are reviewed according to hospital policy.

11. Clinical performance and effectiveness-Safety and quality roles and responsibilities

- A. The health service organisation has processes to:

- Support the workforce to understand and perform their roles and responsibilities for safety and quality
 - Assign safety and quality roles and responsibilities to the workforce, including locums and agency staff
- B.** The health service organisation provides supervision for clinicians to ensure that they can safely fulfil their designated roles, including access to after-hours advice, where appropriate

12. Staff Orientation and induction

- A.** There are documented programmes for personnel orientation and induction to the hospital.
- B.** New personnel members are orientated to the hospital within a time frame determined by hospital policy.
- C.** Every staff member entering the organisation is provided induction training.
- D.** The induction training includes orientation to the organisation's vision, mission and values.
- E.** The induction training includes awareness on employee rights and responsibilities.
- F.** The induction training includes awareness on patient's rights and responsibilities.
- G.** The induction training includes orientation to the service standards of the organisation.
- H.** Every staff member is made aware of organisation's wide policies and procedures as well as relevant department/ unit/ service/ programme's policies and procedures.
- I.** Departmental and service managers implement orientation programmes for departmental and service personnel.

13. Personnel information/ Personnel file for each staff member

- A.** Personnel files are maintained with respect to all staff.
- B.** Personnel files contain the personal information of the personnel member.
- C.** All records of in-service training and education are contained in the personal files.
- D.** Personnel files contain the work history of the personnel member.
- E.** Personnel files contain job descriptions which include scope of practice.
- F.** Personnel files contain the qualifications of the personnel member.
- G.** Personnel files contain copies of any required registration certificate(s).
- H.** Personnel files contain results of all evaluations.
- I.** A designated personnel member is responsible for the storage and retrieval of personnel files.
- J.** Only authorised persons have access to personnel files.
- K.** Personnel files are standardised.
- L.** Personnel files are reviewed at least annually.

14. On-going programme for professional training (including various safety-related aspects), development and Competence development of staff

- A. A documented training and development policy exists for the staff.
- B. The organisation maintains the training record.
- C. Training also occurs when job responsibilities change/new equipment is introduced.
- D. Evaluation of training effectiveness is done by the organization
- E. Feedback mechanisms are in place for improvement of training and development programme.

15. Training on various safety-related aspects

- A. Staff are trained on the risks within the organisation's environment.
- B. Staff members can demonstrate and take actions to report, eliminate, or minimise risks.
- C. Staff members are made aware of procedures to follow in the event of an incident.
- D. Staff are trained on occupational safety aspects.
- E. The hospital has targets for the quality of the training and competence development of the staff, and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.
- F. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the training and competence development of the staff. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.
- G. The hospital has a coordinated plan for in-service training and development which is implemented.
- H. Department and service managers have established in-service training/education programmes relevant to departmental and service personnel.
- I. The hospital uses various sources of data and information to identify the in-service training/education needs of the personnel.
- J. Records of in-service training are kept for each personnel member.
- K. There are guidelines for training and competence development.
- L. Personnel competencies are assessed and recorded after in-service training according to hospital policy.

16. Clinical performance and effectiveness-Quality Improvement, Patient Safety education and training

- A. The health service organisation provides orientation to the organisation that describes roles and responsibilities for safety and quality for:
 - Members of the governing body

- Clinicians, and any other employed, contracted, locum, agency, student or volunteer members of the organization
- B.** The health service organisation uses its training systems to:
 - Assess the competency and training needs of its workforce
 - Implement a mandatory training program to meet its requirements arising from these standards
 - Provide access to training to meet its safety and quality training needs
 - Monitor the workforce's participation in training
- C.** The health service organisation has strategies to improve the cultural awareness and cultural competency of the workforce to meet the needs of its Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander patients

17. Continuing education, research and other educational experiences to acquire new skills and knowledge and to support job advancement.

- A.** There is a development strategy for the hospital which ensures that managers receive the training required to fulfil their responsibilities.
- B.** There is a training strategy for the hospital which ensures that all personnel update their knowledge and skills regularly.
- C.** Personnel are informed of opportunities to participate in advanced education, ongoing training and research, and acquire postgraduate qualifications relevant to the services provided by the hospital.

18. Performance appraisal

- A.** A documented performance appraisal system exists in the organisation.
- B.** The employees are made aware of the system of appraisal at the time of induction.
- C.** Performance is evaluated based on the pre-determined criteria.
- D.** The appraisal system is used as a tool for further development.
- E.** Performance appraisal is carried out at pre-defined intervals and is documented.
- F.** Key performance areas for each personnel member are identified in their job descriptions.
- G.** The performance of individual personnel members is reviewed when indicated by the findings of quality improvement activities.
- H.** There is at least one documented evaluation of each personnel member each year or more frequently as defined by hospital policy.
- I.** New personnel members are evaluated as defined by hospital policy.

19. Industrial relations based on current labour legislation

- A.** There are mutually agreed processes for the satisfactory conduct of industrial relations activities, which meet the requirements of current legislation.

- B. There are recognition agreements with trade unions and/or health professional organisations, where applicable.
- C. Disciplinary procedures are implemented.
- D. Grievance procedures are implemented.
- E. Dispute and appeal procedures are implemented.

20. Disciplinary and grievance handling policies and procedures

- A. Documented policies and procedures exist.
- B. The policies and procedures are known to all categories of staff of the organisation.
- C. The disciplinary policy and procedure is based on the principles of natural justice.
- D. The disciplinary and grievance procedure is in consonance with the prevailing laws.
- E. There is a provision for appeals in all disciplinary cases.
- F. The redress procedure addresses the grievance.
- G. Actions are taken to redress the grievance.

21. Health needs of the employees

- A. A pre-employment medical examination is conducted on all the staff
- B. Health problems of the employees are taken care of in accordance with the organisation's policy.
- C. Regular health checks of staff dealing with direct patient care are done at least once a year and the findings/results are documented.
- D. Occupational health hazards are adequately addressed.

22. The department/ service implements processes that support employee rights during care.

- A. There are processes that support employee rights during care.
- B. Measures are taken to protect the employee's privacy, person and possessions.
- C. The personnel respect the rights of employees to treatment and to refuse treatment.

23. Each service is managed to ensure the provision of a safe and effective service

- A. A designated individual is responsible for each service
- B. The service manager ensures that policies and procedures are available to guide the personnel and that they are implemented.
- C. The manager plans and implements an effective organisational structure to support his/her responsibilities and authority.
- D. The responsibilities of the manager and personnel are defined in writing.

CHAPTER-16
CONTINUOUS QUALITY IMPROVEMENT (CQI)

- 1. There is a structured quality improvement and continuous monitoring programme in the organisation.**
 - A. The quality improvement programme is developed, implemented and maintained by a multi-disciplinary committee.
 - B. The quality improvement programme is documented which is comprehensive and covers all the major elements related to quality assurance.
 - C. There is a designated individual for coordinating and implementing the quality improvement programme.
 - D. The quality improvement programme promotes and demonstrates use of innovations to improve process efficiency and effectiveness.
 - E. The designated programme is communicated and coordinated amongst all the staff of the organisation through appropriate training mechanism.
 - F. The quality improvement programme identifies opportunities for improvement based on review at pre-defined intervals.
 - G. The quality improvement programme is a continuous process and updated at least once in a year.
 - H. Audits are conducted at regular intervals as a means of continuous monitoring.
 - I. There is an established process in the organisation to monitor and improve quality of nursing care.

- 2. There is a structured patient-safety programme in the organisation.**
 - A. The patient-safety programme is developed, implemented and maintained by a multi-disciplinary committee.
 - B. The patient-safety programme is documented.
 - C. The patient-safety programme is comprehensive and covers all the major elements related to patient safety and risk management.
 - D. The scope of the programme is defined to include adverse events ranging from "no harm" to sentinel events.
 - E. There is a designated individual for coordinating and implementing the patientsafety programme.
 - F. The designated programme is communicated and coordinated amongst all the staff of the organisation through appropriate training mechanism.
 - G. The patient-safety programme identifies opportunities for improvement based on review at pre-defined intervals.
 - H. The patient-safety programme is a continuous process and updated at least once in a year.
 - I. The organisation adapts and implements national/ international patient-safety goals/solutions.

3. Managers and leaders work collaboratively to develop, implement and maintain effective risk management systems in the hospital.

- A. Hospital-wide risk management systems are developed and implemented.
- B. The risk management team develops and maintains a risk register for the hospital.
- C. Risk management processes include documented plans and actions to eliminate or reduce the identified risks.
- D. Risk management processes include ongoing documented monitoring of risks.
- E. Management and leaders ensure the development and implementation of documented policies and procedures for risk management processes and activities.
- F. Ongoing in-service training of all personnel in these policies, procedures and risk management principles, including reporting of adverse events, is documented.
- G. One or more qualified and/or skilled and/or experienced individuals supervise the implementation of the risk management system.
- H. A system for monitoring near misses/adverse events/sentinel events is available and includes the documentation of responses to recorded incidents and interventions to prevent recurrence of the incident or minimise harm in the event of a recurrence.
- I. The hospital has a policy for communicating relevant information to patients affected by adverse events and sentinel events, including the outcome of investigations.
- J. Analysed data, including near misses, adverse events and sentinel events is used to monitor the effectiveness of the risk management system.
- K. Risk management systems are reviewed and the risk register updated whenever there are changes in hospital systems and processes, or physical facilities.

4. As part of risk management, an occupational health and safety system is implemented in accordance with current legislation.

- A. Policies and procedures on all aspects of health and safety that guide personnel in maintaining a safe work environment are implemented.
- B. Management makes provision for occupational health services according to a documented policy framework.
- C. The person(s) providing the Occupational Health Service has access to a qualified Occupational Health practitioner.
- D. The hospital provides information and training on risks specific to the healthcare workers.

5. A formalised proactive quality improvement approach is maintained in the service.

- A. Indicators of performance are identified to evaluate the quality of treatment and patient care.
- B. There are formalised quality improvement processes for the service that have been developed and agreed upon by the personnel of the service.
- C. The quality improvement cycle includes the monitoring and evaluation of the standards set and the remedial action implemented.
- D. A documentation audit system is in place.
- E. Incidents relating to complaints about the linen management are recorded and acted upon using quality improvement methodology.
- F. The pharmacy has a system in place to monitor the appropriate use of antibiotics within the hospital.
- G. Data relating to medication errors and adverse drug reactions is used to improve medication management within the hospital and monitor the effectiveness of actions taken to prevent recurrence of such events.
- H. The quality improvement cycle includes the monitoring and evaluation of the standards set and the remedial action implemented.

6. The department/service implements risk management processes -Human Resource, Medical/ Surgical/ Paediatric and Obstetric Care)

- A. The department conducts ongoing monitoring of risks through documented assessments as part of the hospital's risk management processes.
- B. A system for monitoring near misses/adverse events/sentinel events is implemented, which includes the documentation of responses to recorded incidents and interventions to prevent recurrence of the incident or minimise harm in the event of a recurrence.
- C. Relevant personnel are trained in the procedures relating to the reporting and investigation of near misses/adverse events/sentinel events.
- D. Security measures are implemented to ensure the safety of patients, personnel and visitors.
- E. Fire safety measures are implemented.
- F. Hospital policy on handling, storage and disposal of healthcare waste is implemented.
- G. Aids are available for manual handling of heavy goods.
- H. Ladders are available where required.
- I. The operating department team participates in the hospital's surveillance of surgical capacity, volume and results.

7. Risks to the health and safety of personnel, employees or visitors are assessed and control measures introduced in order to minimise or eliminate risk and promote safety.

- A. Occupational health personnel are included in the assessment of risks to the health of employees attached to any work.
- B. Occupational health personnel have access to and utilise consultative services associated with evaluating workplace hazards such as industrial hygiene, workplace toxicology, ergonomics and epidemiology.
- C. There are monitoring mechanisms to ensure that employees adhere to safe systems of work, including the use of protective clothing.
- D. Vulnerable groups of workers are identified.
- E. Where there is risk of injury, it has been determined whether it is possible to avoid manual handling, or to provide mechanical aids in place of the latter.
- F. There is a mechanism to ensure that employees are aware of risks and their consequences.
- G. Documented information on the safe handling and storage of hazardous substances is available and provided to the management of the hospital.
- H. First aid is available to employees.
- I. A system for the monitoring of near misses/adverse events/sentinel events is available, which includes the documentation of interventions and responses to recorded incidents.
- J. Security measures are in place and implemented to safeguard and protect employees, personnel and visitors.
- K. Fire safety measures are implemented.
- L. Hospital policy on handling, storage and disposal of healthcare waste is implemented.

8. Patient Safety in patient care

- A. Management ensures proactive risk management across the organisation.
- B. Management provides resources for proactive risk assessment and riskreduction activities.
- C. Management ensures implementation of systems for internal and external reporting of system and process failures.
- D. Management ensures that appropriate corrective and preventive actions are taken to address safety-related incidents.

9. Patient safety and quality systems Policies and procedures

- A. The health service organisation uses a risk management approach to:
 - a. Set out, review, and maintain the currency and effectiveness of,

- policies, procedures and protocols
- b. Monitor and take action to improve adherence to policies, procedures and protocols
- c. Review compliance with legislation, regulation and jurisdictional requirements

10. The hospital improves the safety and prevents injuries at patients. This includes that the hospital identifies and prevents risks and injuries and that the hospital learns from adverse events.

- A. The hospital has a policy for patient safety and risk management. The policy describes risk management and the effort of reporting and learning from adverse events, including near-misses. Furthermore, the policy describes how intersectorial events are handled.
- B. The hospital describes and substantiates which risks are made subject of a special assessment and effort.
- C. The hospital conducts risk assessments of the selected risks and launches initiatives based on the analyses.

11. The quality improvement programme is supported by the management.

- A. The leaders at all levels in the organisation are aware of the intent of the quality improvement program and the approach to its implementation.
- B. The management makes available adequate resources required for quality improvement programme.
- C. Organisation earmarks adequate funds from its annual budget in this regard.
- D. The management identifies organisational performance improvement targets.

12. Applying quality improvement systems

- A. The health service organisation applies the quality improvement system from the Clinical Governance Standard when:
 - a. Monitoring the delivery of comprehensive care
 - b. Implementing strategies to improve the outcomes from comprehensive care and associated processes
 - c. Reporting on delivery of comprehensive care
- B. The health service organisation applies the quality improvement system from the Clinical Governance Standard when:
 - a. Monitoring the effectiveness of clinical communication and associated processes
 - b. Implementing strategies to improve clinical communication and associated processes
 - c. Reporting on the effectiveness and outcomes of clinical communication processes
- C. The health service organisation applies the quality improvement system from the Clinical Governance Standard when:

- a. Monitoring processes for partnering with consumers
- b. Implementing strategies to improve processes for partnering with consumers
- c. Reporting on partnering with consumers

13. The organisation identifies key indicators to monitor the clinical structures, processes and outcomes, which are used as tools for continual improvement.

- A. Monitoring includes appropriate patient assessment.
- B. Monitoring includes safety and quality-control programmes of all the diagnostic services.
- C. Monitoring includes medication management.
- D. Monitoring includes use of anaesthesia.
- E. Monitoring includes surgical services.
- F. Monitoring includes use of blood and blood components.
- G. Monitoring includes infection control activities.
- H. Monitoring includes review of mortality and morbidity indicators.
- I. Monitoring includes clinical research.
- J. Monitoring includes patient safety goals.
- K. The organisation identifies and monitors priority aspects of patient care.

14. The organisation identifies key indicators to monitor the managerial structures, processes and outcomes, which are used as tools for continual improvement.

- A. Monitoring includes procurement of medication essential to meet patient needs.
- B. Monitoring includes risk management.
- C. Monitoring includes utilisation of space, manpower and equipment.
- D. Monitoring includes patient satisfaction which also incorporates waiting time for services.
- E. Monitoring includes employee satisfaction.
- F. Monitoring includes adverse events and near misses.
- G. Monitoring includes availability and content of medical records.
- H. The organisation identifies and monitors priority managerial activities in the organisation.

15. There is a mechanism for validation and analysis of quality indicators to facilitate quality improvement.

- A. There is a mechanism for validation of data.
- B. There is a mechanism for analysis of data which results in identifying opportunities for improvement.
- C. The opportunities for improvement are implemented and evaluated.

- D. The organisation uses appropriate quality improvement, statistical and management tools in its quality improvement programme.
- E. Feedback about care and service is communicated to staff.

16. There is an established system for clinical audit.

- A. Medical and nursing staff participates in this system.
- B. The parameters to be audited are defined by the organisation.
- C. Patient and staff anonymity is maintained.
- D. All audits are documented.
- E. Remedial measures are implemented.

17. Incidents are collected and analysed to ensure continual quality improvement.

- A. The organisation has an incident reporting system.
- B. The organisation has established processes for analysis of incidents.
- C. Corrective and preventive actions are taken based on the findings of such analysis.
- D. The organisation shall have a process for informing various stakeholders in case of a near miss / adverse event.

18. Sentinel events are intensively analysed.

- A. The organisation has defined sentinel events.
- B. The organisation has established processes for intense analysis of such events.
- C. Sentinel events are intensively analysed when they occur.
- D. Corrective and preventive actions are taken based on the findings of such analysis.

19. Integrating clinical governance

- A. Clinicians use the safety and quality systems from the Clinical Governance Standard when:
 - a. Implementing policies and procedures for recognising and responding to acute deterioration
 - b. Managing risks associated with recognising and responding to acute deterioration
 - c. Identifying training requirements for recognising and responding to acute deterioration

20. The patient is identified prior to any health activity.

- A. There are guidelines for patient identification
- B. There are guidelines determining method and responsibility to ensure correct page and indication of right and left-sided image in accordance with referral before image is produced.
- C. The staff knows when to make patient identification.

- D. Patients are identified according to the described procedure and method.
- E. Correct page and indication of right or left-sided image are secured in connection with imaging in accordance with the standard.
- F. The policies and/or procedures require the use of two patient identifiers unique to the patient, not including the use of the patient's room number or locations.
- G. Patients are identified before administering medications, blood or blood products.
- H. Patients are identified before taking blood and other specimens for clinical testing.
- I. Patients are identified before providing treatments and procedures.

21. The hospital develops an approach to improve the safety of verbal orders among caregivers.

- A. Policies and procedures that address the accuracy of verbal and telephone orders are implemented.
- B. The complete verbal or telephone order or test result is written down by the receiver of the order or test result, who signs as having done so.
- C. The complete verbal and telephone order or test result is read back by a second person, who signs as having done so.
- D. The order is confirmed by the individual who gave it by signing the relevant document as per hospital policy.

22. Clinical handover

- A. The health service organisation, in collaboration with clinicians, defines the:
 - a. Minimum information content to be communicated at clinical handover, based on best-practice guidelines
 - b. Risks relevant to the service context and the particular needs of patients, carers and families
 - c. Clinicians who are involved in the clinical handover
- B. Clinicians use structured clinical handover processes that include:
 - a. Preparing and scheduling clinical handover
 - b. Having the relevant information at clinical handover
 - c. Organising relevant clinicians and others to participate in clinical handover
 - d. Being aware of the patient's goals and preferences
 - e. Supporting patients, carers and families to be involved in clinical handover, in accordance with the wishes of the patient
 - f. Ensuring that clinical handover results in the transfer of responsibility and accountability for care.

23. The hospital develops an approach to improve the safety of high-alert medications.

- A. Policies and/or procedures that address the identification, location, labelling and storage of high-alert medications are implemented.
- B. High-alert medications are available only in designated departments.

- C. Measures to prevent the inadvertent administration of high-alert medications are implemented, e.g. hazard labels.
- D. Clinical practice guidelines are available to guide prescribing of high-alert medications.
- E. Patients prescribed high-alert medications are monitored for side effects or adverse drug reactions.
- F. Policies and procedures that address the management of look-alike, sound-alike medications are implemented.

24. The hospital develops an approach to ensuring correct site, correct procedure and correct patient surgery.

- A. Policies and procedures that establish uniform processes to ensure the identification of the correct site, correct procedure and correct patient are implemented.
- B. The hospital uses a clearly understood mark for surgical site identification and involves the patient in the marking process.
- C. The mark is made using ink that will not be washed away when the patient's skin is prepared for surgery.
- D. The hospital uses a process to verify that all documents and items required to perform the marking are available, correct and functional.

25. The hospital develops an approach to reduce the risk of patient harm resulting from falls.

- A. Policies and procedures to reduce the risk of patient harm resulting from falls in the hospital are implemented.
- B. Patients identified as being at high risk of falls due to their condition, diagnosis or location undergo a falls risk assessment as part of their initial assessment and following a change in condition, medication, etc. according to hospital policy.
- C. Measures are implemented to reduce fall risk for those assessed to be at risk.
- D. All falls are reported, recorded and monitored as part of the quality management system in each patient care unit.

26. Quality control procedures are in place, followed and documented in Medical Physics and Radiation Oncology.

- A. There is a quality control process for the medical physics imaging / Radiation Oncology service, which is implemented.
- B. Quality control of radiation treatments and planning are done according to accepted international and local standards. (ICRU, IAEA, etc.)
- C. Quality control includes validating test methods.
- D. Quality control includes daily surveillance of imaging results.

- E. Quality control includes rapid correction when a deficiency is identified.
- F. Quality control includes equipment maintenance/testing/safety.
- G. Quality control includes documenting results and corrective actions.
- H. External audits for quality assurance are utilised to periodically evaluate the medical physics /Radiation Oncology service.

27. Quality Improvement, Patient Safety and Performance Measurement

- A. The health service organisation uses organisation-wide quality improvement systems that:
 - a. Identify safety and quality measures, and monitor and report performance and outcomes
 - b. Identify areas for improvement in safety and quality
 - c. Implement and monitor safety and quality improvement strategies
 - d. Involve consumers and the workforce in the review of safety and quality performance and systems
- B. The health service organisation ensures that timely reports on safety and quality systems and performance are provided to:
 - a. The governing body
 - b. The workforce
 - c. Consumers and the local community
 - d. Other relevant health service organisations
- C. The health service organisation has valid and reliable performance review processes that:
 - a. Require members of the workforce to regularly take part in a review of their performance
 - b. Identify needs for training and development in safety and quality
 - c. Incorporate information on training requirements into the organisation's training system

28. Risk management (Incident Reports management systems)

- a. The health service organisation:
 - a. Identifies and documents organisational risks
 - b. Uses clinical and other data collections to support risk assessments
 - c. Acts to reduce risks
 - d. Regularly reviews and acts to improve the effectiveness of the risk management system
 - e. Reports on risks to the workforce and consumers
 - f. Plans for, and manages, internal and external emergencies and disasters
- b. The health service organisation has organisation-wide incident management and investigation systems, and:
 - a. Supports the workforce to recognise and report incidents
 - b. Supports patients, carers and families to communicate concerns or incidents

- c. Involves the workforce and consumers in the review of incidents d. Provides timely feedback on the analysis of incidents to the governing body, the workforce and consumers
- e. Uses the information from the analysis of incidents to improve safety and quality
- f. Incorporates risks identified in the analysis of incidents into the risk management system
- g. Regularly reviews and acts to improve the effectiveness of the incident management and investigation systems
- c. The health service organisation:
 - a. Uses an open disclosure program that is consistent with the National laws and regulations.
 - b. Monitors and acts to improve the effectiveness of open disclosure processes

29. Applying quality improvement systems

- A. The health service organisation applies the quality improvement system from the Clinical Governance Standard when:
 - a. Monitoring recognition and response systems
 - b. Implementing strategies to improve recognition and response systems
 - c. Reporting on effectiveness and outcomes of recognition and response systems

30. There are documented quality management and improvement processes which are implemented throughout the hospital.

- A. There is a system for the implementation of quality management and improvement processes. Managerial and clinical leaders and relevant stakeholders participate in the implementation of the quality management and improvement processes.
- B. The processes reflect the scope of service delivery in relation to managerial, clinical and support services (including formal educational services where applicable).
- C. The leaders identify priorities for monitoring activities.
- D. The documented quality improvement processes include all components of quality management activities, i.e. standard and indicator selection, monitoring, evaluation and remedial action.

31. The leaders coordinate the quality management and improvement processes and provide technological and other support.

- A. Quality management and improvement processes are coordinated among all relevant services.
- B. The leaders provide the required technology and support.
- C. There are relevant training processes to equip personnel with the necessary competencies for the design, implementation and evaluation of quality management and improvement processes.

32. Clinical processes are reviewed and the data obtained is used to drive improvements in patient care.

- A. The leaders identify key measures to monitor the quality of clinical processes.
- B. Leaders use clinical practice guidelines to guide patient care processes.
- C. Clinical audits are performed to evaluate the quality of care provided, drive improvements in service provision and monitor performance over time.
- D. Clinical processes are evaluated and the results used to drive improvements in patient care.
- E. Medical, nursing and other clinical leaders use available and relevant clinical practice guidelines in clinical monitoring as part of a structured clinical audit.
- F. Professional performance is monitored as part of clinical monitoring.

33. The quality of clinical record keeping is monitored by means of patient record audit.

- A. Patient clinical records are reviewed regularly.
- B. The review is conducted by medical, nursing and other personnel, who are authorised to make entries in patient records or to manage patient information.
- C. Records of active and discharged patients are included in the review process.
- D. Deficiencies in the quality of record keeping are addressed by appropriate interventions.
- E. The effectiveness of these interventions is evaluated as part of the ongoing monitoring of the quality of patient records.
- F. Where the use of abbreviations is permitted, a standardised abbreviation list is available.
- G. Standardised diagnosis and procedure codes are used as required by country-specific directives.

34. There are relevant managerial quality monitoring systems.

- A. Appropriate data is collected and used to study areas targeted for improvement.
- B. Appropriate data is collected and used to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of interventions implemented to achieve improvements.
- C. The results of these monitoring activities are communicated to the leaders and governance structure of the hospital.

35. Analysed data is used to improve the quality of managerial and clinical services.

- A. Clinical monitoring data is used to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of improvements.
- B. Managerial monitoring data is used to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of improvements.
- C. Clinical and managerial data and information are integrated as needed to support decision making.
- D. Comparisons are made over time within the hospital.
- E. Comparisons are made with similar hospitals, when possible.
- F. Comparisons are made with standards and desirable practices.

36. Improvement in quality is achieved and sustained.

- A. The hospital documents the improvements achieved and sustained over time.
- B. The data collected for monitoring and evaluation purposes is used to inform the development of processes to ensure that improvements are sustained over time.

CHAPTER-17
CENTRAL STERILE SUPPLY DEPARTMENT (CSSD)

- 1. CSSD is managed to ensure the provision of a safe and effective service.**
 - A. A designated individual is responsible for the sterilising and disinfecting service.
 - B. The manager ensures that policies and procedures, which include the standard intent as a minimum, are available to guide personnel in the service and that they are implemented.
 - C. The manager plans and implements an effective organisational structure to support his/her responsibilities and authority.
 - D. The responsibilities of the unit manager are defined in writing.

- 2. The unit is designed to allow for effective decontamination and sterilisation of medical equipment and supplies.**
 - A. The design of the sterilising and disinfecting unit and the layout of equipment ensure the flow of work from the soiled to the clean side of the unit.
 - B. There is a washing and decontamination area, with clean running water and a sink connected to the sewage system.
 - C. There is a pre-packing area with storage facilities for clean materials.
 - D. The autoclave area is equipped with loading and unloading trolleys at the correct height.
 - E. There is a storage area for sterile packs with racks which allow for an adequate circulation of air.
 - F. Adequate light and ventilation are available.

- 3. Effective sterilising equipment is available.**
 - A. There are one or more autoclaves or their equivalent capable of sterilising porous loads (gowns, drapes and dressings), as well as wrapped and unwrapped instruments.
 - B. Autoclaves/sterilising units are appropriate to their use and comply with licensing requirements.
 - C. Where liquids are sterilised, an autoclave with a fluid cycle and a reverse osmosis or distillation plant are also provided.
 - D. Where ethylene oxide is used as a sterilising agent, the installation complies with relevant safety standards and legislation.
 - E. The sterilising ability of each autoclave is tested daily and the results recorded in a log book.
 - F. The sterility of each pack is shown on indicator tapes, which are suited to the processes used.
 - G. Any incidents of failure of sterilisation procedures are recorded and investigated.

H. Sterilising and disinfecting unit personnel ensure that all equipment is included in the hospital's equipment replacement and maintenance programme.

4. The sterility of equipment and supplies is maintained.

- A.** There is a mechanism to ensure that sterile supplies are dated and used on a “first expired first out” basis.
- B.** The maintenance of sterility is checked before any sterile packs are issued.
- C.** There is a system for the ordering, storage, maintenance and distribution of sterile supplies.

5. A formalised proactive quality improvement approach is maintained in the service.

- A.** Indicators of performance are identified to evaluate the quality of the service.
- B.** The quality improvement cycle includes the monitoring and evaluation of the standards set, and the remedial action implemented.

CHAPTER-18

DIETARY SERVICES

- 1. The food service is managed to ensure the provision of a safe and effective service.**
 - A. A designated individual is responsible for the food service.
 - B. The food service manager ensures that policies and procedures are available to guide personnel and that they are implemented.
 - C. The manager plans and implements an effective organisational structure to support his/her responsibilities and authority.
 - D. The responsibilities of the unit manager are defined in writing.

- 2. The kitchen is designed to allow for hygienic food management.**
 - A. The food service area meets with health and safety regulations.
 - B. There are separate hand washing facilities in the food preparation area, with soap and paper towels.
 - C. The temperature, ventilation and humidity levels are controlled and monitored to ensure satisfactory working conditions and cleanliness.
 - D. There is an effective method of fly control.
 - E. There is adequate lighting and ventilation, including in the storage areas.
 - F. Refrigerators and freezers can be opened from the inside using a safety release mechanism.

- 3. The food service premises are designed to provide facilities for food handlers.**
 - A. Lockers are provided for food handlers, which can accommodate their outer clothing.
 - B. There are adequate, suitable and conveniently placed change rooms, toilets and ablution facilities for food handlers.
 - C. Ablution and change facilities are well lit and well ventilated.
 - D. Ablution facilities are kept clean.
 - E. Adequate numbers of suitable refuse containers are provided in or near each change room, hand washing and toilet area.

- 4. The therapeutic nutritional service has adequate facilities and equipment to meet the treatment needs of the population served.**
 - A. There is adequate space for dietitians/nutritionists to treat patients effectively.
 - B. Adequate and relevant equipment and materials are available to provide an effective service.
 - C. There is adequate space for the storage of equipment and materials.
 - D. Privacy is ensured through private cubicles, curtains or screens.

5. Policies and procedures guide the management of the service.

- A. The departmental manager ensures the availability and implementation of policies and procedures for the therapeutic nutritional service.
- B. There is a system in place to ensure that food handlers report conditions that may result in the transmission of infection to other food handlers or to individuals consuming food prepared in the kitchen and appropriate action is taken to prevent transmission.
- C. Policies and procedures are signed by persons authorised to do so.
- D. Policies and procedures are compiled into a comprehensive manual, which is indexed and easily accessible to all personnel.
- E. Each policy and procedure is reviewed according to hospital policy.
- F. Outdated policies and procedures are recalled and archived according to hospital/organisational policy.

6. Menus are planned and meals are prepared to meet patient needs.

- A. A suitably qualified person advises on meal development.
- B. There is a planned weekly menu, suitable for different seasons.
- C. Patients are provided with at least three meals per day.
- D. Wherever possible, patient food preferences are respected and substitutions made available.
- E. Cultural preferences are taken into account.
- F. The nutritional needs of patients without teeth and geriatric patients are considered.
- G. There are no more than 14 hours between the evening meal and the next substantial meal.

7. Food handlers maintain a hygienic food preparation environment.

- A. Food handlers wear appropriate protective clothing.
- B. There is a mechanism to prevent unauthorised individuals from entering food preparation areas.
- C. Persons not normally employed in the food service wear protective clothing while in the area.
- D. Preparation surfaces are cleaned and dried between use for different activities.
- E. Separate cutting boards are kept for raw and cooked food as well as different types of food, e.g. vegetables, meat, fish.
- F. Floors, walls and ceilings are clean.

8. Food products and meals are hygienically stored, prepared and served.

- A. Potentially high risk foods, unprepared food and prepared items are stored separately.
- B. Frozen food is defrosted in a refrigerator.
- C. Food should reach a temperature of at least 70 degrees Celsius during cooking and reheating.

- D. Food waste is placed in covered containers and removed without delay from places where food is prepared.
- E. Where the Cook-Chill Process of food preparation is used, reheating of chilled food begins no longer than 30 minutes after the food is removed from the chiller.
- F. Where the Cook-Chill Process of food preparation is used, the temperature of the heated food reaches at least 70 degrees Celsius, for not less than two minutes.
- G. Food is served within 15 minutes of reheating.

9. Food is stored under conditions which ensure security, hygiene and freshness.

- A. The manager of the food service ensures that secure storage areas are available to food service personnel.
- B. The manager ensures that the foods are checked for quality, quantity and temperature on delivery.
- C. The management ensures that the storage of food in dry storage, refrigerators and freezers complies with food hygiene regulations.
- D. Foods are stored at acceptable temperatures; thermometers are used and temperature records are maintained.
- E. Appropriate action is taken if the temperatures are persistently outside the recommended range.
- F. Foods are stored separately from non-foods.
- G. Foods are stored off the ground, on racks or shelving of an impenetrable material.
- H. Different types of food are kept separately.
- I. Stock is rotated to prevent expiry of perishable items.
- J. Pest control measures are implemented.

10. The therapeutic nutritional service is managed to ensure the provision of a safe and effective service.

- A. A designated individual is responsible for the therapeutic nutritional service.
- B. The therapeutic nutritional service manager ensures that policies and procedures are available to guide personnel and that they are implemented.
- C. The manager plans and implements an effective organisational structure to support his/her responsibilities and authority.
- D. The responsibilities of the manager are defined in writing.

11. All patients treated by dietitians/nutritionists have their healthcare needs identified through an established assessment process.

- A. Only those individuals permitted by applicable laws and regulations or by registration perform the assessments.

- B. The findings of assessments performed outside the hospital are verified on admission.
- C. Patients are reassessed at intervals appropriate to their conditions, care plans, individual needs or according to hospital policies and procedures.

12. The care provided to each patient is planned and written in the patient's record.

- A. Clinical practice guidelines, relevant to the patients and services of the hospital, are used to guide patient care processes.
- B. The implementation of guidelines is monitored as part of a structured clinical audit.
- C. Guidelines are reviewed and adapted on a regular basis.

13. Nutrition and hydration

- A. The health service organisation that admits patients overnight has systems for the preparation and distribution of food and fluids that include nutrition care plans based on current evidence and best practice
- B. The workforce uses the systems for preparation and distribution of food and fluids to:
 - **Meet patients' nutritional needs and requirements**
 - **Monitor the nutritional care of patients at risk**
 - **Identify, and provide access to, nutritional support for patients who cannot meet their nutritional requirements with food alone**
 - **Support patients who require assistance with eating and drinking**

14. Documented policies and procedures guide nutritional therapy.

- A. Documented policies and procedures guide nutritional therapy including assessment and reassessment.
- B. Nutritional therapy is planned and provided in a collaborative manner.
- C. There is a written order for the diet.
- D. Patients receive food according to their clinical needs.
- E. Food is prepared, handled, stored and distributed in a safe manner.
- F. When families provide food, they are educated about the patient's diet limitations.
- G. The hospital has targets for the quality of the effort for patients with nutritional risk, and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.
- H. The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality for patients with nutritional risk. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.

15. Food and nutrition therapy appropriate for the patient and consistent with his or her clinical care is regularly available.

- A. Food appropriate to the patient is regularly available.
- B. Food orders appropriate for the patient's nutritional status and needs are documented in the patient's record.
- C. Wherever possible, patient food preferences are respected and substitutions made available.
- D. When families provide food, they are educated about the patient's dietary limitations.
- E. Patients assessed as being at nutritional risk receive nutrition therapy.
- F. A collaborative process is used to plan, deliver and monitor nutrition therapy.
- G. Nutrition therapy provided, whether oral, enteral or parenteral, is documented in the patient's record.
- H. Response to nutrition therapy is monitored and recorded.

CHAPTER-19

LINEN SERVICES

- 1. The linen management service is managed to ensure the provision of a safe and effective service.**
 - A. A designated individual is responsible for the linen management service.
 - B. The linen management service manager ensures that policies and procedures are available to guide personnel and that they are implemented.
 - C. The manager plans and implements an effective organisational structure to support his/her responsibilities and authority.
 - D. The responsibilities of the service manager are documented.

- 2. Where there is a laundry on site, the department is designed to allow for safe and effective processing of linen.**
 - A. The space in the laundry is adequate to deal with the calculated or estimated dry weight of articles to be processed and the type of washing equipment.
 - B. The laundry facilities comply with the requirements of the standard..
 - C. The laundry provides a clear flow of laundry from the soiled to the clean side with no crossover of these lines.
 - D. Trolleys, bins, vehicles or other equipment used for the transport of linen bags are designed to avoid damage to linen and to be cleaned easily.
 - E. Clean overalls, aprons, gloves and footwear for on-site sorting of used linen are provided and correctly used.
 - F. Adequate hand washing facilities are provided.
 - G. Washing machines are fitted with water level gauges or dip gauges and the quantity of water is regularly checked.
 - H. The size and number of washing machines are adequate to meet the number of loads per hour, including peak loads.
 - I. Ironers/laundry presses are adequate to ensure the processing of laundry items without undue delays.
 - J. The machine cage volume is specified by the manufacturer.
 - K. Loads are regularly weighed.
 - L. Washing machines are fitted with thermometers, which are tested every 6 weeks and calibrated every year.

- 3. Where there is no on-site laundry, the linen-bank facilities allow for efficient handling of linen.**
 - A. The arrangement between the hospital and the off-site laundry clearly states the responsibility for sorting, counting, collection and delivery of linen.
 - B. Where sorting takes place on site, there is a clear flow of linen from the soiled to the clean side with no crossover of these lines.

- C. Trolleys, bins, vehicles or other equipment used for the transport of linen bags are designed to avoid damage to linen and to be cleaned easily.
- D. Clean overalls, aprons, gloves and footwear for on-site sorting of used linen are provided and correctly used.
- E. Soiled linen sent to the off-site laundry is sorted into bags (or other acceptable containers) which clearly indicate the contents.

4. Linen stock control mechanisms are implemented.

- A. Access to the laundry/linen-bank is controlled.
- B. There is a method of accounting for the numbers of different linen items sent for laundering.
- C. There is a process to verify the numbers and physical condition of linen items sent and received.
- D. A record is kept of linen issued.
- E. Secure storage facilities are available.
- F. There is an inventory of all linen stored.
- G. Records are audited.
- H. All losses are investigated, reported and recorded.

CHAPTER-20
HOUSEKEEPING SERVICES (HK)

- 1. The housekeeping service is managed to ensure the provision of a safe and effective service.**
 - A. A designated individual is responsible for the housekeeping service.
 - B. The housekeeping service manager ensures that policies and procedures are available to guide personnel and that they are implemented.
 - C. The manager plans and implements an effective organisational structure to support his/her responsibilities and authority.
 - D. The responsibilities of the service manager are defined in writing
 - E. Pest control measures are implemented.

- 2. Facilities and equipment are adequate to provide a safe and effective cleaning service.**
 - A. Secure storage areas and well-maintained equipment are available to housekeeping personnel.
 - B. Chemicals for cleaning are safely stored out of the reach of patients, children and visitors.
 - C. Chemicals for cleaning are securely and accurately labelled.
 - D. There is adequate storage place for brooms and mops.
 - E. Mops and brooms are cleaned and dried before being stored.
 - F. Cleaning cupboards are adequately ventilated.
 - G. Soiled linen is placed in bags designated for that purpose.
 - H. Soiled linen is stored in a secure facility.
 - I. There is a mechanism whereby the manager of the housekeeping service can communicate the current state of housekeeping-related facilities and equipment to central facility management.
 - J. Personal protective equipment (PPE) is available to housekeeping personnel to protect them from infection and the potentially harmful effects of chemicals used in the course of their duties.

- 3. The housekeeping personnel work with the infection control committee to ensure safe waste disposal.**
 - A. Waste is segregated in accordance with documented controls.
 - B. Housekeeping personnel use colour-coded charts (or other suitable coding) to identify the colour of bag and type of container appropriate to the type of waste generated.
 - C. Waste is protected from theft, vandalism or scavenging by animals.
 - D. Waste is collected at appropriate times so that hazards are not caused.

CHAPTER-21

OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH

- 1. The Occupational Health Service is managed to provide the personnel and resources required for an effective service.**
 - A. A designated person is responsible and accountable for the management of the Occupational Health Service.
 - B. There is an adequate number of personnel to provide for the needs of the Occupational Health Service.
 - C. Occupational health personnel have the necessary and appropriate training, credentials and skills to carry out their responsibilities.
 - D. Occupational health personnel participate in continuing medical education in occupational health.
 - E. Occupational health personnel have appropriate access to a physician with expertise and credentials in occupational health care.

- 2. The mission statement and overall policy of the Occupational Health Service reflect current international best practice.**
 - A. The Occupational Health Service has an overall policy that contains as a minimum a mission statement.
 - B. The policy is authorised by senior management.
 - C. The policy is clearly displayed within the department, communicated to all employees and available to all interested parties.
 - D. The policy is reviewed at appropriate intervals as determined by the department, but at least every three years.
 - E. The services to be offered are consistent with the mission of the department.
 - F. The services to be provided are described in the strategic plans of the department.

- 3. Where students are trained as part of undergraduate or postgraduate programmes, the Occupational Health Service ensures formal training.**
 - A. There is a designated member of the personnel of the Occupational Health Service who coordinates student training.
 - B. The training programme is structured in accordance with the guidelines of the appropriate registration body and training facilities.
 - C. Training periods are recorded and evaluated.

- 4. The functions of the occupational health practitioners are provided in accordance with ethical and professional practices and legal requirements**
 - A. Occupational Health Services are provided in accordance with relevant standards promulgated by local, provincial and national guidelines, laws and regulations.

- B. Copies of relevant laws and regulations are available and readily accessible.
- C. Legislation is reviewed regularly at a frequency determined by the hospital but at least every three years and the reference records updated accordingly.
- D. When outdated legislation is retained for future reference or research purposes, it is clearly marked as outdated, removed from the current reference documentation and stored in such a way as to guard against unintended use.

5. The hospital provides appropriate medical care to the employees of the hospital and/or organisation.

- A. Occupational Health Service personnel are informed of the potential workplace hazards for each employee.
- B. Occupational Health Service personnel have ready access to appropriate reference materials regarding occupational health care.
- C. Where routine medical care is offered to employees by the Occupational Health Service, medical complaints by employees are differentiated in terms of workplace-related complaints and other medical conditions.
- D. The management of medical conditions includes consideration of the relationship of the employee and the medical condition to the workplace environment and work practices.
- E. The management of medical complaints includes consideration of the employee's fitness to continue present work practices.
- F. The management of medical complaints includes consideration of any disability that may have been sustained.
- G. The management of an acute injury includes measures to minimise disability and return the employee to an optimal functional state as soon as possible.
- H. Employees are screened for mental health issues that may arise from working conditions, illness or disability and are managed appropriately.
- I. Records reflect both screening for and management of mental health issues.

6. Details of the hospital's and/or organisation's absenteeism and sickness rates are recorded and analysed to allow for informed decision making by the senior management team.

- A. Employees who are absent from work are evaluated to ensure that they have regained sufficient health to be returned to their particular work place.
- B. Such evaluation includes, but is not limited to, the extent and duration of the condition that caused the absence from work.
- C. Such evaluation includes, but is not limited to, the extent and duration of potential hazards that may affect the employee's health.

D. Analysis of employee absenteeism and sickness provides data for risk management planning, for example analysis of back injuries causing employee sickness and absenteeism.

7. The Occupational Health Service has an appropriate medical surveillance programme, which meets the needs of the population served.

A. The health surveillance programme is appropriate for the health risks to which employees are exposed.

B. The data collection process is designed to provide information that can be used in determining measures to eliminate, control and minimise the health risks to which employees are exposed.

C. There is an effective employee recall system to ensure that employees are seen at appropriate intervals.

D. Personnel responsible for the development and implementation of the health surveillance programme are appropriately trained and updated.

E. Records of each employee under surveillance are appropriately stored and managed in accordance with hospital policy relating to management of information and appropriate legislation.

F. Records are available to the employee upon request.

G. Employees are aware of their right to access their records relating to the health surveillance programme.

H. Pre-employment examinations are conducted that consider the health of the individual and the requirements of the prospective workplace.

I. Pre-termination examinations are conducted when employees leave the employ of the hospital and/or organisation to provide accurate information on their state of health on departure.

J. Lifestyle habits (weight, diet, exercise, alcohol and/or tobacco use, etc.) are assessed when potential exposure to hazardous agents may be affected by those habits.

8. The Occupational Health Service builds capacity in the workplace through the provision of information, education and counselling services.

A. The Occupational Health Service works with the personnel of other health services, non-governmental organisations and local governmental structures to provide health education and build capacity within the workforce.

B. Posters are displayed in relevant areas within the hospital.

C. HIV counseling and screening services are offered with due regard for confidentiality.

D. Information provided is appropriate for the language/s and comprehension of the population served.

- 9. There is a system to ensure that reports and records are efficiently managed with due regard for confidentiality.**
- A.** There is documented evidence that occupational health practitioners write reports on occupational health-related issues.
 - B.** There is documented evidence that occupational health practitioners write letters and serve notices to remedy occupational health problems.
 - C.** There is documented evidence that occupational health practitioners record and file health-related statistics and evaluate trends.
 - D.** There is documented evidence that occupational health practitioners complete questionnaires from an occupational health perspective.
 - E.** There is documented evidence that occupational health practitioners provide reports and comments on inspections, complaints, investigations.
 - F.** There is documented evidence that occupational health practitioners compile occupational health report forms.
 - G.** There is documented evidence that occupational health practitioners utilise standard or prescribed occupational health report forms or recording systems in respect of inspections, investigations and work of a recurring nature, e.g. notifiable medical conditions.
 - H.** Personal information about an employee that is unrelated to the ability to perform the specified job safely is handled in a confidential manner.
 - I.** Signed consent is obtained from employees prior to the release of any employee-related information.
 - J.** Current versions of relevant documents and information are available at all locations where operations essential to the effective functions of the Occupational Health Service are performed.